

D2.3 Social-ecological system analysis

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Lead authors: Julia Neidig and Liam Ó Riada (BC3)

Contributors: CES, CER, MRU, UBB, UGOT, UNICT, UT, WR

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

At the core of this deliverable are the analyses of the social-ecological systems that shape the framing and lens through which BIOTraCes' target cases are studied. The deliverable zooms onto nine case studies that are culturally, politically, ecologically, and geographically diverse in terms of the rich diversity of contexts of European landscapes. The objective of this deliverable is to better understand the complex interplay of how values, types of knowledge, power dynamics, decision-making processes, ecological processes, institutional (e.g. market) dynamics and multi-level governance frameworks do shape the dynamics of social-ecological relationships, interactions, and co-dependencies. The thick description of each of the nine SES also aims to shed light on current blockages and potentials for transformative change, focusing specifically on power relationships and dynamics within the different cases that evolve from both local and broader institutional/governance, including market-led policy and regulatory frameworks.

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1 Introduction and outline

Authors: Julia Neidig, Liam O’Riada, Unai Pascual

At the core of this deliverable are the analyses of the social-ecological systems (hereafter: SES) that shape the framing and lens through which BIOTraCes’ target cases are studied. The deliverable zooms onto nine case studies that are culturally, politically, ecologically, and geographically diverse in terms of the rich diversity of contexts of European landscapes. The objective of this deliverable is to better understand the complex interplay of how values, types of knowledge, power dynamics, decision-making processes, ecological processes, institutional (e.g. market) dynamics and multi-level governance frameworks do shape the dynamics of social-ecological relationships, interactions, and co-dependencies. The thick description of each of the nine SES also aims to shed light on current blockages and potentials for transformative change, focusing specifically on power relationships and dynamics within the different cases that evolve from both local and broader institutional/governance, including market-led policy and regulatory frameworks. For this end, each research partner conducted a SES analysis based on the methodological approach to data collection applied in their fieldwork and following a common BIOTraCes SES framework. These SES analyses are further embedded into the case study reports (D2.5) and build the base for the WP3 deliverable, specifically under task T3.1.

In the following, we briefly describe how this deliverable has been created, thereby embedding its framing and choice of approach in BIOTraCes’ overarching conceptual and methodological roadmap ([Section 2](#)). This is followed by a presentation of the overall conceptual BIOTraCes SES framework that allows for process-relational perspective on the nine case studies and their prevalent SES. These analyses focus on the description of local SES as dynamic and constantly changing systems of relations embedded into higher impact sectors ([Section 3](#)). [Section 4](#) dives into the nine case studies by presenting thick and locally contextualised narratives of these nine SES while also proposing an alternative vision of what the SES could be. [Section 5](#) concludes with an overall discussion on key findings derived from the nine SES analyses, focusing on the need of shifting the way we value, know and talk about biodiversity from instrumental towards relational approaches and of shifting power from higher scales and impact sectors towards local communities through co-governance of social-ecological systems. We finally conclude with insights from approaching social-ecological systems as systems of relations and processes.

2 How this deliverable was created

Authors: Julia Neidig, Liam O’Riada, Unai Pascual

2.1 Drawing on previous BIOTraCes deliverables

The SES analyses build upon and draw on the following BIOTraCes deliverables: D1.6, D1.7, and D1.8:

D1.6 works as a guidance document through the plurality of theories and frameworks conceptualising the relationships, interactions, processes and dynamics between, in the broadest sense, the social and the ecological. While not being exhaustive, it reflects the epistemic plurality and diverse expertise within the BIOTraCes consortium. By proposing frameworks embedded into diverse schools of thought, we aimed to offer flexibility for the use of plural interpretations of nature-society relations emerging from the case studies while avoiding a top-down definition of a single approach to understanding what a SES implies.

To allow for comparability across the different theories and frameworks, D1.6 explores how each theory or framework conceptualizes society-nature relationships and interactions, examines underlying power relations that may challenge or enable transformative change and offers conceptual pathways for the inclusion of marginalized perspectives, values, and identities. It further offers an entry point into how different SES theories and frameworks shed light on the four PEPE principles at the heart of BIOTraCes (i.e. Pluralising, Empowering, Politicising, and Embedding).

D1.8 describes the BIOTraCes overarching methodology to cross-case analysis and across-case synthesis, including a flexible approach for the SES analyses. Here, D1.8 identifies broadly four main clusters of SES approaches:

- *A SES approach that can incorporate grounded theory on all sorts of relations between the social and the ecological.*
- *A SES approach that is based on a holistic view of nature and that gives a counterweight to a technical and reductionist approach.*
- *A SES that does not look from the social to the ecological or vice versa, but one, based on system theory, that focuses on reciprocal inter-relationships.*
- *An approach embedded in sustainability sciences focused on systems approaches and that is also associated with the biodiversity-science-policy interface (IPBES).*

Of further relevance is the tension described in D1.8 resulting from the use of grounded theory in the cases and application of theoretical concepts that bring along a compelling theoretical framework, such as encountered in different approaches towards SES analyses. Acknowledging this tension is important, as it impacts how BIOTraCes interprets and analyses SES across very diverse cases and contexts. The consortium hence decided to primarily look at **SES as systems of relations**. These relations can exist between and across different logics of power related to different actors and institutions (norms and rules), impact-sectors, people, nature, economy, culture, ideologies, frames and the more than human, etc. (D1.8, p.42).

Given the spirit of BIOTraCes that has been developed towards a more grounded-theory approach to data collection and analysis in the different case studies to understand society-nature relationships in the context of diverse cultural, political, economic, or ecological processes, we chose a different approach to understanding ecological and biophysical processes than initially described in the task description of the proposal. Here, we draw specifically on D1.7, in which project partners consider that *"it is key to understand how nature works and functions. This forms the foundation of ecological literacy as it provides a critical foundation for making informed and sustainable decisions about how we live, how we grow and develop our communities and settlements, and how we address the environmental and socio-economic issues with which we are confronted. Ecological literacy involves the capacity to know and understand places as ecological systems, including how they function and connect with other systems. To achieve a nature-positive society, it is imperative to substantially increase the ecological literacy of our societies, including that of the lay citizens, decision makers and scientists."* (p.11).

That is, instead of proposing a rigid list of standardized biodiversity indicators (e.g., species richness, richness of species with high conservation value out of the total species richness, richness of invasive species), as initially suggested and mentioned in the DoA (Description of work) as regards task T2.3, we decided to adapt the focus by addressing a specific *biodiversity challenge* that is linked to a core feature of each of the SES prevalent in the different case studies and for whose governance the creation and enhancement of local ecological literacy is key. Here, special attention has been paid, for example, to the specific

local and institutional framing of nature or biodiversity (loss) or ecosystems. The biodiversity challenge has been selected based on relevant information or/and secondary data that was already available and accessible to the research partners, e.g., through the societal partners or other relevant actors.

2.2 A common approach within WP2

Given the connectedness of the different WP2 deliverables, WP2 developed a coherent and collective approach to the collection of the relevant information from BIOTraCes partners for each deliverable. Each WP2 task hence had a dedicated section in the monitoring forms developed under T2.1 to gather for the tasks' relevant information throughout the case study designs and implementations. The SES analyses are further parts of the overarching case study reports (D2.5) where a more expansive description of each case study can be found. This collective approach was chosen to facilitate reporting on each case study and to avoid – where possible – redundancies between the different WP2 deliverables.

2.3 D2.3 specific project activities

Embedded in this overarching WP2 approach, T2.3 conducted two workshops with the research consortium at two of the project live meetings, and several meetings with relevant BIOTraCes research partnership members. These task-specific activities served to adapt the task and its deliverables to the case study contexts, preliminary findings and the methodological approaches applied.

A **first workshop** was conducted at the second live project meeting in Mértola (**May 2024**) with at least one representative of each research partner. The main objective was to define a core set of common SES aspects (social and ecological) that would form the building blocks of the SES analyses. The following components based on previous literature and BIOTraCes deliverables were suggested by the lead team:

- Knowledge, science-based vs. other forms of knowledge.
- Values, e.g. instrumental, relational and intrinsic values.
- Power: to, with, and over.
- Institutions (norms, rules), in the case study and in the high impact sector.
- Cultural aspects shaping human-nature relationships.
- Narratives, discourses, paradigms regarding society-nature-relations, e.g. dominant vs. marginalized narratives of the broader impact sectors and the local context.
- Economic structures: market structures, finance, economic barriers.
- Decision-making processes: how and by whom decisions are being made and implemented, (power) relationships between different (institutional) actors.
- Main biodiversity challenge identified in each case study.
- Main methods and approaches used to assess the biodiversity challenge status and trend in the case study context.
- Multi-scale perspective: Review of available data on the chosen biodiversity component/challenge in the context of the broader impact sector.
- Types of knowledge on the chosen biodiversity component/challenge informing/impacting governance processes in the case study context.

The lead team proposed the following discussion questions: Which common components should be added/removed from the social perspective? Which common components should be added/removed from the ecological perspective? Are there primary and secondary SES components?

BIOTraCes partners responded that it may be misleading to open the discussion on SES components with a differentiation of the social and ecological dimension. This may create a separation between society and nature, while the core idea is to understand the interplay and co-dependencies of human-nature relationships while overcoming a conceptual divide of nature and society. Hence, BIOTraCes' interpretation of the different SES in each case study should be focused on the relationality of the different core components, coming back to D1.8's interpretation of SES as "systems of relations".

Workshop participants discussed that instead of having a fixed BIOTraCes SES framework, an approach would be needed that allows for flexibility. The proposal was to work with reflexive and guiding questions that point to several possible SES components such as those presented by BC3 initially.

A collective decision was made to approach to the SES analyses through the creation of nine SES narratives, focusing on, first, what is there that is important in the current SES, second, what influences what is important, third, what could be, and forth, what would be needed. Following, each SES narrative would then describe the status quo of the SES, the underlying drivers, an alternative future vision, and possible strategies or pathways to get to alternative plural nature-positive SES.

Following this proposal, the lead partner then developed a new roadmap and SES conceptual approach for the completion of this deliverable (see [Section 3](#)). This final framework is also the outcome of the bilateral iteration and feedback from specific research partners.

In **May 2025** at the third consortium live meeting that took place in Hungary, a **second workshop** was conducted, again with a least one representative of each research partner. The objective of this workshop was to get a first picture of the nine different SES and the changes that occurred from the past to the present, leading towards positive visions of the future. The researchers were invited to select and present two photos that indicated *changes in the case studies' SES, either positive or negative, from the past to present*. Photo 1 represented the SES before the biodiversity innovation (in the past) and photo 2 depicted its current state to date (during/after the intervention). Researchers were asked about the changes that did occur in the SES due to the biodiversity innovation.

The second part of this workshop consisted in envisioning positive, nature-inclusive futures for the SES of the different case study. For this envisioning exercise, we used the method of "postcards from the future". Researchers were asked to write postcards from the future following the prompt: "How do we imagine the ideal SES in 2045? We put ourselves into the shoes of our case studies niche innovators in the year 2045 and write a postcard from their perspectives addressed to us, the BIOTraCes researchers. In those postcards, we can read about all the positive changes that occurred in the 2 decades after BIOTraCes finished, about e.g. transformed or deepened relationships between communities and nature, plural values, biodiverse landscapes, new forms of economic activities and decision-making. The postcards were used as an inspiration to write the vision of an alternative social-ecological system in each local context, that can be found in the nine SES narratives in [Section 4](#).

3 Social-ecological system analysis: common approach and framework

Authors: Julia Neidig and Unai Pascual

3.1 What do we mean by Social-Ecological System?

In BIOTraCes we define a **SES as a *system of relations*** composed of linkages, interactions and interdependencies of social and ecological domains and their diverse components, including human and non-human actors. Those are shaped, inter alia, by cultural, political, social, economic, and ecological factors. Society and nature are linked via complex processes and relations, in which different manifestations of power through discourses, social structures and ecological processes are central in any understanding of the transformative potential of and within the SES. For example, different social and ecological power manifestations can either lead to lock-ins or leverage transformative change. In this deliverable, we hence aim to better understand the complex interplay of the SES components, the factors driving its changes over time and scale, and the processes and relations that are shaping the state of the SES, to identify barriers, lock-ins and enablers of transformative change in the local case study contexts and the higher impact sectors those cases are embedded in.

The social-ecological relations of the systems are shaped by human and non-human actors, some of which act as niche innovators by implement transformative innovations that target specific biodiversity challenges. Those innovators face diverse root causes of biodiversity loss, lock-ins, and barriers that may complicate a long-term successful biodiversity innovation locally and across higher scales. However, certain aspects of the SES can also act as enablers that facilitate a pluralising, empowering, politisizing, and embedding of transformative innovations within social-ecological relations and processes. Both lock-ins and barriers, but also enablers of transformative change can be found, for instance, in power and decision-making dynamics shaping the SES (e.g. bottom-up or top-down), laws, regulations, and standards on the (supra-)national, regional, local level and in the high impact sectors, plural human-nature values (such as instrumental, relational, and intrinsic ones), different types of knowledges (such as technical, experimental, or traditional), biophysical and ecological processes (e.g. native and invasive species, climate change, biodiversity loss) or the broader paradigms and economic structures of the high impact sectors (such as nature conservation/restoration, smart/green growth/sustainability fix, industrialised agriculture) (see Figure 1).

By zooming onto these different aspects of a SES and understanding their interactions with each other, we apply a process-relational epistemological and ontological lens (Hertz et al., 2020; Garcia et al., 2020a), following what West et al. (2020) call the "relational turn in sustainability science". That is, instead of understanding SES through the entities that together form the system and that exist independently of processes or relations, as e.g. found in substance ontologies, we understand SES as primarily built from interdependent processes and relations, including the interactions of the different system components listed above and their linkage with a variety of human and non-human actors. It follows then that SES is understood as a whole and composed by diverse relationships across different components that are inherently dynamic and change and adapt as relationships and processes unfold (Garcia et al., 2020a). Applying a relational lens to analysing SES can further shift environmental governance of complex systems towards practices more attentive to the local context and conditions assuring changes in the SES are social-ecologically just (Kenney-Lazar et al., 2023).

Approaching a SES by emphasizing the focus on occurring processes and relations can help to overcome various challenges inherent to SES research, as described by Garcia et al. (2020b), through “(i) integrating the social and ecological, (ii) better accounting for complexity, (iii) better accounting for dynamics across scales (time and geographical), and (iv) better combining/integrating different knowledge systems” (ibid, p2). The BIOTraCes SES framework presented here aims to contribute to these goals especially by drawing closer attention to the PEPE principles. For instance, focusing on processes and relations in the SES helps directing attention to the importance plural values and knowledge may play in framing and making decisions regarding the biodiversity challenge, both in the SES and the high impact sectors. Further, it can help elicit and shed light on dynamics that enable the inclusion of some types of values and knowledges while marginalizing others, hence disentangling potential barriers and enablers for *pluralising for transformative change*.

Understanding the diverse social and ecological communities and their power relations that shape significantly the state of the local SES is further key to highlight the different agencies to enable change from the bottom-up and from within the power structures while shedding light onto marginal communities’ values, knowledges and perspectives and their inclusion or exclusion from the discursive framing and decision-making regarding the SES. Naming these inclusion and exclusion mechanisms is hence precondition for *empowering* to occur (see e.g. Charli-Joseph et al., 2018).

BIOTraCes’ SES analyses further highlight the embeddedness of local SES in broader scale structures, both institutional and economic. Paying closer attention to the many ways higher scale paradigms influence local actions and strategies is crucial for the identification of opportunities for amplifying the biodiversity innovation’s impact across scale and for enabling an *embedding* in institutional governance structures. Lastly, drawing attention to the multiple entanglements of the social and the ecological by pointing towards those, often marginalized, human-nature perspective aiming to overcome human separation from nature and including them in policy-making debates, processes of *politisizing* can emerge shifting human-nature relations from being an apolitical, technocratic discussion towards being at the centre of the SES and its decisions. This ultimately can support the creation of SES narratives that build on thick descriptions of the local context and multiple social-ecological relations existent in it (Vigliano Relva and Jung, 2021).

Figure 0. BIOTraCes’ conceptual framework of social-ecological systems.

3.2 SES analysis – a practical guide for each case study

This section provides a practical guide that helped operationalize the BIOTraCes SES framework into nine thick contextualized narratives of the processes and relationships of many of the SES aspects that shape the local system and its barriers and enablers. To develop the case studies' SES narratives, consortium partners drew on the data collected via participatory action research applying a mixed method approach best fitted to the respective case study context (see deliverable D2.1: Case study plan – selection of methods and triangulation). Following the more detailed description of each case study context and the status quo of the SES that can be found in D2.5 chapter 3 "case study contextualization", each SES narrative examines the SES dynamics, interactions and relations and alternative future visions of plural nature-inclusive SES. For the writing of the SES narrative, **project partners were guided by the following prompts and guidance questions therein:**

A) What influences how local SES are formed, framed, and governed?

1. SES impact on different actor groups: How are the case study's different actors group impacted by the SES?
2. Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups: How are the different case study's actor groups (social and ecological) deciding over the state of the SES? E.g., how are decisions regarding the SES being made and implemented? What are the relationships between different decision-making actors? What are power dynamics, including power imbalances in the decision-making process?
3. Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing: How are the case study's different types of knowledge regarding the biodiversity challenge informing and impacting governance processes in the case study context? On which types of knowledge are the case studies' dominant biodiversity framings based (e.g., science-based, local, or traditional knowledge)?
4. Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss: How does the SES function and how do we understand it (focus on ecological processes)? What are direct drivers of biodiversity loss in the case study?
5. Values underpinning decision-making processes: How are specific values informing and shaping the policy- and decision-making processes?
6. Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics: Considering the i) political, ii) cultural and iii) institutional power dynamics, how do those power relations impact the type of knowledge, values, and overarching narrative used in the governance of the local SES?
7. Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector: How do the impact sector's institutions (e.g. norms and rules) and overarching narrative of the biodiversity challenge impact the local SES and how it is governed?
8. Economic structures' impact over the SES: How do economic structures (market structures, finance, economic barriers) influence the SES?
9. Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector: How is the locally identified biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends assessed (e.g. methods and types of data) in the broader impact sector?
10. Current enablers and barriers for transformative change: Considering questions 1-9, how is the current SES enabling and/or constraining transformative innovation options? What elements of the SES can be considered opportunities/ leverages or barriers for transformative change?

B) Vision: What are alternative visions, framings, narratives, forms of governance for the local SES?

To transform current human-nature relations and related SES narratives, alternative imaginaries about SES are needed, both in the local context and in the broader impact sector, that move beyond the business as usual. This section serves as a closing of the SES narrative, a short envisioning of what could be and can hence be understood as a “vision of the future” describing alternative perspectives on human-nature relations identified in the case studies: What are alternative visions, framings, narratives, forms of governance for the local SES? Focus could here be e.g. on transformed and/or deepened relationships between different social and ecological actors; new understanding of “nature-positivity”; transformed lifestyles; integration of plural types of knowledge and values in decision-making processes; transformed power relations and dynamics, transformed institutions, norms, rules; alternative economic/ market structures; transformed understandings of biodiversity challenges, their assessment and broader society-nature relations, etc.

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4 BIOTraCes' 9 Social-ecological systems

This chapter contains the nine SES narratives that offer a thick description of the processes and relations shaping the state of the local SES that BIOTraCes' biodiversity challenges are embedded in. After a short description of the case studies, each SES narratives zooms onto (i) the SES impact on different actor groups, (ii) decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups, (iii) types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing, (iv) ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss, (v) values underpinning decision-making processes, (vi) and political, cultural and institutional power dynamics. The SES are then analysed through embedding them (vii) in their corresponding high impact sectors, (viii) the broader economic structures, (ix) the assessment of the biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector, before then identifying (x) current enablers and barriers for transformative change. Each SES will conclude with an alternative vision of an SES that enables the PEPE principles and with a final discussion of the main aspects of the SES analysed.

4.1 Urban Schoolyards-Biodiversity Lab, Spain

Authors: Julia Neidig and Liam Ó Riada (BC3)

This case study is about schoolyard greening in public pre- and primary schools in Vitoria-Gasteiz, Basque Country, Spain. In concretely, it follows the implementation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program initiated in 2022 as a response to a manifesto of the municipal associations of parents demanding healthier and greener school environments a year earlier. Administrated by the city hall and funded by different public grants, as of 2025 14 schoolyards have been renaturalized through replacing hard with permeable, natural surfaces such as sand and soil and the adding of plants, trees, and lawn areas, nature-based play equipment and garden elements. The process was implemented through a collaboration of different municipal entities and, in various degrees, together with the educational communities of the different schools.

We zoom on to the various challenges derived from a combination of complex administrative structures and responsibilities scattered across different institutional entities, plural imaginaries attached to the role of schoolyards in education and urban planning, and a diversity of actors involved and needed to make the schoolyard interventions successful. Concretely, we disentangle the various challenges, but also potentials of the current program structure together with multiple actors to envision a schoolyard greening program in future, where biodiversity and equity are at center of the design, use, and narrative of the schoolyard.

The overarching research objective is to explore to what extent green schoolyards can be part of a wider transformative change towards a (bio)diverse society. For this end, we applied a participatory action research approach in close collaboration with BIOTraCes societal partner, the Environmental Studies Center of Vitoria-Gasteiz, and the municipal Department of Education leading the program. We further collaborated with representatives of the local educational communities, the main recipients of the schoolyard transformations.

We draw on document and archival data as well as field- and workshop-based data. We found that the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program in its current state of governance, regulations, and broader paradigms contains both barriers and opportunities for transformative, nature-inclusive change in the social-ecological system. The multi-level governance embedded in two high impact sectors of urbanism and education with their

past and current dominating paradigms is still based on unequal (power) relations resulting from rigid and complex top-down structures and furthering human disconnection from nature. However, as actors active in schoolyard transformations navigate these barriers, their initiatives can be considered challengers to current lock-ins.

Overall, we encountered throughout our research a relational narrative shift. This can be seen, e.g., in a variety of actors' stronger emphasis on care as being learned and practiced in the schoolyards towards other peers and nature. This shift implies longer participatory processes, potentially enabling a deeper integration of educational communities into the decision-making process in a way that their concrete needs are at the heart of the schoolyard transformations. The process of learning between institutional and educational community actors has already led to an adaptation of processes to overcome previous shortcomings, leverage current program successes, and respond to the educational communities' feedback. This shows potential for an adaptive co-governance form in future of municipal schoolyard greening.

This document focuses on the case study's transformative biodiversity innovations, including an analysis of inclusion and exclusion mechanisms, niche innovators and key players, scalable bottom-up innovations, and an initial mapping of interventions.

4.1.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

Understanding urban schoolyards as social-ecological systems (SES) includes looking at them as nested socio-ecological configurations embedded into the wider urban system, i.e. as part of a neighborhood (and city and region and so on) with its communities, infrastructures, networks, governance, and nature. Each school with its yard can hereby be considered a single SES. All the SES of the different schoolyards together make another SES on the city-wide scale, and so on. In the following description we focus on the SESs of urban schoolyards, on the smallest scale, the individual school, and on the city-wide scale – the municipal governance of the different schools; nested into multiple governance layers across local-to-global policy scales. Schools and their green yards are important places where relationships between children and their community and nature are formed and shaped. Concretely, schoolyards as SES are, among other things, relational places for learning and playing, for the creation of social cohesion and community and places of biodiverse habitats and hence are important places to build strong connections and bonds between the social and ecological, that are needed for a long-lasting sustainable and nature-inclusive society.

The SES of urban schoolyards, here focusing on those belonging to public pre- and primary schools, are thereby shaped by governance frameworks of two overarching, multi-level public sectors, namely the urban planning and the educational sector. Those sectors with their overarching paradigms are enormously shaping the way schoolyards are seen and governed. In both sectors, there is a tendency to understand the social and the ecological as separate units, with an overall emphasis on the social as prior to the ecological. This becomes apparent in the human- and adult-centered approaches and framings of both education and nature/biodiversity and their respective governance based on dominant values (instrumental) and forms of knowledge (scientific/technical). Both sectors have further been identified in previous literature as drivers of the extinction of experiences in and with nature and to further disconnection of society from nature. That is, to overcome this distinction and hierarchization of society and nature, new forms of social-ecological relationships need to be formed and included in the way we understand and govern the SES of an urban schoolyard embedded in an urban community. In the following, we describe the current state of the SES of urban renaturalized schoolyards.

Figure 1. Mapping the social-ecological system of urban schoolyard greening with institutional actors (Workshop, June 2023).

4.1.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

The SES of a schoolyard impacts the multiple actors involved in the biodiversity innovation differently. Overall, in this case study, we identified in previous sections two broader actor groups: Institutional and educational community actors. Institutional actors, while shaping the governance framework and holding the decision-making power, are the ones least impacted by the state of the current SES. Meanwhile, educational communities and their surrounding neighborhoods are the ones directly experiencing its impacts. Educational communities comprise the children and their families, parents’ associations, teachers and other educators, and school employees such as cafeteria and maintenance staff. Children are thereby at the center of the biodiversity innovation and hence most affected by the state of the schoolyard. As for now, the status quo of public schoolyards’ designs can be described as grey, asphalted areas with a dominance of spaces for competitive sports. These schoolyard designs, first, increase children’s vulnerabilities towards climate change impacts, especially heat; second, further inequalities in access to and use of space in relation to gender, (dis)abled bodies, and socio-economic background, and third, are not sufficiently responding to children’s needs, including safe and sustainable learning and play environments.

The literature on renaturalization of schoolyards points to a multiplicity of positive impacts with the promise of generating long-term sustainable relationships between younger generations and nature/biodiversity. Applying an intersectional lens, those benefits include increased gender equality and social inclusion by enabling access to urban nature and green recreational and educational spaces for children belonging to marginalized

communities, nature-inclusive learning spaces enabling deeper human-nature connections through early-on contact with and care for nature, green child-centered infrastructures, increased resilience towards extreme weather events (e.g. heat), and increased social cohesion at the neighborhood level, by understanding schoolyards as a community space open and accessible to a broader public (see e.g. Chawla et al., 2014; Raney et al., 2023, Frisk and Larson et al, 2011; Cilliers et al., 2024). What remains an issue in the current state of the SES is the uneven distribution of these positive impacts that disadvantages those children and educational communities of more vulnerable and marginalized backgrounds as they face structural barriers to participate in design and implementation, access, use, and maintenance of transformed and green schoolyards. As for now, parents are considered a core driver in assuring that benefits of renaturalized schoolyards reach their children. That is, schools attended by families holding less resources and capacities to get involved in the schoolyard governance process are less likely to experience their full benefits.

Second, a core component of the SES of urban schoolyards is its educational aspect. For that, teachers and educators play an important role in realizing the potentials of renaturalized schoolyards by using them as a resource and space of creative and embodied learning. Given the current education paradigm, that is mostly driven by classroom-based learning aiming for standardized and indicator-based evaluations of pupils (such as in PISA assessments), teachers often lack both resources and knowledge of how to integrate schoolyards holistically throughout the curriculum. While there are more trainings and materials available for teachers, they report on many structural, administrative, and practical constraints hindering the implementation of a more child-centric, embodied and experiential style of teaching steering towards closer human-nature relationships, including evaluation pressures, safety and insurance concerns, families with diverging values and expectations regarding education (Ó Riada et al., forthcoming; Workshop 1, February 2025; Workshop 2, April 2025). Nonetheless, the role of teachers for assuring that the benefits of the green schoolyards reach all children, regardless of their genders, (dis)abilities, or socio-economic backgrounds is essential. Teachers and educators can hence be considered as important facilitators of the biodiversity innovation.

Third, there are increasing calls to understand the SES of an urban schoolyard as part of the wider neighborhood, that is, as an urban park that can be used after school hours by diverse neighborhood community members (Flax et al. 2020; Stevenson 2020). This would move the understanding that schoolyards merely belong to pupils attending the respective school towards a meeting place that can enhance social and intergenerational cohesion at the neighborhood level. Despite most schoolyards still being closed after schooling hours for humans, the wider neighborhood is nonetheless already profiting from the renaturalization efforts, in form of increased biodiversity in the neighborhood as green schoolyards are embedded into a network of green spaces and corridors offering habitat and space for movement of more-than-human actors (Clauzel et al. 2025). Although mentioned as a long-term objective of schoolyard greening, as for now, administrative hurdles, open questions about responsibility and insurance, the fear of vandalism, and lacking political will (in form of an increased budget for maintenance) are often put forward as a reason for why most schoolyard have not been opened for a broader public yet (Workshop 2, April 2025).

4.1.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

Processes of decision-making are highly complex as different aspects of the schoolyard governance are scattered across different public bodies on the municipal and regional level. Decision-making thereby follows mostly a top-down logic, whereby municipal and regional policymakers allocate necessary funds and decide over the criteria for their use. In the specific case of the schoolyard program, those funds are coming from two regional ministries (of education and health), and from the city hall, that is, requirements for how to use those funds may differ according to the funding body which complicates their use on the school level. The municipal administration has a certain, yet limited, leverage of adapting the implementation of those funds to the realities of the schools. The municipal administration further holds the authority over physical transformations of the school environments of the urban public pre- and primary schools. Concretely, in this case study, the municipal administration could decide the criteria for the schoolyard interventions. However, the decisions over which schools to intervene at and how much funding to allocate are coming from the councillors of the city hall. Consequently, there is a lot of uncertainty in respect to the continuity of the schoolyard greening program which depends mainly on the political willingness to prioritize the improvement of degraded educational spaces, by dedicating parts of the annual city budgets to, among other things, the renaturalization of schoolyards.

The municipal school council is the formal space that should enable the participation of the municipal educational communities in the decision-making. It is designed as a space where local politicians, municipal technical staff, the educational communities (represented by teachers and parents' associations), and labor unions representing the different educational employees meet and discuss relevant topics. In practice, this space however has been criticized for not fulfilling this function. For example, the schoolyard-specific commission of the municipal school council has only met twice in 3 years. That is, the educational communities – while main recipients of the biodiversity innovation – have very little decision-making power over their schoolyards. Furthermore, if they want to enact change over their own space, they are facing complex, complicated and inefficient administrative obstacles that are hard to overcome. Little changes in the schoolyard thus require complex paperwork and agreements across different city hall departments. This challenges bottom-up initiatives on the smallest scale. Looking at the city-wide SES of schoolyards governance, there are hence clear and unbalanced power dynamics that hinder an equal participation of those actors mostly affected by the biodiversity innovation – the educational communities, and especially the children. This also challenges the long-term stability of and equality within the SES.

The current paved state of most schoolyards greatly limits the direct impact educational communities can have to introduce nature into the SES without administrative support to initiatives such as bringing plants to school or introducing raised-bed school gardens. Depaving and greening schoolyards has, however, proven to be a popular proposal in votes on participatory budgeting. A neighbourhood in Vitoria-Gasteiz thus voted to green a school in a participatory budgeting election, while most recently, greening eight schoolyards garnered the most votes in Bilbao's participatory budgeting vote¹.

¹ See e.g., <https://www.deia.eus/bilbao/2025/10/14/bilbainos-priorizan-naturalizacion-ocho-patios-10214347.html>

Participatory budgeting is thus a mechanism for broader civil society to affect municipal budget decisions towards greening schoolyards. It must be noted, however, that this can benefit already privileged neighbourhoods and schools, since these are the most likely to be organized and have the resources to put forward proposals.

4.1.1.3 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

The governance of SESs of urban schoolyards is mostly based on technical and scientific knowledge. Given the high level of institutionalization of the biodiversity innovation of schoolyard greening, it follows those “universal” types of knowledges dominating the broader urban planning sector. Technical concepts, such as nature-based solutions or ecosystem services based on a more instrumental value system and applied similarly across diverse socio-cultural contexts are thereby significantly determining the local governance. This includes both the discursive framing of the biodiversity innovation, e.g. its contribution to climate change adaptation and resilience building, but also its physical aspects, such as the choice of plants and nature-based objects to be put in the schoolyards, that adheres to international standards. (Positive) scientific evaluations of the outcomes of the schoolyard greening intervention are thereby core decision criteria for local decision-makers to decide over the prolongation of the municipal schoolyard greening program. Biodiversity’s and nature’s contributions to children are hence measured and evaluated through indicators, i.e., the dominance of technical and scientific knowledge undermines other types of knowledge, such as experiential or traditional knowledge that children and other actors receive through interactions with the environment and the community. A few initiatives, nonetheless, show the potential to shift this shortcoming. For example, adjacent to the schoolyard greening program, the municipality employs a citizen science project. While this is to generate scientific knowledge about the success of the biodiversity innovation through lay people, it also enables a process of embodied learning - and the generation of experiential knowledge -, as the participants are brought closer to interact and observe biodiversity generated by the schoolyard greening program.

When it comes to the wider education system, the Spanish educational framework, guided by frameworks of international organizations such as the OECD, has long prioritized standardized, cognitive knowledge geared towards textbook-based classroom learning. The latest education reform, however, has for the first time recognised the role of place-based, situated knowledge, and promotes transdisciplinary project-based learning, which presents an opening for novel pedagogical approaches in nature. However, since teacher training has so far been focused on transmitting disciplinary knowledge in classroom settings, these innovations will require changes in teacher training to come into practice broadly (Ó Riada et al., forthcoming).

4.1.1.4 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

The ecological aspects of the SES of urban schoolyards are very much manicured and controlled by humans. Every “natural” element is following a specific objective, mostly for human well-being, and is hence maintained if it “serves a purpose”. That is, plants are chosen for their educational or play aspects or for their resilience towards a changing climate, e.g. for their cooling effects. Hard surfaces are replaced by permeable, natural soils to allow for water drainage and cooling. Some plants or elements are also chosen as they attract insects or birds or offer a habitat for them, such as flowers or insect hotels - to enable learning in and from nature. That is, the schoolyards are also understood as embedded and connected to the city-wide green infrastructure, including urban parks,

gardens, renaturalized streets and overall green corridors that are thought to facilitate movement of urban fauna.

While biodiversity loss in cities has been driven in the last decades by urbanizations and industrialization processes, over the last two decades local efforts have been made to re-introduce biodiversity into the urban realm. However, as research participants report, locally native urban biodiversity is increasingly endangered by climate change, where many species, such as the local oak, are struggling to adapt to the higher temperatures in urban areas. Overall, the ecological components of the SES are understood through a dominantly anthropocentric lens, further strengthening a domination of nature by society. While this is the dominant view, we also identified voices throughout this research calling for schoolyard designs including “wilder” nature (=less manicured), so that children can learn about local biodiversity. That is, there are different perspectives on the ecological aspects of the SES emerging and entering the local discourse.

The manicured approach to the management of nature by the city council has recently been subject to great discussion in the face of a months-long strike of the municipal gardening department. The vast growth of urban nature this has caused has on the one hand led to many complaints towards the city council by citizens used to manicured nature, which expressed concerns about threats to public health, while sensationalist messages about snakes and ticks among the weeds have been circulating online. On the other hand, the increase in urban biodiversity caused by the lack of mowing, etc., has opened the discussion to more ecocentric perspectives on urban nature.

Interestingly, there has been a social-ecological perspective emerging as well, based not on increasing biodiversity by doing away with gardeners and leaving it to its own devices, but which combines the struggle for decent working conditions for gardening workers with improving biodiversity. In a move to reduce costs, the city council has in recent years increasingly subcontracted gardening tasks to private firms paying lower wages. These private contractors, however, lack knowledge of the local ecosystem and of which species are native or invasive, for instance. Instead, calls for the city council to again employ more specialized municipal garden workers that can promote species of interest have emerged. Apart from the higher labor costs this would entail, fears remain among the city council of a lack of understanding by citizens for measures to increase biodiversity long-term, such as protection areas from mowing. Nevertheless, the mayor has announced that the effects of the gardener’s strike are being closely monitored and due to the emerging biodiversity, a reduction of mowing cycles is being considered².

4.1.1.5 Values underpinning decision-making processes

Following the dominance of technical and scientific knowledge, instrumental values are those determining the political and discursive framing of the schoolyard greening program. Emphasis is thereby on the instrumental benefit to children, including nature’s contributions to social inclusivity, gender equality, and climate change adaptation. Specific nature-based elements are also selected under a logic of cost-efficiency (low maintenance) or for its aesthetic value. While not as dominant as instrumental values, research participants are also drawing increasing attention to relational aspects of the biodiversity

² See e.g., <https://elpais.com/clima-y-medio-ambiente/2025-06-20/una-huelga-de-jardineros-en-vitoria-provoca-una-explosion-de-flores-si-se-deja-que-se-desarrollen-las-plantas-la-biodiversidad-se-multiplica.html>

innovation. During the multi-actor workshops, participants, for instance, emphasised those values that relate (i) to human-human relationships through nature, i.e., community building, collaborative play between children, and care for each other and the broader community, etc. or (ii) to closer human-nature relationships, including care for nature and closer interactions with nature (workshop 1, February 2025). Thus, the program of renaturalization of schoolyards is not aiming primarily for an increase in biodiversity, but for biodiversity to fulfill diverse social functions, both instrumentally and relationally, intrinsic values of nature are only on the margins. The increasing focus on the schoolyards' relationality may be taken as an indication of a diversification of values in the overall narrative of the municipal schoolyard greening program, however, it remains to be seen if those relational values will also be acknowledged in the political dimension/ decision-making.

4.1.1.6 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

The SES of an urban schoolyard is embedded in a multi-level governance structure, in which higher scale regulations, but also discourses determine the local realities and possibilities. National educational laws and regional regulations and requirements for schoolyards, such as international best practices for nature-based initiatives trickle down to the local scale. Local institutional actors are then required to follow those higher scale politics and overarching narratives that, in part, do not meet the local needs and specificities. That is, to enact transformative change locally, institutional actors must navigate those higher scale politics and respond, e.g., to funding requirements that may be at odds with local needs. This leads, for example, to a bricolage approach to funding, in which multiple funding strategies are used to prolong the pilot schoolyard greening initiative locally. This enables local administrative staff to collect more evidence for the need for and importance of the biodiversity innovation that is needed to win mid-term political support, but it also limits local planners in challenging overarching, higher scale nature-exclusive narratives, logics, and structures. The dominant narrative on the governance of the SES of the Basque Governance recognizes a need for transformation of current paved schoolyards. Nevertheless, the values guiding this need for change are mainly promoting physical activity in an inclusive way that considers the diversity of pupils (cultural, ethnic, age, sexual, functional, etc.). Thus, paved schoolyards are seen as an issue because they mostly offer opportunities for competitive sport, which leads to an unequal use (especially between boys and girls) and therefore large differentials in physical activity. This perspective comes from the health department of the Basque Government, and associated funding lines therefore aim primarily at promoting physical activity in an inclusive way. Nevertheless, introducing natural elements into the schoolyards is recognized to achieve this in the guidelines for transforming schoolyards of the health department of the Basque Government (Basque Government 2019). While biodiversity is thus not prioritized in the dominant narrative, it does open opportunities, both by providing funding lines that can be used for greening schoolyards and for highlighting the role of nature in achieving social goals in schoolyards such as health and inclusivity.

4.1.1.7 Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector

In the urban planning sector, the re-introduction of nature and biodiversity to urban environments has been increasingly put forward as a solution to many urban challenges across the globe, e.g. environmental degradation resulting from the industrial city or stagnant economic growth. Following, the "green city" has thereby developed into a dominant sector paradigm to increase, first, resilience towards climate change impacts,

and second, to generate economic growth on the local scale. To operationalize this “green city”, decision-makers across scales apply a managerial, technocratic logic. In respect to the governance of the local SES - especially through urban environmental and sustainability planning, this led locally, inter alia, to an orientation of the local discourse regarding biodiversity towards what is considered “standard” and “best practice” globally, that often overrun local place-based ecological and community needs. It further led to a governance process that is mostly top-down and through a managerial approach and has been criticized for leaving too little space for real participation of residents and with that local needs and vulnerabilities are not sufficiently taken into account (Neidig et al, 2023 and 2024).

In education policy, there is a change happening in the dominant narrative, which is opening up possibilities for transformative learning in and through nature. Since the 1990s, the education policy discourse has been dominated by framings of the OECD based on human capital theory, which view education mainly as an input for economic growth and promote the standardization of education to make it comparable internationally e.g. through PISA tests and foreground the kinds of knowledge valued by markets. In recent years, however, aspects of transformative learning have entered the policy discourse, such as inviting different forms of knowledge through experiential and embodied learning, contextualization of knowledge and interdisciplinarity. This is also reflected in the current Spanish education law and curriculum, which was introduced in 2020 and to which different environmental and pedagogical renewal movements contributed. Such an opening up of the curriculum is an important precondition for integrating renaturalized schoolyards into teaching practices. Decades-long neoliberal approaches and austerity in response to the Eurozone crisis in the later 2000s / early 2010s, however, have left schools with few resources to carry out more elaborate and time-intensive transformative educational approaches and teacher training in these innovative approaches is so far lacking (Ó Riada et al., forthcoming).

4.1.1.8 Economic structures’ impact over the SES

While the SES of urban schoolyards is not directly embedded in market dynamics, it is nonetheless affected by an overall neoliberal logic that dominates both the urban and the educational sector. Following section 7, the focus of local decision-making on integrating urban nature/biodiversity can also be explained through a nonlinearization of the urban globally. Nature and biodiversity are thereby, next to its other benefits, also considered for its contribution to economic growth, e.g. through rising real estate prices and gentrification processes generated by urban greening, low-carbon, and smart initiatives. In the local case-study context, urban renaturalization, sustainable mobility, and low-carbon initiatives have been priorities of urban planning over more than two decades. Despite this local, political focus on generating a “green city” and up-valuing most of the public space, open spaces of school environments have been politically highly neglected. This may also be since school spaces are not directly linked with economic growth (instead, e.g. public green parks have been directly linked with increasing real estate prices). The covid-19 pandemic brought these shortcomings to light and helped shift attention to the urgent need of generating improved learning and play environments for the youngest, also under the lens of public health. Nonetheless, it is unclear whether this increased attention on school environments will be translated into a long-lasting governance priority.

The market-orientation of education policy due to dominant framings of education as a factor for economic growth has in the past marginalized place-based knowledge and

learning in and through nature that can happen in renaturalized schoolyards. Innovative concepts such as learning situations (situaciones de aprendizaje) introduced in the new curriculum, which emphasize transdisciplinary and experiential learning, however, now enable novel learning approaches that integrate nature into teaching.

4.1.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

Currently, nature-based solutions are dominating urban planning agendas. This is, in part, due to their expected contributions to multiple challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and societal challenges (such as increased climate vulnerabilities of marginalized communities). Given the dominance of NbS globally, vast monitoring and evaluation methods have been developed with the goal of an efficient assessment of their effectiveness in urban planning and are being applied across diverse socio-geographical contexts. As Goodwin et al. (2024) found based on a global assessment of 226 NbS initiatives, most evaluation methods focus on quantifiable, ecological indicators, as those indicators have "A history of standardization and pursuit of objectivity" (Goodwin et al., 2024, p11). Overall, there is a stronger focus on those ecological indicators relating to climate change challenges than to biodiversity challenges. Indicators used to assess NbS contributions to biodiversity are, e.g., those concerning restoration, novel ecosystems, ecosystem management, or ecosystem protection (ibid.).

One way to collect this data is for example through citizen science projects that invite residents to collect information on bird, insect, and plant species they discover around their neighborhoods. While helping to monitor the urban biodiversity, those initiatives also help to increase both awareness and knowledge about local biodiversity and its challenges. This could also help to tackle the extinction of experience and an increasing ecological illiteracy. One of the major biodiversity challenges encountered in this case study relates to human disconnection from the natural world, this also relates to lacking education regarding biodiversity. Studies conducted in the Basque Country with secondary school pupils found that children lacked important knowledge regarding native, local species, what authors called a 'Native Species Awareness Disparity' (Barrutia et al., 2022). This disparity was found even more in children growing up in urban areas than those in rural areas.

4.1.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

The SES of urban schoolyards - in its current state of governance, regulations, and broader paradigms determining the human-nature relationship - contains both barriers and opportunities for transformative change towards a nature-inclusive society. The multi-level governance embedded in two high impact sectors of urbanism and education with their past and current dominating paradigms is still based on unequal (power) relations between different social and ecological aspects of the system. However, as actors navigate the current state of the SES, their initiatives and innovations can be considered challengers to current lock-ins.

Overall, one of the strongest barriers towards transformative change of the SES of urban schoolyards lies thereby in its current top-down governance approach that, on the one hand, puts the burden of driving transformative change on educational communities facing limited resources to enact change, while on the other hand, giving them little leeway to participate in and implement their own vision of transformative schoolyard governance. That is, those mostly impacted by the state of the SES are the ones holding the least decision-making power. This governance structure further leads to an unequal distribution

of the possible benefits of schoolyard greening, whereby those with more agency to enact change are more likely to maintain the biodiversity innovation. This deepens already existing structural environmental injustices.

Concretely, lacking minimum standards for green schoolyards on the municipal (and higher) scales and too complex administrative procedures make the implementation of the biodiversity innovation more difficult. So far, there are no minimum requirements for schoolyards in terms of renaturalization. This means that greening efforts can vary significantly in their impact and may not always be distributed equally across the diverse educational communities due to lacking financial resources assuring the participation of all public municipal schools to participate in the schoolyard greening program. Hence, there is a need to establish minimum requirements across all public schoolyards. Second, the complexity of the administrative structure, with responsibilities scattered across various departments and governance levels, makes it difficult for the educational communities to implement their own initiatives, bottom-up, as they need permission from different entities with different requirements. To navigate this, educational communities need both the knowledge regarding these administrative procedures and the resources (time). This complexity effectively acts as an institutional lock-in, resisting more adaptive and inclusive governance approaches.

Another barrier determining the success of the biodiversity innovation lies in the increasing human disconnection from nature. This becomes apparent in the specific schoolyard greening program in the voices raised against schoolyard greening, e.g., for its safety concerns (children falling of trees they are climbing on or being stung by a bee) or perceived dirt (children playing in the mud as perceived as dirty, uneducated). Rejection of the schoolyard interventions is also coming in relation to the gender-inclusive design that are by some perceived as taking away opportunities for competitive sports, such as football. This disconnection is also apparent in the corresponding high impact sectors relevant for the urban schoolyard governance that are following a neoliberal paradigm that puts nature above society, as described above.

Besides these barriers, however, we encountered throughout our research a relational narrative shift. This can be seen for example in increasing calls from a variety of actors demanding a stronger emphasis on the relational value of schoolyards in their governance and political framing. This shift implies slower and longer participatory processes that enable the educational communities, and specifically the children, to partake in the decision-making process in a way that their needs and perspectives are at the heart of schoolyard transformations. There has been a visible process of learning since the start of the municipal program that led to an adaptation of requirements and processes to overcome previous shortcomings, leverage program successes and respond to the educational communities' feedback. That is, technical institutional actors already apply strategies to overcome those barriers resulting from local governance structures and can hence be considered niche innovators.

Overall, there are indications of a value and paradigm shift visible in the educational sector (see above). That is, on the national scale, the latest education law enables new forms of learning and teaching that are more tailored towards creating sustainable and caring human-nature relationships. On the local level, there are increasing calls for the educational communities to implement relational ways of teaching and learning, also in the framing of the local biodiversity innovation.

4.1.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

In this narrative of the social-ecological system of urban schoolyards, social and ecological actors, processes and relationships are considered equally important. The system is both nature- and society-inclusive. This means that relationality is at the heart of the biodiversity innovation's narrative. Schoolyards are thereby understood as those physical places that enable deep social-ecological relationships and interactions, between children, their wider (educational and neighborhood) communities, and more-than-human actors. The municipal schoolyard governance is hence designed in a way that strengthens relationality through schoolyard greening. For example, decision making is highly participatory and involves the educational communities, - and specifically the children - in the schoolyard design, implementation, use, and maintenance. Through a better integration of children in the decision-making process, children take increased ownership over the schoolyard and its different elements, moving from adult-centric to child-centric approaches. The children become stewards and carers of biodiversity, also through embodied and experiential learning.

This shift to a purely relational schoolyard also attributes more agency to biodiversity and its many more-than-human actors moving through or inhabiting the schoolyards. That is, biodiversity is not only desirable because of its many contributions to people, but because of its intrinsic and relational values. Schoolyards are thereby becoming important urban biodiversity hotspots, attracting many different native and non-native species finding safe habitat in those urban educational spaces. Plant species are thereby selected for the cultural, traditional, and intrinsic values they hold, following local and experiential knowledge next to the knowledge that has been collected through collaborative citizen science projects.

The administrative and political structure has been simplified to facilitate schoolyard greening for those educational communities that want to implement it themselves. Educational communities have the agency to enact smaller changes on their grounds without complex administrative processes. This includes an improved collaboration between institutional actors and educational communities, e.g. through regular multi-stakeholder meetings, political support for the educational communities, including continuity and stability of the program through an annual municipal budget, and political commitment to renaturalize every municipal schoolyard following common minimum requirements and concrete objectives of schoolyard greening decided by the municipal educational actors. Local political decision makers put sustainable learning environments as a political priority, following regional and national education frameworks that propose a public educational system based on values such as inclusivity and sustainability - and that enable alternative forms of learning and teaching, including on early-on training of future teachers, e.g. in universities programs.

The transformation of the SES of urban schoolyards towards a long-term sustainable, nature-inclusive biodiversity innovation includes the participation of multiple actors in the decision-making process. This involves dedicated participatory processes together with children, but also teachers to identify their needs and perspectives. Those participatory processes with sufficient time and resources dedicated to them are implemented over the course of a minimum of one school year and involve the children in the design and even in the implementation. The schoolyard governance has been rethought as a co-governance in which the specific educational communities are being given more leeway to implement initiative bottom-up. Children are taking ownership of their schoolyard starting with

designing its play and relax elements, that are mostly nature-based. They help, where adequate, in the implementation of those designs, e.g. through painting or building. Children further have a say in how to maintain and use the schoolyards, in collaboration with the broader neighborhood community.

Further, part of the municipal annual budget is dedicated to schoolyard greening. This assures that all public schools can benefit from renaturalized schoolyards that follow some minimum requirements for nature-inclusive educational spaces. That is, trees, permeable soils, water fountains, nature-based play equipment, garden areas, and flora and fauna co-inhabiting the urban schoolyard are becoming the norm of urban schoolyards designs, assuring that all children, independent from their socio-economic background, can enjoy green schoolyards. The political commitment and actions to improve the municipal public-school environments contribute over the long run to making those schools more attractive to a wider population. Children from diverse backgrounds, both local and those migrated from faraway places, are attending, playing with and learning from each other. That is, green schoolyards are one of many contributing factors to fight educational segregation. The political attention and commitment to improve public schools has also shifted the responsibility for driving change on the local scales, away from parents and teachers towards the institutional, public sector that has taken the responsibility to provide adequate governance frameworks improving the degraded situations of many schools just a few years ago.

Schoolyards are seen and governed as complex, yet fulfilling social-ecological systems. That is, they fulfill many social and ecological functions (e.g. of social cohesion, climate change adaptation or habitat for urban biodiversity), while being places where social-ecological relationships, interactions and co-dependencies manifest. Schoolyards are hence places of creative play, but also offer quiet and relaxing, and places for alone time, meeting places for the neighborhood, stimulating learning environments, and habitat for more-than-human actors

4.1.3 Discussion

The social-ecological system(s) in which the biodiversity innovation of urban schoolyard greening is embedded in are currently presented with multiple lock-ins resulting from a complex governance framework, dominating biodiversity narratives of human domination over nature that trickle down from the relevant high impact sectors of urban planning and education. Zooming on to the SES of urban schoolyards governance on the municipal scale, we can detect an imbalance in the current state of the SES. This imbalance can be found, on the one hand, between social and ecological components, and, on the other hand, between different actor groups. More concretely, there is a human domination over nature (i.e. biodiversity) and a power imbalance between institutional and educational community actors, and between educational communities of different socio-economic backgrounds.

Narratives regarding biodiversity that dominate the overarching high impact sectors have a huge impact over how the local SES is being governed. This also relates to the type of values and knowledges used to frame the local biodiversity innovation.

However, we see initiating narrative shifts that may implicate an overall paradigm shift locally, where relational aspects of the SES are coming more and more to the fore and receive a stronger emphasis. The question remains how these relational aspects, such as fostering nature connectedness in school children, can be translated into concrete policies and program schemes. To overcome issues of justice in access to green school

environments, these need to be enshrined as minimum standards for all schoolyards, instead of relying on mostly competitive funding lines. This is especially clear in the Spanish context of dual public and charter / private school system, which has led to severe school segregation and where public schools accommodate most of the children from migrant families. These schools are systemically disadvantaged in competing for funding for schoolyard greening and public greening initiatives need to focus on these most marginalized schools, while considering their situation and providing all the resources needed.

The broad recognition across both civil society and local and regional governance of issues of gendered use of space that paved schoolyards cause is an important leverage point towards a generalized paradigm shift in viewing schoolyards. This has triggered a wide agreement for the need to transform these spaces. While green elements are a clear part of visions for transformation of schoolyards in both policymaking and civil society, there is a need to elevate the role of nature and especially intrinsic and relational values of nature. This is especially important in the policy narrative which is framed within the perspective of Nature-based Solutions and therefore disproportionately highlights instrumental values of nature.

Another leverage point that is changing the vision for schoolyards is the need to adapt to climate change. While this is still not a central motivation in Vitoria-Gasteiz due to its comparably mild climate within Spain, schoolyard greening in cities further south in the country such as Barcelona is principally motivated by the need for climate shelters. Climatic considerations in the design of schoolyards are therefore likely to increase in the future as temperatures rise. However, these examples have also shown tendencies towards framing nature narrowly as a Nature-based Solution or technical 'fix' for the problem of heat islands in schoolyards. To be transformative, greening intervention must therefore be seen as a leverage point in itself for triggering a holistic rethinking and remaking of the school. Further opportunities for leverage here are the new education law and curriculum, that opens up opportunities for integrating nature into teaching through innovative learning approaches, as well as the fact that schools need to integrate the schoolyard in the schools 'educational project', giving them the opportunity create a new nature-inclusive narrative and mission statement.

The main barrier constraining these leverage points from triggering a generalized change in schoolyards is inertia in the standards for schoolyard design both at the regional and national level. These standards still prioritize cost-efficiency and therefore lock in paved schoolyard designs due to their easy and thus cheap maintenance. Without changes in these standards that recognize nature's benefits for the inclusiveness of schoolyards, climate adaptation, sustainability education and nature-positivity, change towards green schoolyards will not be generalized. Transformation is therefore currently limited to the municipal scale. At this scale, participation and local co-governance is an important leverage point, since greening interventions have only proven to be successful if they directly responded to the needs of the individual school.

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4.2 Traditional Herder's Knowledge, Hungary

Authors: Bálint Sándor and Zsolt Molnar (CER)

The Hungarian BIOTraCes team works closely with traditional herders, whose knowledge and practices are essential for maintaining Hungary's grasslands. Of the country's one million hectares of grassland, around half a million require grazing to preserve their exceptional ecological value. These ancient, species-rich habitats depend on extensive, well-timed, and skilfully managed grazing—something only experienced herders can provide. Yet the number of herders is rapidly declining, not because their work is obsolete, but because society and key sectors such as conservation and agriculture overlook their indispensability. As socio-ecological and economic pressures intensify, herders must continuously adapt, drawing on both inherited and newly developed knowledge. The project therefore explores how tradition-based innovations can support pastoral communities and strengthen their role in biodiversity conservation.

The case study aims to identify pathways for revitalizing pastoralism, shifting societal perceptions of herders, and improving the regulatory and support systems shaping their work. Pastoralism is an ancient, adaptive profession, but recent policy and administrative changes—often intended as support—have made it more difficult to practice. Today, herders' contributions remain undervalued, even though their management of livestock and pastures sustains biodiversity and produces high-quality foods derived from plants inedible to humans. Proper grazing is one of the few agricultural activities that enhances biodiversity rather than undermining it. In a context of accelerating climate change, the adaptability of pastoralism and the depth of traditional ecological knowledge make it vital for Hungary's future.

The research spans the entire country, documenting herders' knowledge, connecting communities across regions, and encouraging forms of self-organisation that strengthen their collective voice. This is the first national effort to foster broad professional cooperation among herders, at a moment when pastoralism faces existential threats. Working with an internally diverse and historically marginalized group raises important ethical considerations: researchers must build trust, respect cultural boundaries, and acknowledge the social isolation many herders experience. Particular attention is given to supporting older herders, encouraging young people to enter the profession, and working with the recently established Hungarian Women Herders Group.

The team has organized "Forum of Hungarian Herders" meetings to facilitate dialogue with policymakers and other stakeholders, sparking new ideas and helping clarify long-standing challenges. International exchanges have further broadened herders' perspectives and stimulated technological and organisational innovation. Emerging examples suggest that meaningful transformation is possible but preserving traditional ecological knowledge and enabling its evolution require long-term support.

In sum, herders today face not only ecological change but also shifting regulations, social expectations, and economic pressures. Safeguarding biodiversity and food security in Hungary depends on strengthening pastoralism. Supporting a new generation of "conservation herders" is therefore central to the transformative aims of this project.

4.2.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

The most serious problem facing the national and international agricultural and nature conservation environment is that there is a desire to separate and treat differently the landscape and the people who live and work in it, and especially those who maintain it. However, with the gradual elimination of activities that maintain the landscape, the values

and characteristics that need to be protected and preserved are disappearing at an increasingly rapid speed. In our case study, although most herders and farmers are unfamiliar with and do not refer to the concept of the SES system, they nevertheless seek solutions and formulate demands within this theoretical system.

In Hungary, decision-making has been moving away from the SES over the last two hundred years, and this trend is continuing under the current agricultural and nature conservation decision-making activities. In fact, they maintain a system based exclusively on financial and economic indicators, which does not even attempt to interpret the system created by the combination of landscape and people. This problem has several components: the flaws of international regulatory and support systems; corruption, bureaucracy, and cosmetic arrangements; and a complete lack of interest and, in many cases, incompetence. The basic principles of SES are best understood by those working at lower levels in nature conservation and agriculture on the one hand, and by local communities on the other; for natural reasons, they are the most sensitive audience in practice.

The direct drivers of biodiversity loss in the case study can be classified into several types. First, we could consider natural processes, but given the history of the Carpathian Basin, we cannot speak of natural processes in the past. The current situation has been shaped most significantly by almost a thousand years of extremely significant and, to this day, increasingly intense human landscape formation. In the case of the SES, the ideal vision for the future is to keep the landscape alive. If the landscape is not alive, it is impossible to live with it, nor is it possible to use its resources in a balanced way. So, we must start from the basic needs of the landscape: in terms of the regulatory background, water management and soil restoration are the first and most important issues! Once activities to restore the functioning of the landscape have been stepped up, the next step is to help the people who currently live in the landscape to acquire the traditional ecological knowledge and practices that do not fundamentally interfere with the functioning of the landscape yet provide resources and livelihoods for those who live there. We are attempting to collect a segment of this knowledge, the ecological and livestock-related knowledge of traditional herders and the innovative solutions based on this knowledge, within the framework of our case study, and then prepare it for later social use.

4.2.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

In general, in European cultures - but also specifically in Hungarian regulatory and support practices - there is a general societal perception of the need to separate the functioning of nature from the human environment and its impacts. This situation, however, is almost incomprehensible in our time. A social-ecological approach does not currently exist in Hungary, but rather only through the work and research of a few individuals is attempting to draw attention to the role and importance of this way of thinking and value system. The most serious problem of the Hungarian and international agricultural and nature conservation environment is that they want to separate the landscape from the people who live, work and specifically maintain it. To take a concrete example, they want to maintain Hungary's protected grasslands of natural value - which are also cultivated landscapes - by making it impossible and excluding the human landscape-forming and landscape-maintaining activities that have been present there for hundreds of years, for example by severely restricting grazing. It is precisely the values and features that need to be protected and maintained that are disappearing at an increasingly drastic rate as the activities that sustain the landscape are gradually being eliminated. In our case study, herders and some farmers, although mostly unaware of and not naming the concept of the SES system, are looking for solutions and formulating demands within this theoretical

system. Some conservation professionals have encountered the concept itself and even understand and perceive its importance. Yet the implementation of the regulatory environment obliges them to do the exact opposite in the practice of their work. In most cases, the infrastructure and staff involved in decision making and implementation have little or no theoretical knowledge or understanding of its importance. Thus, in fact, there is no comprehensive link between SES and the participants in our case study, or in Hungarian society in general.

4.2.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

Several of the social and ecological actors identified in D2.5 (contextualization chapter 3) have decision-making power over the state of SES in our case study. As discussed earlier, we can distinguish several distinct segments in terms of the regulatory environment:

In Hungary, the Ministry of Agriculture is responsible for enforcing general international standards for agriculture and animal husbandry and for establishing and maintaining harmonization of national legislation. Although the activities of the Ministry of Agriculture do not cover the principles of the SES at all, its infrastructure is the most authoritative in matters concerning agriculture and nature protection. At the same time, there has been an extremely flawed decision-making process over the last two hundred years, which has tended to move away from the SES, and which has continued at an accelerated pace under the current Ministry of Agriculture. In fact, they maintain a system that thinks solely in terms of financial and economic indicators, which does not even intend to interpret the system of landscape and people. This problem is made up of several parts: failures in the international regulatory and support systems; corruption, bureaucracy and spectacular measures; a total lack of interest and, in many cases, incompetence.

The same can be said of national and EU nature conservation legislation. The regulatory and maintenance environment for nature conservation also falls under the Ministry of Agriculture. Within this institution, the Department of National Parks and Landscape Protection is responsible for the harmonization of nature conservation legislation. However, there is also a very strong dominance of agricultural approaches and interests in nature conservation issues and practices. The National Park Directorates are merely the managers of public assets (nature reserves and the movable and immovable property and livestock needed to carry out their functions), playing an executive role in the system. Thus, there is no substantive intermediate infrastructure formally able and capable of driving the practical implementation of the system towards SES principles. Although there are conservation rangers and other persons in the National Parks system who are very close to the SES approach, their powers of intervention are unfortunately very limited. As a result, they can only assist in the practical implementation of the SES principles in a semi-official or other way. This behavior can sometimes even threaten their jobs and positions, so relatively few of them resort to such methods.

Animal health and welfare organizations play a decision-making role in our case study. They only overlap with the SES principles to a very limited extent. Animal health standards are also closely linked to agricultural standards. On the other hand, the environmental impact of many of the active substances tested and successfully used in animal care, which are compulsory and used in animal health, is unknown or only partially known. In this respect, there is a serious lack of theoretical and practical information at the level of decision-makers, manufacturers and users. Accordingly, optimal implementation into legislation is typically lagging. Thus, even if one wants to implement SES principles in the field of animal health, one is unable to take the appropriate action in the absence of

information. The former is based on the research evidence that only a few of the widely used products for the mandatory treatment of livestock against external and internal parasites have been tested in any meaningful way. However, they have been found to have serious detrimental effects on insect fauna and, in turn, on grassland ecosystems when used inappropriately. In addition, only a minority of farmers are aware of this impact, while the regulations do not take it into account (there are no information or mandatory conditions of use to prevent negative effects).

The various breeders' organizations, which may set standards for indigenous and other livestock breeds in our country, may also play a decision-making role for herders. The scope of the activities of these organizations is, however, not linked to the SES principles, but only a very broad interpretation of them would allow some common ground to be found. They therefore have no role in this matter.

4.2.1.3 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

We have written about government involvement before. At present, biodiversity is not given any consideration, and in many cases is being deliberately and consciously destroyed. There is a growing number of cases where the public is trying to use its limited means to take action against damage to nature and the environment. This is not only a case of uncontrolled and excessive use/exploitation of natural and environmental resources and the suppression of basic citizens' rights, needs and interests. Such government actions and decisions lack any realistic professionalism and any justification compatible with the public interest. Unfortunately, over the last decade, corruption has become more frequent and more serious in matters that have a very serious impact on nature conservation and biodiversity. So unfortunately, we must count almost exclusively negative effects on governance processes. In this respect, it makes no difference what type of knowledge is relied upon in decision-making. Among the main actors in our case study, herders naturally represent local and traditional knowledge, as well as innovations partly based on traditional knowledge. Conservationists and researchers already rely heavily on science-based knowledge. At the same time, our own research team necessarily relies strongly on local traditional ecological knowledge in addition to scientific knowledge.

SES in general is of very little importance in Hungarian society; there is not much awareness of it. It should be added that there is a growing demand in society for SES principles and methods, but at the same time the country is facing much more serious political-socio-economic problems than it is able to address (or even be able to disseminate emerging needs and methods). It is a contradiction that the ecological problems caused and aggravated by inadequate policies are not being addressed in a way that society has the time and the means to address them properly, but that economic solutions are also being sought to address them. Of course, these methods delay and exacerbate the situation of ecosystems (including people).

The principles of SES are best understood by those working at lower levels in conservation and agriculture on the one hand, and by local communities, on the other, who are the most receptive audience in practice. This naturally follows from the fact that the living space, housing and work of these people are directly and strongly linked to, or even dependent on, socio-ecological-economic processes. This includes herders. It should be added, however, that they do not formulate the principles of SES consciously and precisely, but rather experience the necessary positive and negative processes, associated with it. The relationship of conservationists to the same issue is different, as they can often experience the same issues on a scientific basis, but also as members of a local community. However, experiencing the real-life situation in today's bureaucratic and regulated environment is

not easy for any of them, as change would require conscious energy and financial investment from the lowest individual level to the top national levels, with more sacrifice for the long-term interests and benefits of communities and all citizens of the country. At the same time, it is a well-known process that people are typically unwilling to give up their comfort and are only forced to do so by necessity. So, the very timely and necessary solutions that the SES embraces are coming. The theories contained in SES are only secondarily followed by that part of society which is not directly connected (through housing, work, etc.) to the natural environment, the landscape and the communities living in it, but which nevertheless considers the problem important through media and influencers or other influencing communications. Unfortunately, this section of human society follows the principles of SES mostly in theory but does not make serious commitments or even abandonments to achieve them.

4.2.1.4 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

The direct drivers of biodiversity loss in the case study can be of several types. First of all, we could think of natural processes, but given the history of the Carpathian Basin, we are talking about processes that have not been natural for a long time. The present situation has been shaped most significantly by almost a thousand years of very significant human landscape formation, which has been increasing until today.

The systematic regulation of rivers and drainage, starting in the mid-1800s, has now dried up the landscape to the point where there is hardly any water reserves left. Although there are scientifically and socially based proposals to properly manage the remaining water and reverse the process, no meaningful policy or decision is taken beyond the spectacular. Thus, the desertification of the country is taking place directly and immediately, and despite social pressure, neither the government nor the institutions responsible for water management are doing anything to counter it. As a result of the drought, the possibilities for agricultural production are becoming increasingly unpredictable and the weather more extreme. While it is possible to talk about climate change, the tasks and opportunities for humans to influence the weather and local climate are largely unrealized. So, it is not worth talking about climate change, but rather about human activities that change the climate, or the lack of them. The average annual temperature is increasing. As a result, woody vegetation is drying out, and grasslands are being eroded in the absence of rain or are boiled when rain falls. The regulatory environment does not adapt in any way to changing conditions, making it impossible for livestock farmers to adapt, causing financial and long-term damage to nature. The species composition of grasslands is changing very rapidly. Invasive and other harmful species that are of no use to herders are spreading through the grasslands, taking over very large areas every year. The natural and protected species diversity of grasslands is thus gradually being degraded. In addition, agricultural and nature conservation activities are strongly reinforcing this process through outdated grazing and harvesting standards. Soils are becoming more compacted, and their structure is deteriorating year by year. As a result, they are unable to absorb rainfall, which runs off and evaporates on the soil surface.

The grazing systems that maintain grasslands are disadvantaged by regulations and bureaucracy that are unable to adapt to change to such an extent that livestock keeping and the associated traditional ecological knowledge and innovations are threatened. So, the people who are disappearing from the degraded landscape are precisely those who have the potential and the ability to mitigate, halt and sometimes reverse the damaging processes. This dwindling section of society is increasingly disappearing, and the technological options created to replace them are in practice not, or only partially, able to

fulfil their role. In the case of many technological advances, in the long term they are leading to the initiation or intensification of ecologically damaging processes. In fact, there are two fronts on which a major battle needs to be fought: the survival of the people who live in and maintain the landscape (and their traditional ecological knowledge and innovations), and the restoration of the elements necessary for the landscape to function properly. Unfortunately, the two are intimately linked: it would be pointless to keep herding communities and knowledge alive if there is no place to eventually herd in an extremely changing and degrading natural environment. However, it would be pointless (and impossible) to put in place processes to normalize the landscape if people who can maintain it professionally are no longer present in the landscape. Overall, the survival of Hungary's landscapes, its ecological stability, its cultural, intellectual and practical heritage, the genetic values of its livestock and the country's food and drinking water security are under threat. There is a clear downward trend in biodiversity, the speed of which is greatly increased by the destructive activities still being carried out by humans and the lack of corrective regulation.

4.2.1.5 Values underpinning decision-making processes

The values that are being created and developed in the context of the case study seek to influence policy and decision-making processes from several directions. The most basic and realistic instrument is to strengthen and increase the number of grassroots initiatives. Firstly, we need to strengthen local communities and public opinion to the extent that their presence becomes a factor for the executive and local decision-making bodies at the grassroots level. This can be followed by the development of an advocacy group that is capable and able to negotiate with middle-level and, progressively, top-level decision-maker institutions and individuals. In this process, we have made more significant progress in strengthening local communities. From here, work can continue to increase stakeholder engagement and communication. Policies are unlikely to change dramatically for the reasons already given and are unlikely to generate the minimum substantive response expected. Therefore, it is the decision-making bodies and institutions that are independent of policies and play an indirect role in the lives of livestock keepers and the state of biodiversity that should be the first to be put under more pressure to achieve the theoretical and practical goals set. Another possibility is to try to influence public opinion outside the industry, which can also exert pressure on decision-making and policy activities. Today, public pressure is increasingly being exerted to bring together large numbers of individuals by various means to curb decisions and implementation measures that are extremely damaging from an ecological point of view. A similar example is when citizens' initiatives and implementation processes are triggered by the failure to take the necessary decisions and measures. In conclusion, we must rely primarily on the role and power of society to shape opinion and intervene to achieve results.

4.2.1.6 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

The current political and institutional power relations have little regard for the alternative methods, knowledge and values offered by SES. Background information on this has been shared previously. Regarding the cultural context, there are formal and other socially based institutions and communities that offer opportunities to take into account SES principles in some degree and form. Although not yet widespread and not yet taking a very effective form, there are several social communities that are emerging with the intention of civil society coming together, most of which are trying to consider and implement SES values and scientific background, either explicitly or subconsciously.

4.2.1.7 Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector

A fundamental circumstance is that policy conditions significantly ignore the problems related to SES principles and their possible solutions. Since the upper interest is not substantially related to the fulfillment of the SES principles, and social pressure is not sufficient to achieve changes, the various institutions, their norms and rules do not take them into account. Mostly, unconscious and neutral decision-making takes place in the direction of SES, which simply does not take these circumstances into account. In certain cases, we can also report on specific countermeasures, when the basic principles and practical implementation possibilities of the SES are consciously destroyed in favor of political and national economic interests (typically also affected by corruption). In many cases, institutional systems appear to be neutral, taking no responsibility for planning and implementation, nor for the impacts that arise from their work. Typically, they try to assume a service provider and enforcer role and communicate about themselves, thereby avoiding responsibility. The professional opinions of individual employees of the institutions may of course differ from this, but in most cases, internal professional initiatives are quickly eliminated due to the force of higher-up instructions.

4.2.1.8 Economic structures' impact over the SES

It is difficult to generalize regarding market structures. Market conditions set at the national, government level do not explicitly take into account the principles of SES. We could rather say that among small and medium-sized entrepreneurs there are those who, considering the discussed aspects, enjoy increasing support from society, even in an otherwise inadequately designed support and financing system and in the face of gradually degrading ecological conditions. This social support can be observed most strongly among producers striving for short food chains, the number of which is gradually increasing in various agricultural sectors, including at the level of local small producers. Across Europe, and in Hungary in particular, it is typical that large producers and traders do not typically strive to establish short food chains. A very significant part of the economic goods produced in our country – and here we can specifically talk about agriculture, including live animals and animal products produced in animal husbandry – are not sold, processed and consumed locally. Moreover, there are the environmental and ecological conditions that, with rapid changes in recent years, are increasingly making certain types of production activities impossible. As an example within Hungary, the drying out of landscapes – it is a process practiced by humans until even this day – is causing serious emigration and demographic problems in several regions (the most serious situation is at the region of Kiskunság and Békés-county), as agriculture and the associated employment opportunities are becoming increasingly scarce, and there are no other livelihood opportunities that can absorb large numbers of people in these regions. So, it is not the principles of SES that are being enforced, but rather people are trying to escape from a landscape that is considered increasingly unlivable from economic, social, ecological and other perspectives. The developments built up by the national high management further worsen the situation in terms of the ecological environment, as they typically disregard the basic principles of the SES, which also concern ecological aspects, and establish environmentally destructive industrial facilities under the pretext of creating job opportunities. Returning to the example of drought, they are not trying to address the ecological problem that would best serve the principles of SES and the needs of society. Instead, they try to intervene using methods that are ineffective in the long term, and in some cases even harmful, for local society and nature, based on completely different principles.

4.2.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

Typically, the domestic institutional system cannot handle locally perceived and specifically defined biodiversity-related problems and challenges individually. The identified challenges and trends may be fully scientifically based or simply based on practical observations. Regardless, the compulsion to act is triggered when many similar reinforcements arrive over a sufficient period, and when associated with appropriate social pressure and narrative. So, the broader impact sector has a severely delayed reaction time. The appropriate level of key stimulus (e.g. the combined implementation of scientific and social positions and pressure) triggers communication that acknowledges the problems and initiates the planning of responses. At the same time, increasingly accelerating ecological processes may lead to increased erosion of biodiversity due to slow infrastructural reaction times.

4.2.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

Although the situation is probably similar in many parts of the world, one of the most serious dangers in Hungary is the treatment of the landscape (and the entire ecosystem within it) and humans on separate theoretical and practical levels. One of the biggest inhibiting factors is that society, the relevant organizational structure, and the regulatory and support systems are all designed as if they were independent and determinable from their entire ecological and natural environment. The advantage lies in the social and scientific recognition that is now beginning to emerge extremely slowly: the separation of landscape and people is no longer possible in Europe. To mitigate and stop the increasing ecological damage to the natural environment, we need to think in a complex system, for which there are (for now) some local initiatives. Other countries in Europe may be already ahead in this process in some respects. The increase in social needs experienced by the population in Hungary due to natural-ecological and related economic reasons (e.g. agriculture) may mean the appreciation of the basic principles of SES in the future, as well as the planning and application of practical options.

4.2.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

For SES, the ideal vision is to keep the landscape alive. If the landscape is not alive, it cannot be lived with, nor can its resources be used in ways that bring it into balance. We must start from the basic needs of the landscape: in terms of the regulatory framework, water management and soil restoration are the first and most important issues! We consider this fundamental because these factors provide the basic conditions for the survival of the landscape and thus for any socio-ecological process and environment that is integrated into the landscape. At the same time, the inertia and slowness of the regulatory environment no longer allow for the rapid handle and reversal of the damage caused by the increased pace of ecological problems and extreme climatic conditions. So, in addition to the siege of decision-making infrastructure and personnel, there is a parallel need for a major transformation of societal thinking and lifestyles, and the launch of active interventions, even to the point of civil disobedience. We highlight this example because the impact of the recent severe droughts, despite misleading government communication, has led to a situation where citizens directly and currently most affected by the drought (although in fact everyone is equally affected by water management issues, as water has now become a national treasure) have started to implement point-based local water containment attempts at their own expense under the legal category of civil disobedience. Thus, in some situations, social

interests and professional arguments are beginning to override the outdated and, in some cases, unprofessional and inappropriate regulatory framework. Of course, this process should not be an end in itself but rather seen as a potential short-term tool to address the increasingly pressing issues of food security, drinking water security and ecology. In other words, society is already receiving the kind of inputs that are beginning to influence the way it organizes itself and its environment (both human and natural) towards SES principles. If we succeed in harnessing these social waves in the future, we may be able to achieve increasingly effective results in society and the landscape by informing the public at large and by using and disseminating the traditional ecological knowledge that has been gathered and disseminated so far.

Since activities to restore landscape function have already been stepped up, the next step is to help people living in the landscape now and potentially in the future to acquire the traditional ecological knowledge and practices that do not fundamentally disrupt the landscape but still create resources and livelihoods for those who live there. One segment of this knowledge, the ecological and livestock-related knowledge of traditional herders and innovative solutions to this knowledge, is what we are trying to gather in our case study and prepare for future social use. Although we are currently facing many barriers in this area, our collections could play a key role for the extensive livestock sector in the future. The big question is whether there will be policy changes that will facilitate this process. The most practical course of action in the present situation may be to seek to use these collections in a way that is not currently possible, as many cultural, regulatory and practical infrastructural circumstances prevent or severely limit the possibilities for their publication. Instead, we are preparing these materials for the future, when society and policymakers will, by necessity or otherwise, demand this type of knowledge. By that time, presumably the demand will have created the conditions for publishing the material in various forms.

There are, of course, much more obvious ways of transferring knowledge than the above method. Community building among people living in the landscape should be a cornerstone of SES. Hence the need to create communities not only to save and maintain the traditional ecological knowledge of herders, but also to understand and use it from the direction of society becomes essential. Our current work covers this in the sense that we have successfully encouraged different groups (e.g. by gender, age, regions, types of livestock kept, etc.) within herders and herders' societies to engage in community building, networking and exchange of experiences. Of course, this process needs to continue for herders to form officially and professionally recognized communities and to inform and influence decision-making processes, regulatory environments and civil society opinion. In addition, this process should be extended in the future to those people who are not herders in terms of their occupation and culture, but who need or will need the knowledge and practical skills of herders to a greater or lesser extent to successfully coexist with the landscape. People in this category can include a wide range of people: people who are already living in the landscape; people who are moving back to the landscape and have the knowledge they need; people who are moving back to the landscape but do not have the knowledge they need; people who are moving back to the landscape but do not need the knowledge to survive there, but still need the support to build social communities. In addition, groups can be distinguished by occupation whose knowledge needed to live in and with the landscape is in some form or part complementary to that of herders. These may be small farmers, people who are trying to be partially or totally self-sufficient, people working in agriculture - who may have a professional and material interest in the knowledge linked

to livestock -, organizers of any agricultural sector that uses livestock keeping and grazing as a complementary activity (the role of no-till should be highlighted here!!!), etc. The important point here is that it is not only the herders, i.e. those who are in some way entrusted with this profession and task by the community or who work in it in some other way (as employees of a farmer or as self-employed), who need the knowledge of the herders. Both researchers and the relevant practical sectors need to incorporate this kind of knowledge and practice into their own systems. This will also help to sustain herding and allow people and occupations from any part of the SES to see through to elements of the landscape that do not directly affect them but are essential to its functioning. The building of communities and the transfer of the knowledge needed to live in and with the landscape must therefore be extended at some point to all members of society who need it. Moreover, it is not only those individuals and groups who need it that should be given access to the necessary knowledge, but the general shaping of society's consciousness should increase the number of those who can play any role in building a society that functions in accordance with the SES principles. We need to continuously develop ethical, culturally appropriate, socially usable and inclusive ways of doing this for local stakeholders in the future.

The economic and market structures related to nature conservation need to be transformed. For the last two, it is essential that locally produced raw materials and products can be processed and sold locally. Obviously, the most optimal situation would be for the small communities that emerge to be able to meet their basic food needs from their own activities, but given the social structure of modern Europe, this is almost impossible to achieve without external inputs. The solution that comes closest to the most optimal objective should therefore be the first to be identified: local economy, but most on a regional or national scale at the largest. There are many resources and even services available from extensive livestock farming which are ignored or considered unnecessary by modern society, but which it is trying to obtain from other sources. To exploit these, major infrastructural improvements are needed, which cannot be achieved solely through local initiatives and funding. It is therefore worth adding this objective to the list as part of long-term strategies, in which national or even international assistance and experience should be sought. There is also the unanswered question of what standardized opportunities and positive or negative impacts emerging technological opportunities may have in the future.

It is necessary to take a different approach to understanding and assessing the challenges of biodiversity in different ways. The concepts of biodiversity and nature conservation are closely related, as has been the case up to now. However, in the changing ecological and climatic context of our times, we need to remain grounded in reality. Accordingly, we need to review what possibilities the changing or already changing landscapes and conditions offer for the future. Although, in the best case, we should return to the natural and ecological conditions that have been known for roughly 150-200 years, we must nevertheless recognize the very low probability of this happening. There are many cases where changes that take place in too short a time and have too great an impact affect certain local, regional and national conditions to such an extent that it is physically impossible to restore the original conditions in the short term (e.g. the decline and even disappearance of certain indigenous species can unfortunately not be prevented, or even slowed down). This leads to a compelling need for adaptation on what the changed - and even partially restorable - landscape characteristics will allow in the short- and long-term future. It is possible that the expansion of certain cultivated and wild plant and animal species (even, in extreme

cases, invasive species) may be so successful that it is either not possible or not really in the human interest to fight it. So, there may be a new level of adaptation where we seek to preserve and exploit the changed conditions (or some element of them) in the hope of long-term stability. While this will not change the basic mechanics and laws of how the landscape works, it may involve a significant reassessment of the elements of the landscape and some of the principles of SES.

It is expected that the highly extreme changes in the natural-ecological environment and climate, and the equally extreme changes in human society will pose challenges to professional and civil society organizations, communities and individuals working on SES objectives for which we do not have ready solutions and proposals today. At any time, processes may emerge, even as previously unknown factors, for which we do not have ready answers at local or global level. We should expect to be unprepared...

4.2.3 Discussion

A social-ecological approach does not currently exist in Hungary, but rather only through the work and research of a few individuals is attempting to draw attention to the role and importance of this way of thinking and value system. The most serious problem of the Hungarian and international agricultural and nature conservation environment is that they want to separate the landscape from the people who live, work and specifically maintain it. To take a concrete example, they want to maintain Hungary's protected grasslands of natural value - which are also cultivated landscapes - by making it impossible and excluding the human landscape-forming and landscape-maintaining activities that have been present there for hundreds of years, for example by severely restricting grazing. It is precisely the values and features that need to be protected and maintained that are disappearing at an increasingly drastic rate as the activities that sustain the landscape are gradually being eliminated. In general, we can say that there is no comprehensive link between SES and the participants in our case study, or in Hungarian society in general.

The implementation of the SES principles is also made more difficult in the Hungarian case study by the fact that natural and climatic changes, as well as drainage and river regulation, which have had an extremely negative and damaging impact on the landscape over the last 150 years, are making it increasingly difficult to carry out activities that sustain the landscape. These human activities and their effects manifest themselves in different ways and with varying intensity in different regions of the country. However, it can be said that climate change, and in particular man-made climate change at the local (e.g., national) level, has a uniformly negative impact on the development of our natural and agricultural environment. In this context, it is becoming increasingly difficult to maintain the activities, knowledge, and traditions of traditional communities linked to nature and agriculture. At the same time, it is becoming impossible to develop and sustain innovative socio-ecological processes and social environments that meet the expectations of our contemporary society. The outcome of this process cannot be predicted, as there are many sudden factors emerging in both the ecological sense and on the part of human society. At the same time, we can say with certainty that we are currently living in an era of significant ecological restructuring, where it is extremely difficult to develop appropriate long-term strategies. It is difficult to shape public opinion in the right direction because rapidly changing circumstances and new proposed solutions follow each other in quick succession, causing a great deal of misinformation in policymaking, public opinion, and traditional communities alike. Thus, the demand for SES has been growing steadily and strongly in recent years, and we should not expect the development and implementation

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of uniform and strong SES principles in society in the coming years (in the Hungarian context). Of course, it is worthwhile and necessary to intensify efforts in this direction!

4.3 Mertóla Future Lab, Portugal

Authors: Fernanda Belizario and Luciane Lucas dos Santos (CES)

The Mértola case study (Mértola Future Lab) explores how regenerative governance and community-led initiatives can offer transformative responses to desertification, climate change, and rural abandonment. The focus of the Mértola case study is to examine how regenerative practices can be activated through local food systems to enhance community resilience in a context shaped by ecological degradation, rural depopulation, and socio-economic marginalization.

Known for its rich historical heritage and striking semi-arid landscape, Mértola, a municipality in the Baixo Alentejo Region in Portugal, today faces major ecological and socio-economic challenges. These include population decline, aging demographics, limited economic opportunities, and increasing climate vulnerability. Yet, this apparent fragility has also opened space for experimentation with innovative, inclusive, and sustainable alternatives.

Mértola is one of the pilot sites of the BioTraCes project, which investigates how biodiversity can be protected and regenerated through just and inclusive governance. In this context, the Mértola case highlights the value of a participatory approach to ecological transition. Mértola's case is particularly relevant because it links environmental regeneration with social justice by mobilizing local knowledge, fostering intergenerational dialogue, and promoting a diversity of actors and experiences. Similarly, this case allows us to reflect upon the relevance of intersectional lenses to go a step further in terms of environmental justice, with underrepresented groups taking benefit from environmental betterments and being less affected by an unequal environmental burden.

At the heart of this process is the Mértola Future Lab, a local strategy towards ecological transition that gathers a range of initiatives and projects to this end, as well as a diversified group of organisations committed to be part of a collectively designed strategy to face climate change in a semi-arid area. Mértola Future Lab addresses key regional concerns such as climate adaptation and biodiversity regeneration, while also tackling social and economic resilience. It is worth recalling that 47% of Mértola's surface is already affected by high rates of soil degradation (Roxo, Casimiro and Sousa, s/d), which points out not only the environmental problem but also the impacts on agricultural practices.

This local strategy co-designed and co-implemented by different local organizations and stakeholders - highly animated by the Mértola City Council - has managed to bring together public institutions like the Mértola City Council and the Santana de Cambas' Community Meeting House, educational institutions such as local schools, associations and NGOs such as the Guadiana Valley Business Association and the Agency for the local development in the Southwest Alentejo (ESDIME), and grassroots associations like Terra Sintrópica. Mértola City Council and Terra Sintrópica Association play a pivotal role in this BIOTraCes' case study as they are the societal partners in the case, welcoming the CES team and helping us understand the cross-case strategy in Mértola engaging a diversified set of organisations.

What makes the Mértola case unique is the networked approach to transformation. Terra Sintrópica and Mértola City Council do not act alone—it is part of a broad coalition that includes public authorities, NGOs, schools, vocational training centers, research institutes, and regional development agencies. Many of these partners are also involved in the Mértola

Food Network, a participatory governance model that brings different actors together around the shared goal of food safety. This collaborative ethos ensures that regeneration is not treated as a technical fix, but as a deeply social and political process that requires engagement, negotiation, and redistribution of power and resources.

In terms of funding, the sustainability of these efforts relies on a mosaic of national and international sources, including foundations such as Stiftung Drittes Millennium and the Leopold Bachmann Stiftung, EU funds (notably from the ERDF via COMPETE 2020), and cross-border cooperation programs like POCTEP (Interreg Spain-Portugal). Programs like the Healthy Neighborhoods Program also support specific projects that address social vulnerabilities through ecological action.

In sum, the Mértola case offers a vivid example of how small rural communities can become laboratories for regeneration and resilience. By placing community participation, environmental justice, and local sovereignty at the center of ecological transformation, Mértola challenges the dominant narrative that rural peripheries are doomed to decline. Instead, it invites us to see such territories as fertile grounds for reimagining the relationship between people, place, and biodiversity.

4.3.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

4.3.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

The Mértola case study reveals a social-ecological system (SES) shaped by a web of interactions between human and more-than-human actors, structured by desertification, depopulation, water scarcity, and emerging regenerative initiatives. These actors do not operate in isolation; their roles, vulnerabilities, and transformative potential are deeply interconnected with territorial imaginaries, institutional capacities, cultural values, and ecological processes. Below we present key actor groups and their positioning within the SES.

1. Elderly rural residents and low-income populations

These groups are among the most directly affected by SES degradation. Living in isolated villages, often with poor mobility, they face direct impacts from soil infertility, declining water availability, and loss of traditional farming systems. Their lives are also affected by weak access to health services and pensions, especially for older women. Despite these constraints, they are vital holders of local knowledge—especially regarding subsistence agriculture, wild plants, and seasonal patterns.

However, this knowledge has long been undervalued and marginalized in formal land management or policy design. Lock-ins include inadequate mobility infrastructure, lack of targeted communication strategies, and insufficient institutional mechanisms to integrate their knowledge. Nonetheless, initiatives such as the Grandmother's Kitchen and Therapeutic Gardens (by TSA) are starting to reposition their agency within regenerative strategies.

2. Women in social economy organizations and food provisioning

Elderly women from the community in general and the ones who are working at schools and nursery homes (e.g. cooks) hold crucial know-how on healthy, seasonal, and biodiversity-friendly food practices. Yet, their role is largely invisible in biodiversity policy discussions. While these women are essential to the local food system, they face social and economic lock-ins—including gendered undervaluation of labor and limited decision-

making power. The participatory food governance strategy of the Mértola Food Network (MFN) is gradually elevating these contributions by revaluing cooking as a practice of care, transmission, and ecological learning.

3. Young people and children youth

Youth is impacted by declining educational and employment prospects, often migrating away and weakening the generational continuity necessary for territorial resilience. There is also a fragile connection between young people and environmental awareness. They are insufficiently reached by biodiversity-related communication or vocational strategies. While initiatives such as the Mértola Biological Station and ALSUD provide training in agroecology, game management and biodiversity management, these efforts are still too limited to counter the dominant perception of Mértola as a “place without a future.” Dependencies include a lack of career pathways, mobility options, and place-based innovation ecosystems.

4. Regenerative actors and agroecological entrepreneurs, including newcomers with environmental backgrounds, agroecological entrepreneurs, or project-based professionals, are both contributors to and shaped by the SES. They are less directly affected by socio-ecological degradation (often arriving with financial and educational resources) but are impacted by bureaucratic hurdles, cultural resistance to change, and the difficulty of scaling innovations in a structurally fragile economy. They depend on external funding and may lack long-term embeddedness, raising concerns about the sustainability of their contributions if the local social fabric is not strengthened. Their innovations often contrast with prevailing economic structures, generating both inspiration and tension.

5. Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and Societal Partners

Civil society organizations (CSOs) such as Terra Sintrópica (TSA), ESDIME, ALSUD, and Empresários do Baixo Guadiana (Association of the Guadiana Valley’s undertakings) play a central role in shaping the SES through innovative actions like the Mértola Food Network, the Mértola Future Lab, and training programs in regenerative agriculture and biodiversity-related vocations. These organizations are often at the forefront of proposing and implementing nature-positive solutions—such as syntropic agriculture, regenerative pastures, and alternative food systems—that directly challenge business-as-usual approaches in the region. They are empowered by access to EU and national funding, policy advocacy tools, and recognition in regional and international forums.

However, their capacity to operate and innovate is also constrained by several structural limitations. These include the reduced administrative and financial autonomy of the municipality, fragmented institutional landscapes, and the high dependence on project-based funding. Additionally, despite their prominence, CSOs tend to be concentrated in the village of Mértola, while many of the municipality’s 106 dispersed localities remain physically and socially distant from these hubs of innovation. This spatial concentration can hinder the broader social embedding of the regenerative agenda and limit the reach of their initiatives.

The effectiveness of CSOs is further tied to their ability to work in concert with other actors. These organizations thrive when they form synergistic relationships not only with the Mértola City Council (MCC) but also with each other, creating an ecosystem of cooperation that enhances legitimacy, resource-sharing, and collective impact. At the same time, their initiatives are dependent on gaining validation from local communities—something that is not automatic. Community trust must be built and maintained, especially when these

organizations are perceived as external or disconnected from daily rural realities. These dynamic underscores the importance of inclusive engagement strategies that go beyond organized civil society to reach individual citizens and informal networks.

6. Mértola City Council (MCC)

The Mértola City Council (MCC) is a pivotal institutional actor within the SES, actively supporting and co-developing biodiversity-oriented strategies such as the Mértola Future Lab (focused on ecological transition and adaptation to climate change), the Mértola Food Network (a grassroots initiative that gathers different organizations and individuals to co-implement a locally-based food system for Mértola), the Grandma's kitchen (a project that fosters intergenerational co-learning and exchange, and stimulate parents to prepare healthy, territorially-based recipes for children for changing eating habits). A core strength of MCC lies in its commitment to participatory governance model, exemplified by its role in co-organizing the Mértola Food Network and its integration with civil society actors like TSA, ESDIME, and ALSUD.

However, MCC's role in fostering transformation is constrained by the structural limitations of municipal autonomy. The implementation of its regenerative agenda often collides with national and EU regulatory frameworks, especially in areas such as public procurement, where the law mandates prioritization of lowest-price contracts—frequently in conflict with goals of biodiversity, locality, and sustainability. Overcoming these constraints requires political coordination and policy alignment that go beyond Mértola's borders.

In this sense, the viability and legitimacy of MCC's innovations are being reinforced as Mértola increasingly inspires and engages other municipalities in the Baixo Alentejo region. While not a prerequisite for its strategies, this expanding network amplifies the impact and reach of Mértola's pioneering regenerative efforts. By building broader alliances, Mértola can further amplify its influence and strengthen advocacy for regional-scale changes to policy and governance. The Food Basin initiative exemplifies this potential: while Mértola's internal successes already drive significant change, connecting with neighboring municipalities through shared food sovereignty and regenerative agriculture strategies offers an opportunity to expand and deepen the impact of its pioneering work. Inter-municipal collaboration is not only instrumental for scaling impact but also vital for demonstrating that localized innovations are not isolated experiments, but models with relevance for broader territorial regeneration.

Furthermore, MCC's engagement in horizontal governance structures—such as the governance pact underpinning the Mértola Food Network—reinforces its role not as a top-down authority but as a facilitator of collective transformation. Its relationship with CSOs is marked by complementarity: the municipality offers institutional infrastructure and political leverage, while CSOs contribute technical innovation, social trust, and community embeddedness. For governance to function as a tool of regeneration, this alignment must be nurtured and expanded—both within Mértola and across the wider territory.

7. Roma communities and migrants

Initiatives like the Shelter Land Project led by Terra Sintrópica (TSA) mark an important shift in the way marginalized groups are considered in regenerative processes. By offering housing and training in syntropic agriculture to refugees, TSA has helped reframe these populations as contributors to territorial regeneration. This approach encourages the integration of migrants and promotes mutual learning between newcomers and local residents.

While TSA has played a crucial role in fostering inclusive practices in Mértola, particularly through initiatives such as ShelterLand, a broader institutional commitment is required to transform these into sustained governance mechanisms. The question of migrant inclusion is particularly relevant given the demographic composition of the Baixo Alentejo, where migrant labor has become increasingly significant in agriculture and local economies over the last decade. Migrants, including seasonal workers and newly settled families, often face barriers to participating in territorial planning and decision-making processes, despite their growing role in the region's socio-economic fabric. Similarly, Roma communities—historically present in the Baixo Alentejo—remain structurally marginalized in governance spaces (EAPN Portugal, 2021). Without a more systematic approach to integrating these groups into co-governance structures, their knowledge, cultural practices, and potential contributions to social-ecological regeneration risk remaining under-recognized and underutilized.

Despite this, there remain important dependencies. These communities rely on recognition from local authorities and CSOs to be included in regenerative strategies. Their integration also depends on ongoing support from intermediary organizations such as TSA, which facilitate access to resources, legitimacy, and networks.

8. More-than-human actors — In Mértola's SES, more-than-human actors—such as degraded soils, invasive acacia trees, the Guadiana River, cork-oak forests, steppe birds of the montado, and keystone species like the Iberian lynx—are active forces that shape ecological conditions and human livelihoods. Soil infertility limits agricultural viability and community self-sufficiency, while species such as the lynx and steppe birds act as indicators of ecological balance and restoration potential.

These non-human elements are not merely impacted by human decisions—they are entangled in them. The Iberian lynx, for instance, depends on controlled hunting areas and species management, reflecting a shift in how traditional practices like hunting are being reimagined. Similarly, steppe birds and montado ecosystems require recognition and protection to ensure their survival, especially amid changing land use pressures.

Terra Sintrópica (TSA)'s syntropic agriculture approach stands out by explicitly valuing these cooperative relationships. Practices such as those in Malhadinha Vegetable Garden illustrate how soil regeneration is intertwined with biodiversity restoration. Syntropy encourages direct cooperation between human and more-than-human actors, moving beyond extractive models toward reciprocal regeneration.

4.3.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

Decision-making in Mértola's SES is shaped by a **hybrid structure of formal authority and experimental co-governance**, where power circulates unevenly among public institutions, civil society organizations, landowners, and ecological actors. This configuration reflects both **long-standing institutional hierarchies** and **emerging participatory models** that seek to address biodiversity loss through regenerative practices and horizontal governance.

Formal Decision-Making Actors and Institutional Power

At the institutional level, the Mértola City Council (MCC) has been a key driver of the territory's regenerative agenda. It has strategically positioned Mértola as a "living laboratory" for biodiversity regeneration and climate adaptation, particularly through its

active role in the Mértola Future Lab and the Mértola Food Network (MFN). One of the most significant steps has been in public procurement: although national legislation and EU guidelines limit the ability to favor local or organic suppliers, the Council has worked within these frameworks to adjust its purchasing policies. By interpreting the rules of Directive 2014/24/EU on cost-based tendering in a flexible way, it has been able to prioritize small-scale procurement that guarantees the inclusion of local suppliers in public catering. This has enabled part of the municipality's collective catering services—such as school and eldercare canteens—to be supplied with local, organic food while remaining compliant with procurement regulations.

Public procurement decisions—especially those tied to collective catering—are being made collectively in spaces like the MFN, where institutional actors co-deliberate with civil society representatives and local producers. The stimulation of local organic production for collective catering is done in a concerted and planned manner. This includes: (1) a prior verification of local producers' supply agendas, ensuring they are not negatively affected in fulfilling pre-existing distribution commitments; (2) a progressive shift in school menus, discussed and planned with nutritionists, so that soups and salads can increasingly be composed of organic products; and (3) gradual adjustments in the primary supplier framework, involving the replacement of certain vegetables and legumes—traditionally purchased in large volumes from distant suppliers (e.g., potatoes)—with feasible and healthy local alternatives.

The MCC's leadership, particularly through its Vice-President, has also shown political will to distribute power through participatory structures and host municipal meetings in peripheral parishes to reduce territorial exclusion.

Co-Governance and Participatory Spaces

Civil society organizations - especially the Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA), ESDIME, Santana de Cambas' Community Meeting House, and the ALSUD vocational school - have played a transformative role in shaping the governance of the SES - although this set of organisations has mobilized resources and efforts towards a regenerative agenda in the territory, it is worth emphasizing the particular relevance of TSA's contribution regarding community participation, experimentation and change of mentality. The association has led experimentation in syntropic agriculture, promoted forest gardens in schools, and strengthened participatory ecological education, thereby contributing to progressively reshaping both material land-use decisions and ecological imaginaries.

Decision-making within the **MFN** exemplifies this participatory ethos. Cooks, producers, public officials, and technicians come together to make joint decisions on school menus, procurement strategies, and education programs. These decisions are rooted in collective discussions and shared responsibilities, not formal delegation.

The Agroecology and Regeneration Center for the Semi-Arid (CARES) and the Mértola Biological Station (EBM) also contribute to decision-making by generating context-sensitive data and supporting regenerative policies. While not decision-making bodies in themselves, their technical input and visibility lend credibility to alternative land-use models.

Power dynamics

The Mértola City Council (MCC) holds a relatively central — yet balanced — position within the governance landscape. On one hand, it has successfully projected a public commitment to territorial regeneration; on the other, it has fostered a collaborative inter-institutional

climate that has positively influenced the coordination of strategies and decision-making. Nonetheless, certain asymmetries persist. Some organizations and individuals may feel underrepresented in co-governance processes, as the regenerative approach has not achieved unanimous support. Moreover, there is a notable emphasis on the participation of organized civil society—such as social economy entities, development agencies, and cooperatives—while the direct involvement of ordinary citizens remains limited. The community tends to be perceived through the lens of its representative organizations. As a result, groups that form part of Mértola’s contemporary social fabric—such as Roma communities and migrants—often remain excluded from meaningful participation and decision-making.

Power Imbalances and Exclusion

Despite progress, not all actors enjoy equal say in the SES. Landowners and economic elites, although often disconnected from co-governance networks like the MFN, continue to exert strong influence over land-use outcomes through their control of territory and adherence to conventional agricultural practices. These are frequently reinforced by Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) subsidies that favor high-input, non-regenerative models. Many of these actors resist change due to perceived economic risks, slim profit margins, and skepticism toward agroecological approaches. However, a subset of landowners—particularly those with greater financial stability—have begun experimenting with regenerative farming and pastures and game management techniques. This shift has been supported by ESDIME, which has played a key role in fostering and financing these experiments through technical guidance, training, and access to tailored funding instruments. By enabling trial-and-error learning and buffering early-stage losses, ESDIME has created enabling conditions for landowners to test more sustainable models, helping to bridge the gap between economic pragmatism and ecological innovation.

Conversely, ordinary citizens from remote villages, young people, vulnerable groups and marginalized people remain largely peripheral to decision-making. The geographic dispersion of Mértola (106 villages across seven parishes), along with infrastructural limitations and lack of targeted inclusion strategies, reproduces territorial and social disconnection. Focus groups and interviews revealed a split between the “networked Mértola” (engaged in Future Lab and MFN) and the “excluded Mértola” (disconnected to a certain extent from institutional and ecological innovations). However, it cannot be denied that there is a true effort from MCC to integrate the villages by, for example, promoting municipal meetings in all seven parishes than only in the City Council headquarter in Mertola.

Youth voices are notably absent, although the interest of both public administration and an active group of civil society organizations in addressing this gap is clearly visible. The mainstream school system remains only partially engaged in fostering future-oriented ecological leadership. From a more proactive perspective, however, there have been concrete efforts to create regenerative career paths - such as the ALSUD vocational courses on wildlife and environmental management - indicating that a broader youth engagement strategy is still under development. Additionally, a work plan co-designed with the societal partners includes a scheduled workshop for December 2025 (See chapter 6) aimed at exchanging strategic insights with other initiatives—such as those developed in Brazil for living with the semi-arid climate—that have successfully connected youth participation with environmental regeneration.

Knowledge and Discursive Power

Different forms of knowledge play varied roles in decision-making. Scientific, institutional, and technocratic knowledge continue to dominate procurement and planning decisions. However, local and experiential knowledge—especially that held by elderly women, cooks, and small-scale farmers—is gradually gaining recognition. Initiatives such as “Grandmother’s Kitchen” and “Therapeutic Gardens” were explicitly designed to value these non-expert contributions as essential to biodiversity regeneration, emphasizing intergenerational transmission, sensory experience, and embodied care practices. Although both projects have ended due to lack of funding, they remain on hold, with the intention to resume once new financial support becomes available. Their temporary suspension highlights the vulnerability of inclusive, bottom-up initiatives to institutional funding cycles, despite their proven social and ecological relevance.

Nevertheless, epistemic power remains uneven. Actors with academic training, project management experience, or external networks are more likely to influence the SES. Those without digital literacy, schooling, or social visibility need active inclusive practices to be included in strategic planning.

Efforts to pluralize knowledge—such as school-based forest gardens and intergenerational learning initiatives—stand out in the Portuguese context for their meaningful attempts to engage non-experts, like school cooks and grandmothers, in regenerative practices. While still developing and occasionally limited by resources, these initiatives represent significant steps toward inclusive and community-rooted biodiversity strategies.

More-than-Human Actors in Decision-Making

While non-human and more-than-human actors (soils, the river, steppe birds and other threatened species) are not “deciders”, they increasingly co-shape decisions indirectly. For instance:

- Soil (in)fertility and desertification risks point out the relevance of adopting syntropic systems, grounded on the regeneration through the use.
- The presence of invasive species has reframed land management debates.
- The Guadiana River plays a practical role in shaping irrigation and conservation narratives. It is the primary source of surface water in a semi-arid territory, directly conditioning agricultural strategies, water allocation, and biodiversity corridors. Its fluctuating levels and ecological status act as indicators of climate stress and management effectiveness (*Gualda et al., 2014*).
- The Iberian Lynx, the world’s most threatened feline, led to the improvement of wildlife management strategies in Mértola, allowing the municipality to become the first place where the lynx was reintroduced in Portugal.
- The roller (*Coracias garrulus*), one of 17 ground-nesting bird species in Portugal critically threatened by land-use change, has contributed to a better understanding of farming practices in Mértola, as it serves as a bio indicator of agricultural activity.

4.3.1.3 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

In Mértola, multiple types of knowledge—scientific, institutional, experiential, traditional—interact in the governance of biodiversity. However, these forms of knowledge are not equally recognized or embedded in decision-making. Instead, they reflect ongoing negotiations over legitimacy, visibility, and influence in shaping both strategies and imaginaries of ecological regeneration.

Dominant Biodiversity Framings: Institutional and Scientific Knowledge

The dominant framings of biodiversity in Mértola’s governance spaces still rely heavily on science-based and institutional knowledge systems, especially in formal planning and funding mechanisms. Although this science-based knowledge has provided empirical evidence of critical scenarios and thus grounded important decisions for biodiversity regeneration, it is also worth recalling the prevalence of technical discourse over the tacit knowledge of communities. For instance:

- The Mértola Biological Station (MBS) contributes to empirical research and technical assessments that support the case for regenerative interventions, especially around desertification, soil health, and land use transformation.
- Biodiversity loss is often discussed in terms of degraded soils, species disappearance, and water scarcity, all of which are typically diagnosed using ecological monitoring tools, geospatial data, or environmental assessments.
- Funding mechanisms—such as those influenced by ESDIME’s evolving criteria for regenerative pastures—draw on technical indicators to validate investment in biodiversity-positive practices like holistic grazing or syntropic design.

These forms of knowledge offer strategic leverage in aligning local practices with regional, national, and EU biodiversity agendas. Yet, they also risk marginalizing more embodied or situated knowledge systems if not intentionally integrated into governance spaces.

Local and Traditional Knowledge: Slowly Gaining Influence

Local knowledge — particularly held by elderly farmers, community cooks, and non-institutional actors — was undervalued in governance in the past but has gained recognition through specific initiatives:

- The **Grandmothers’ Kitchen Project** (Cozinha d’Avó) frames elderly women’s food knowledge not just as culinary heritage but as environment-related knowledge, tied to seasonality, seed use, and ecosystem resilience.
- The **Therapeutic Garden Project**, designed by TSA to involve the community in regenerative practices, also served to validate the older persons’ soil wisdom.
- The **traditional food preparation** and low-input farming methods play a key role as many of the recipes depend on locally sourced, seasonal ingredients, which historically came from low-input, diversified farming systems. This type of cooking implicitly supports short food cycles, local seed use, and biodiversity in production.

Despite their relevance, these forms of knowledge remain largely contextual and project-dependent, rarely codified into policy frameworks or public procurement decisions unless they are championed by organised civil society groups like Terra Sintrópica (TSA).

Regenerative Education

A third form of knowledge production is emerging through educational initiatives aimed at cultivating ecological awareness among school children:

- Forest gardens and school-based syntropic agriculture projects are reshaping how ecological processes and human-nature relationships are understood by the younger generation.

- These projects promote multispecies literacy, relational values, and embodied learning. Though still modest in reach, they represent a strategic investment in cultural shifts that will likely influence future governance orientations.

However, these initiatives are not yet integrated into mainstream education policy or municipal curricula, and therefore their systemic impact remains limited unless institutionalized.

Transversal and Relational Knowledge

A key innovation in the Mértola case is the development of transversal or hybrid knowledge practices, particularly through the Mértola Food Network and other alternative spaces that foster social cohesion and dialogue on the necessary dietary transition:

- Meetings, workshops, and experimental spaces like PREC (a self-managed restaurant) and Night at the Market foster dialogical knowledge creation, where scientific, traditional, and experiential insights converge.
- In these spaces, biodiversity is not only understood as a measurable condition (e.g., species richness) but as a relational, cultural, and ethical condition tied to memory, identity, and territorial belonging.

These hybrid formats act as knowledge bridges, helping to pluralize both the definition of the problem and the range of possible solutions. They also facilitate inclusive governance, even if informally.

Governance Implications and Knowledge Asymmetries

Despite these innovations, asymmetries in knowledge recognition persist. The governance of biodiversity remains tilted toward actors and practices aligned with institutional logic, formal education, and technoscientific validation. Community-based knowledge is more likely to be mobilized in participatory projects or symbolic initiatives, but less so in infrastructural planning, funding allocation, or legislative decisions.

Tensions also persist in how different knowledge forms are translated across governance layers. For example, while local regenerative practices may align with EU discourses on agroecology and nature-based solutions, their translation into CAP funding mechanisms often fails due to bureaucratic and technical filters that prioritize quantifiable outputs.

4.3.1.4 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

The SES in Mértola operates within the constraints of a semi-arid Mediterranean ecosystem undergoing accelerated climate stress. In recent decades, the region has faced not just traditionally low annual rainfall, but a marked and ongoing decline in precipitation levels, combined with rising temperatures and prolonged drought periods (APA, 2022; 2023). These changes are already altering hydrological cycles and severely impacting soil health, plant productivity, and water availability. Ecological processes are therefore shaped by this increasing climatic aridity, interacting with historical land use patterns — such as intensive monocultures, overgrazing, and river management — that have long prioritized short-term productivity over long-term resilience. Together, these drivers form a structural backdrop of vulnerability, where biodiversity loss is exacerbated by both environmental degradation and limited adaptive capacity at multiple levels of governance.

From an ecological perspective, the system is defined by chronic vulnerability to desertification, water scarcity, and soil erosion, alongside decreasing habitat diversity and

degraded agrobiodiversity. The region's natural resilience has been significantly weakened by human interventions over decades, making the functioning of the SES highly sensitive to small ecological and management changes.

According to climate scenarios RPC 8.5 (considered a severe scenario by the IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change), Mértola will face, in projections for 2040, 2070 and 2100, a combination of a significant reduction in average annual precipitation (404 mm in 2040 and 288 mm in 2100) with an increase in average maximum temperature (36.3°C in 2040 and 39.5°C in 2100). This combination of extremely high temperatures with low average precipitation means that many plant species in the region - including those that are currently seen in the montado, such as holm oak and cork oak - will exceed their tolerance range and will not be able to survive. According to the Mértola Climate Change Adaptation Plan (APA, 2017) "in the RCP 8.5 scenario, there is practically no natural regeneration of holm oak in the future except on the shady slopes to the NNW (north-northwest), which indicates that it is in these locations that trees should be left to regenerate or be planted". This shows that, in addition to direct drivers, it is important to take into account indirect drivers that may influence the struggle against desertification, such as the institutional perspective on the reforestation model to be implemented in the following years and the prevalent imagery on what a productive montado could be.

These climate projections underscore how climate drivers intersect with ecological and governance dynamics in Mértola. The anticipated shifts in precipitation, temperature, and species tolerance reveal not only the biophysical pressures shaping the territory but also the need to reconsider institutional and cultural models of land use and regeneration. Against this backdrop, understanding the ecological processes that underpin the socio-ecological system (SES) becomes essential to anticipate pathways for adaptation and transformation. The following section systematizes the key ecological processes currently structuring the Mértola SES, highlighting how soil, water, vegetation, species interactions, and agrobiodiversity are entangled with both direct and indirect drivers of change.

Ecological Processes in the Mértola SES

1. **Soil degradation** is one of the central ecological processes shaping the SES. Poor soil structure, low organic matter content, and long-term erosion—exacerbated by mechanized tillage and intensive grazing—have reduced the capacity of local ecosystems to regenerate autonomously. Soil fertility, water retention, and biological activity are all critically impaired in many parts of the territory.
2. **Water cycles** are increasingly disrupted. With declining rainfall and rising evapotranspiration, the region suffers from persistent drought stress. Institutional responses to this issue (e.g., small-scale irrigation systems, or lobbying for river transpositions) often replicate infrastructure-heavy approaches, whereas local actors such as Terra Sintrópica propose nature-based solutions such as successional agroforestry systems as more viable long-term alternatives.
3. **Vegetation and land cover dynamics** are central to how the SES regenerates or declines. The abandonment of traditional polycultures, coupled with the dominance of monocultures and extensive pastures, has led to a loss of landscape.
4. **Heterogeneity**. The presence of invasive species (e.g., acacias) further shifts plant communities and threatens native biodiversity—although TSA's syntropic practices reframe some of these invasives as transitional agents that help rebuild soil organic matter.
5. **Species interactions** are influenced by fragmented habitats and declining ecosystem services. Keystone species like the Iberian lynx are emblematic of both

ecological vulnerability and conservation potential. While their presence signals partial recovery in protected areas, functional biodiversity in everyday landscapes—such as pollinators, soil biota, and native seed varieties—remains under threat.

6. **Agrobiodiversity** is a critical indicator of SES health. It is directly affected by market pressures, subsidy regimes, and loss of traditional seed systems. Regenerative actors are trying to reverse this through agroecological experimentation and seed-saving practices, but they operate within an overall system that still incentivizes chemical inputs, monocultures, and standardized production models.

Direct Drivers of Biodiversity Loss in Mértola

The direct drivers of biodiversity loss in the Mértola SES include:

- a. **Land-use change and simplification of landscapes**, especially the replacement of diverse agro-silvo-pastoral systems with cereal monocultures or extensive pastures for cattle breeding. This reduces habitat complexity and ecological niches for wildlife and beneficial insects. Mértola has invested, however, on a different approach to deal with extensive pastures, bringing the concept of regenerative pastures to the scene. Through rotating grazing and innovative forms of soil mobilization, the following results have been detected: enhanced soil health, nutritious fodder and improved water infiltration, to name but a few.
- b. **Soil tillage and erosion**, associated with both historical and current agricultural practices, degrade soil structure, eliminate microbial life, and reduce nutrient cycling, all of which are essential for sustaining plant and animal biodiversity.
- c. **Overgrazing and stocking density** in certain parts of the montado system, which prevents forest regeneration and depletes ground cover, accelerating erosion and compaction.

Invasive species, particularly acacia and eucalyptus, which outcompete native flora and alter fire regimes, hydrology, river and soil conditions. While some regenerative practices attempt to work with these species during transition phases, their unchecked spread remains problematic in unmanaged areas.

4.3.1.5 Values underpinning decision-making processes

The Mértola SES is deeply influenced by competing and overlapping systems of values that shape how nature, biodiversity, land, and food are governed. While recent participatory processes and regenerative projects have helped to foreground relational and intrinsic values in Mértola, much of the governance landscape in national and regional terms remains informed by older, instrumental and productivist paradigms.

However, recent developments in co-governance—particularly through initiatives like the Mértola Food Network and the Mértola Future Lab—are gradually shifting this landscape in Mértola and neighboring municipalities. These processes have fostered greater visibility for relational and intrinsic values, such as care for the land, intergenerational knowledge, and more-than-human cooperation. Co-governance has thus begun to embed new forms of valuation into local policymaking, enabling a more collective, situated, and regenerative perspective on the management of socio-ecological resources. While tensions remain, these participatory dynamics are contributing to a cultural and institutional reconfiguration of how decisions are made and whose values are legitimized.

Instrumental Values in Conventional Policy and Practice

In many public policies and dominant economic sectors (agriculture, forestry, hunting), nature continues to be viewed through an instrumental lens—as a resource to be managed for productivity, extraction, or economic gain. This is especially visible in:

- The implementation of Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) subsidies, which prioritize land area, productivity, and market output over ecological diversity or community well-being. The CAP is the European Union’s main agricultural policy framework, designed to support farmers, promote rural development, and ensure food security across member states. CAP subsidies are financial aids provided to farmers through two main channels: Direct Payments and Rural Development Funds.
- Conventional land-use models that favor extensive grazing or monocultures, guided by values of efficiency, output, and short-term profit rather than regeneration or biodiversity care.
- Regional planning frameworks that focus on infrastructure-based responses to climate stress (e.g., dam construction, river transposition), which treat ecological systems as engineering challenges rather than complex relational environments.

These values shape not only public spending but also administrative modus operandi: procurement routines, project funding criteria, and landscape classification systems reflect and reproduce instrumental logics.

Relational and Intrinsic Values in Regenerative Governance

In contrast, civil society actors and several institutional partners—including the Mértola City Council—have increasingly introduced relational values into governance processes. These emphasize connection, interdependence, responsibility, and care between people, places, and ecosystems.

Examples include:

- The Mértola Food Network (MFN) integrates values of proximity, collaboration, and ecological justice into its collective decisions about procurement, menu design, and agroecological training. Food is not treated solely as a commodity but as a relational good that ties health, land, and community together.
- The syntropic agriculture promoted by Terra Sintrópica is explicitly guided by values of cooperation across species, mutualism, and soil ethics. Nature is not something to manage but to regenerate in dialogue.
- The Grandmothers’ Kitchen (led by the Santana de Cambas’ Community House) and Therapeutic Gardens (led by the Terra Sintrópica Association) promote intergenerational respect, food sovereignty, and memory-based ecological learning, thereby incorporating emotional, cultural, and ethical values into decision-making.

In these initiatives, decision-making is shaped by care-based ethics, multi-species awareness, and the recognition of local knowledge as a form of ecological intelligence.

Plural Value Systems in Conflict and Negotiation

A defining feature of the Mértola SES is the coexistence—and often tension—between plural value systems. While participatory processes have succeeded in pluralizing who participates and what knowledge counts, deep structural and cultural lock-ins still limit the full expression of relational or intrinsic values in mainstream policy:

- Procurement policies often still prioritize cost over ecological or cultural value.

- Funding mechanisms, even when oriented toward sustainability, tend to measure outputs rather than qualitative transformations in land relationships.
- Local actors who hold instrumental values (e.g., older farmers, large landowners) tend to see new approaches as threatening or impractical, especially if they challenge inherited landscapes or routines.

In this context, policy and decision-making processes are often sites of value negotiation, where regenerative actors must translate their relational values into formats recognizable by bureaucracies and policy frameworks.

Values as Drivers of Innovation and Resistance

The transformative potential of Mértola's governance practices lies precisely in this value contestation and experimentation. Many of the region's most promising interventions succeed not by replacing dominant values outright, but by:

- Creating hybrid value spaces (e.g., school menus that are both cost-sensitive and biodiversity-aware).
- Engaging communities emotionally and culturally, so that ecological values resonate with lived experience.
- Performing values publicly—through events like Night at the Market or educational installations—to build broader affective commitment to regeneration.

At the same time, failure to sufficiently engage with the dominant values of certain actors—especially those who perceive loss or risk in transition—can limit uptake or cause resistance, as seen in persistent skepticism toward syntropic farming or soil-based methods among traditional farmers.

4.3.1.6 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

The governance of the Mértola SES is deeply shaped by overlapping political, cultural, and institutional power dynamics that affect whose knowledge, which values, and what narratives are legitimized, resourced, and scaled. These power dynamics operate both vertically (e.g., between national and local levels) and horizontally (e.g., among local actors), reinforcing or challenging the dominant socio-ecological order.

i) Political Power Dynamics

Political dynamics in Mértola are marked by an openness to experimentation yet constrained by multi-scalar dependencies and structural limitations. On the one hand, the Mértola City Council (MCC) plays a progressive role in embracing regeneration-oriented narratives, supporting projects and initiatives like the Mértola Future Lab, the Mértola Food Network, and the Forest Gardens at Schools.

However, this local-level political will is limited by national and EU-level policy frameworks, such as public procurement laws and the CAP subsidy structure, which are built around cost-efficiency and productivity, rather than ecological or relational criteria. This reinforces instrumental logics and makes it difficult to institutionalize alternative values and knowledge systems.

Moreover, political visibility and legitimacy are unevenly distributed across the SES. Actors embedded in structured networks—such as Terra Sintrópica (which, despite its grassroots origins, has gained organizational capacity), ESDIME, or other local initiatives—often have

more access to funding and opportunities for policy dialogue. This positioning does not imply distance from community dynamics, as these actors frequently operate in close cooperation with residents and smaller initiatives. Notwithstanding this proximity, the very presence of certain groups—such as Roma families, migrants, or elderly residents in isolated parishes—remain underrepresented in formal spaces of decision-making. Their lived experiences and knowledge systems, while rich and significant for territorial regeneration, are rarely translated into policy, highlighting the need for more inclusive governance mechanisms that can bridge different forms of social organization and representation.

Political alignment or friction between levels of governance also affects how biodiversity narratives unfold. For instance, local calls for agroecological procurement may be slowed or diluted by regional education authorities or EU auditing mechanisms, creating a tension between political aspiration and bureaucratic realism.

ii) Cultural Power Dynamics

Cultural dynamics shape both resistance and resonance in the governance of biodiversity. Baixo Alentejo carries a strong cultural memory of large estates (*latifúndios*), agricultural hardship, and hierarchical labor relations. This historical backdrop contributes to:

- The persistence of productivist narratives, where ecological regeneration is sometimes perceived as utopian or impractical.
- A gendered division of knowledge, in which women's roles in food systems and ecological stewardship (e.g., as cooks, caregivers, gardeners) are culturally undervalued and politically invisible.
- A split between local and newcomer actors, where newcomers with ecological literacy are sometimes seen as culturally disconnected or imposing external models.

Despite this, regenerative actors are strategically using culture as an entry point for transformation:

- Initiatives like the Grandmothers' Kitchen, forest gardens, and participatory festivals are reframing cultural memory as ecological knowledge.
- Food becomes a cultural-political tool, where cooking, eating, and storytelling recover marginalized values and make biodiversity regeneration emotionally and socially relatable.

Still, cultural resistance remains a soft power barrier that often leads to subtle exclusion or lack of uptake—especially when new practices are perceived as culturally alien or economically risky.

iii) Institutional Power Dynamics

Institutionally, certain actors—such as the Mértola City Council (MCC), regional agencies, and organizations like ESDIME or the Mértola Biological Station (EBM)—hold greater strategic capacity within the local SES. Their relative access to technical staff, policy instruments, and their fluency in bureaucratic and funding procedures position them to align more easily with national and EU policy frameworks. While they may not directly control large financial resources, these actors have the ability to mobilize funding, structure project proposals, and influence the regional development agenda.

This privileged position is partly due to the institutional architecture itself: funding calls, reporting formats, and mechanisms of public visibility tend to favor those who can translate their work into the dominant language of quantitative indicators, administrative accountability, and measurable impact. As a result, grassroots groups, informal initiatives, and knowledge holders with less experience in institutional engagement often face barriers to recognition and support.

However, what distinguishes the Mértola context is the effort made by these more institutionally embedded actors to create bridges between regenerative practices, local knowledge, and institutional logic. Rather than merely reproducing hierarchical structures, actors such as TSA, ESDIME, and MCC are actively experimenting with ways to render regenerative and community-led practices legible to funding bodies and public authorities. This includes adapting reporting tools, framing policy dialogue in inclusive terms, and facilitating participatory arenas such as the Mértola Food Network (MFN), where multiple knowledge forms can co-exist.

Observed institutional tendencies:

- Some organizations might still privilege quantitative indicators (e.g., number of beneficiaries, cost-efficiency, land productivity) compared to qualitative, process-based, or relational metrics. This emphasis **varies by actor**:
 - o Municipal initiatives and local networks in Mértola have shown openness to integrating lived and intergenerational knowledge.
 - o National and regional funding frameworks often privilege standardized and measurable outputs.
- There is a tension between the weight given to **scientific and administrative expertise** and the recognition of embodied, community-based, and intergenerational knowledge.
- The persistence of **linear project logic**—with fixed timelines, predefined deliverables, and KPIs—can clash with the adaptive and iterative nature of regenerative processes.

These tendencies shape how biodiversity and regeneration are framed: often in terms of compliance, mitigation, and measurable risk reduction, rather than through the lenses of care, multispecies cohabitation, or social justice. Nonetheless, the ongoing commitment by key institutional actors in Mértola to integrate diverse epistemologies into governance structures remains a significant step towards fostering a more inclusive and effective socio-ecological transition.

4.3.1.7 Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector

One of the most influential mechanisms is the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), which defines the financial and normative landscape for agricultural development across the European Union. Under the Strategic Plan of CAP for Portugal 2023–2027 (PEPAC), subsidies are allocated through the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). CAP includes direct income support measures—such as basic payments, eco-schemes, and climate/environment/welfare payments—which are mandatory for member states. However, in practice, these funding mechanisms tend to benefit larger, conventional operations that can meet the bureaucratic requirements and scale thresholds often embedded in funding calls ([Lampkin, N. et al. 2020](#)). Regenerative actors in Mértola—typically operating on smaller scales and with diverse crop/livestock systems—face

difficulties accessing such support, resulting in a structural lock-in that slows the transition toward agroecology and biodiversity-friendly models.

National procurement laws and EU directives—particularly the Directive 2014/24/EU—emphasize cost-efficiency as a primary criterion in public tenders. This focus often undermines efforts to institutionalize short-chain food systems and support local, organic production ([FAO et al, 2021](#)) while it does not support the cost for agroecological transition. In practice, cost considerations tend to outweigh social and environmental objectives, making it difficult for small-scale, agroecological producers to compete in large-scale procurement processes. While initiatives such as Mértola’s local food procurement offer promising alternatives, they remain structurally fragile, relying heavily on political will and local coordination rather than robust legal or institutional support.

At a discursive level, the overarching biodiversity narrative promoted by EU and national institutions is still dominated by technocratic and mitigation-focused paradigms especially through the term ecosystem services. Biodiversity is often discussed in terms of carbon capture, emissions control, habitat preservation, and climate risk reduction. These framings rarely acknowledge the value of community-rooted regenerative practices or more-than-human relations that are foundational to Mértola’s approach. This discursive gap reduces the visibility of initiatives like syntropic farming or intergenerational learning projects, which are essential to building resilience in the local SES.

There are, however, emerging opportunities for greater attunement between local experimentation and EU policy orientations ([UN, 2021](#)). The EU Farm to Fork Strategy, part of the European Green Deal, offers rhetorical and policy openings for the promotion of local, healthy, and environmentally friendly food systems. However, the implementation of this strategy at the national level—particularly through procurement frameworks, subsidy allocation, and food regulatory standards—often falls short. Ongoing critiques regarding the weak integration between the EU Green Deal and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) further underscore the risks of fragmentation and highlight potential shortcomings in realizing transformative goals within the Farm to Fork strategy ([Guyomard et al, 2020](#)). In this context, local governance in Mértola plays a dual role: navigating institutional constraints while seeking to realign national and EU frameworks with the regenerative practices being tested on the ground. The success of this alignment may determine the medium- and long-term viability of biodiversity restoration as both a socioecological and economic strategy.

4.3.1.8 Economic structures’ impact over the SES

Mértola’s socio-ecological system (SES) continues to be shaped by extractive and productivist economic logics driven by external forces. The dominant economic activities—extensive agriculture, livestock grazing, and game hunting—reflect a dependence on mainstream land-use models that are not necessarily aligned with long-term sustainability or high economic return. These sectors are highly dependent on subsidies, and decisions on how funding is organized and distributed lie primarily at the EU and national levels. As a result, local governance has very limited influence in steering economic incentives toward regenerative or locally appropriate practices.

Market structures in the region further reinforce these constraints. Centralized food distribution networks and the dominance of large suppliers marginalize small-scale producers, who struggle to access markets or achieve economic viability. For example, wild

game is a traditional activity in the region, but the absence of a certified slaughterhouse makes it impossible to process locally and capture added value (Câmara Municipal de Mértola, 2024). Consequently, processing and profits are redirected to neighboring Spain, weakening the local economy’s capacity to retain and reinvest benefits from its natural resources.

Economic barriers, including lack of infrastructure—such as transportation networks connecting remote villages—exacerbate exclusion and limit the potential for inclusive and resilient local food economies. Financially, regenerative approaches require significant upfront investment and do not promise immediate returns. This economic model can be particularly challenging for smallholders or families experiencing economic vulnerability. Although some landowners with greater financial resilience have started experimenting with regenerative practices (e.g., regenerative farming or game management), often with the support of organizations like ESDIME, these remain isolated efforts – although they play an important role in experimenting and portraying results. The broader economic system does not currently incentivize such transitions at scale.

4.3.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

In Mértola, biodiversity assessment is deeply grounded in scientific fieldwork, focusing on species-level monitoring, soil and vegetation analysis, and agroecological experimentation. The Mértola Biological Station (EBM) plays a pivotal role in this. However, these assessments are not always scaled up or systematically integrated into broader regional/national biodiversity indicators or land-use frameworks.

Table 3.1. Local identification of challenges: methods and types of data

Type of Method	Example in Mértola	Data Type
Ecological Monitoring	Iberian lynx and steppe bird population studies	Species count, distribution data
Soil Quality Assessments	Soil health measurements in agroecological zones like Horta da Malhadinha	Soil carbon, nutrient content, erosion risk
Vegetation Surveys	Vegetation cover and species richness documentation in regeneration areas	Vegetation indices, species diversity
Experimental Agroecological Projects	Terra Sintrópica's syntropic agriculture trials	Productivity, resilience, microclimate data
Climate Adaptation Modelling	Climate Change Adaptation Plan for Mértola (Vizinho et al., 2016)	Scenario modelling, temperature and precipitation

Despite these rich data sources, their integration into policy, land-use planning, and sectoral adaptation remains limited.

4.3.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

The Social-Ecological System (SES) in Mértola operates as both an enabler and a constraint for transformative innovation. On one hand, Mértola has become a living lab for regenerative practices, enabled by strong local actors, participatory governance, and ecological experimentation. On the other hand, entrenched economic models, institutional

lock-ins, and cultural inertia pose significant constraints on the pace and depth of transformative change.

Table 3.2. Enabling Elements (Opportunities and Leverages)

Category	Enabling Element/Key actor	Mechanism/Impact
Scientific Knowledge	Participatory action research/ Mértola Biological Station (EBM), TSA.	Generates data and evidence for biodiversity decline and restorative practices
Experimentation Space	Syntropic agriculture, regenerative pastures/ Malhadinha Vegetable Garden.	Testbed for agroecological methods and soil regeneration in semi-arid conditions
Co-Governance	Mértola Food Network, Mértola Future Lab.	Shared decision-making, policy alignment, community integration
Societal Engagement	Involvement of youth, elderly, refugees /Shelter Land project - TSA	Builds intergenerational & intercultural solidarity
Narrative Innovation	Reframing Mértola as a “territory of regeneration”.	Shifts perception from rural abandonment to a model of resilience
Regional Influence	Projects scaled to neighbouring municipalities (e.g., Alcoutim, Ourique).	Fosters regional replication and policy impact
Education & Culture	Creative workshops (music, storytelling) / School Forest gardens, Therapeutic garden - TSA.	Builds cultural and emotional infrastructure for transition
Policy Adaptation	Flexibility in local procurement for sustainable food	Local laws adapted to encourage biodiversity-friendly practices despite EU constraints

Table 3.3. Constraining elements (barriers and lock-ins)

Category	Constraining Element/Key Actor	Impact
Economic Lock-ins	cattle breeding remains prevalent as economic activity; lack of local meat processing; CAP dependence.	Limits innovation in production and market diversification
Technocratic Constraints	EU procurement laws (e.g., lowest price criteria).	Undermines local food systems and regenerative procurement
Institutional Inertia	Resistance to change in maintenance services (gardening), conservative land imaginaries	Slows implementation of innovative land-use strategies
Cultural Imaginaries	Traditional views of Alentejo as mono-productive & extractive (e.g., cereal plains, mechanisation)	Conflicts with regenerative goals and biodiversity restoration

Social Fragmentation	Disconnection between “two Mértolas” — engaged actors vs. distant residents	Excludes large population sectors from innovation processes
Market Structures	National and European policies favour cheap food over local sustainability	Erodes food sovereignty and economic resilience
Knowledge Gaps	Low technical literacy in rural areas; lack of biodiversity awareness	Undermines understanding and engagement with restoration practices
Imagination Barriers	Limited envisioning of alternative futures by parts of the population	Restricts possibility of reconfiguring relationships to land and nature

The Mértola SES reveals a contradictory dynamic between enabling and constraining trends:

- Capacity is high in the experimental/activist sector (TSA, EBM, ESDIME), which operates with strong knowledge, regional alliances, and a vision for regenerative transition.
- Constraint arises when these innovations must scale, embed into formal governance, or influence dominant economic logic (such as livestock and hunting-centred economies that remain decoupled from biodiversity goals).

Notably, participatory strategies are highly effective where they occur but are not yet fully democratized across all territorial actors. The success lies in Mértola's ability to mobilise local knowledge and shared governance as a counterweight to external and institutional rigidities.

- The SES enables transformation through integration of knowledge, experimentation, and relational governance.
- It constrains transformation through economic dependency, policy incoherence, and imagination traps.

4.3.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

A transformative vision for Mértola's social-ecological system (SES) emerges from the everyday practices, knowledge systems, and affective ties that already exist among certain community members—particularly those most closely connected to food production, caregiving, land stewardship, and social reproduction. These marginalized perspectives offer a powerful counterpoint to dominant, extractivist logics. Rather than framing biodiversity as a technical or regulatory challenge, they embody a deeply relational understanding of human-nature entanglement—one that emphasizes mutual care, cooperation, and embeddedness.

In this alternative imaginary, land is not a backdrop for economic activity but a living system with which to co-evolve. Nature-positivity is not confined to conservation targets or reforestation quotas but unfolds through everyday practices like regenerative farming, seed saving, composting, and intergenerational knowledge exchange. In this vision, “regeneration” does not imply a return to a pristine past nor the linear application of technoscientific fixes, but rather a political, ethical, and ecological commitment to co-producing livable futures through situated, collective experimentation.

Institutionally, this vision calls for a reconfiguration of decision-making processes, moving beyond technocratic and indicator-driven governance. Co-governance spaces like the Mértola Food Network (MFN) represent steps in this direction but could be further expanded to meaningfully include Roma families, immigrants, and other community members currently underrepresented. A future-oriented SES in Mértola would redistribute not only material resources but epistemic authority, validating plural forms of knowledge and experience (scientific, traditional, emotional, embodied) in shaping strategies for biodiversity. Mértola has been taking steps in this direction.

Economically, the vision entails a gradual reorientation from externally dependent, subsidy-driven models to circular, locally rooted, solidarity-based economies. This includes the creation of community-supported agriculture models, regenerative cooperatives, and mutual aid initiatives that tie economic viability to ecological care and social justice. Markets would be shaped not only by price but by values—such as health, reciprocity, biodiversity, and territorial belonging.

This future is not utopian; it is emerging incrementally in Mértola through the actions of regenerative farmers, school cooks, elderly women sharing recipes, and organizations. To thrive, this vision requires ongoing support—legal, institutional, financial, and cultural—to challenge dominant systems and cultivate the conditions for more just and regenerative human-nature relations.

4.3.3 Discussion

The socio-ecological system (SES) of Mértola offers a compelling and complex portrait of how marginal rural territories navigate, resist, and reimagine biodiversity governance under conditions of environmental fragility, institutional constraint, and political underrepresentation. The SES analysis reveals not only the ecological degradation and demographic decline facing the municipality, but also the emergence of transformative practices that embed regeneration in everyday life, collective governance, and multispecies care.

One of the central messages emerging from this analysis is that the Mértola SES is structured by overlapping layers of environmental degradation and institutional lock-ins, but also animated by a diversity of social actors and ecological relations that challenge dominant paradigms. In particular, the SES shows how regenerative governance does not emerge from the simple implementation of best practices or policy tools. Instead, it is a dynamic relational process involving plural knowledge systems, deeply situated cultural imaginaries, and contested power relations.

From an ecological perspective, the Mértola territory faces severe constraints: climate-induced aridity, depleted soils, biodiversity loss, and water scarcity threaten both agricultural viability and ecological stability. However, these environmental pressures have been catalyzed by actors such as Terra Sintrópica (TSA), the Mértola Biological Station (MBS), and the Mértola City Council (MCC). These actors are not simply service providers or technical implementers—they are narrative-makers, policy-shapers, and guardians of a broader vision of regeneration grounded in relational values and social justice.

The SES analysis reveals that while formal governance institutions—especially the MCC—are essential enablers of systemic experimentation, transformative change in Mértola depends on co-governance spaces that blur the line between state and civil society. The

Mértola Food Network (MFN), for example, embodies this hybrid logic. It allows for shared decision-making on procurement, education, and land use, while also acting as a site where food becomes a material and symbolic entry point for rethinking human-nature relations.

However, the democratization of governance is still ongoing. Despite the participatory ethos of many initiatives, significant segments of the population might remain underrepresented in SES decision-making.

The more-than-human dimension of the SES is also critical. In Mértola, biodiversity is not just an abstract indicator or technocratic goal; it is a co-produced condition emerging from the interactions between humans, animals, soils, seeds, and ecosystems. Practices such as syntropic agriculture—promoted by TSA—demonstrate how regeneration can be understood as a process of multispecies cooperation and ecological healing. This perspective challenges conventional conservation models that isolate biodiversity as something to be preserved rather than relationally restored.

Crucially, values play a decisive role in shaping both problems and solutions in the Mértola SES. Whereas national and EU frameworks continue to prioritize instrumental values—efficiency, productivity, and cost-effectiveness—the regeneration movement in Mértola draws on relational and intrinsic values, such as care, reciprocity, and more-than-human flourishing. This value divergence is not only philosophical; it has concrete institutional effects, particularly when EU procurement laws or CAP subsidies undercut local efforts to build ecologically and socially just food systems.

Power asymmetries remain a major obstacle to deeper transformation. Landowners, technocrats, and bureaucratic norms often hold disproportionate influence over how biodiversity is defined and governed. Meanwhile, the experiential and place-based knowledge of cooks, farmers, elders, and community caregivers is still too often treated as dreamy, utopical or ancient. Initiatives like the “Grandmothers’ Kitchen” or the “Therapeutic Gardens” have begun to reverse this trend, but institutional recognition of these knowledges remains fragile and often project-dependent.

Nonetheless, the Mértola SES has demonstrated an impressive capacity for experimentation and learning. The region is not only developing new ecological practices—it is also generating new imaginaries. The reframing of Mértola as a “territory of regeneration”, rather than one of desertification and decline, is a political and cultural achievement with implications for other semi-arid territories in Europe. It demonstrates that regeneration is not merely a technical task—it is a process of cultural, affective, and political reassembly.

What becomes clear in the Mértola SES is that transformation must be both material and symbolic. Soil restoration must be accompanied by narrative shifts; biodiversity metrics must be complemented by cultural indicators; co-governance must mean more than institutional partnership—it must entail epistemic justice and shared authorship of the future.

The enabling factors for transformation identified in this SES include a strong and coherent network of civil society organizations, a politically supportive municipality, experimental governance spaces like MFN, and a local narrative of regeneration that is emotionally resonant and strategically aligned with broader sustainability agendas. Conversely, constraining elements include rigid procurement frameworks, a limited inclusive territorial

mobility and communication, persistent knowledge hierarchies, and socio-economic barriers associated with prevailing structures and economic decision criteria within the agricultural sector.

In sum, the Mértola SES reveals a promising ecology of transformation. It is a laboratory that offers insights into how regeneration can take root in the margins of Europe. By centering care, cooperation, and pluralism—among humans and across species—Mértola invites us to imagine socio-ecological systems not as problems to be solved, but as relations to be renewed.

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4.4 Free-Flowing Rivers, Lithuania

Authors: Goda Kaniušonytė, Karolina Gurjazkaitė, Audra Balundė, and Jonas Tertelis (MRU)

The Anykščiai dam case study examines one of Lithuania's most emblematic river restoration dilemmas, set within the broader European ambition to reverse biodiversity decline and re-establish free-flowing rivers. Located in the small town of Anykščiai in northeastern Lithuania, the Šventoji River is both an ecological corridor of national importance and a deeply familiar feature of local life. Yet, like many European rivers, it has been altered by the construction of dams. The Anykščiai dam, originally built for hydropower but now functionally obsolete, remains a major barrier to ecological connectivity. It obstructs fish migration, degrades river habitats, and contributes to biodiversity loss. At the same time, the dam has become a visible part of the town's landscape and cultural memory, complicating discussions about its future.

This case sits at the intersection of urgent environmental policy goals and local socio-cultural realities. At the European level, the Water Framework Directive and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 call for restoring good ecological status in rivers and reconnecting at least 25,000 km of free-flowing waterways. Lithuania's national policies echo these ambitions, and scientific assessments identify the Anykščiai dam as one of the country's priority barriers for removal due to its ecological impact and limited socio-economic value. However, translating these policy frameworks into local practice is far from straightforward. Earlier efforts to initiate dam removal did not result in a restored river or strong community consensus, reflecting the challenges of aligning ecological imperatives with diverse local perspectives, values, and concerns.

The BIOTraCes project takes up this challenge by investigating how participatory action research (PAR) can support transformative biodiversity governance. Working with societal partners the project explores how inclusive and creative engagement methods can reframe contentious debates into opportunities for dialogue and co-creation. Through stakeholder interviews, media and policy analysis, and experimental participatory practices, the research seeks to understand how residents, authorities, businesses, and cultural actors construct meaning around the river, and how their voices can be included in decision-making processes.

The significance of the Anykščiai case lies in both its ecological and social dimensions. Ecologically, dam removal offers a rare opportunity to restore migratory fish populations and re-establish natural fluvial processes. Socially, the case reveals how histories, identities, and attachments to place shape environmental governance. It demonstrates that biodiversity restoration cannot succeed through technical solutions alone but requires building trust, integrating plural knowledge systems, and creating genuine spaces for shared decision-making. In this sense, the Anykščiai dam is not only a barrier in the river but also a symbol of the broader challenge of reconciling ecological sustainability with community resilience across Europe.

4.4.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

4.4.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

In our case study, the Social-Ecological System (SES) is centred on the Šventoji River and the dam in Anykščiai, which affects different actor groups in various ways. **National authorities and policymakers** engage with the SES primarily through environmental

policy and strategic planning. When specific policy goals or measures pertain to the Anykščiai, this engagement extends to cooperation with **local authorities** for implementation. Their work is informed by scientific and analytical insights, national political priorities, and advocacy from **non-governmental organizations (NGOs)**. Many policy frameworks—such as those related to environmental monitoring, assessment, goal setting, and the identification of necessary measures—are derived from **EU nature directives**. Within this context, authorities develop regulations, establish objectives, and formulate plans that are subsequently operationalized at the local level.

National scientific experts contribute through research, environmental monitoring, and assessments, thereby informing policy and participating in political and decision-making processes (e.g., expert groups). Nonetheless, the communication of scientific findings to the public and communities remains limited, which can hinder broader societal understanding of environmental issues.

At the **municipal level, local governance and authorities** interact with the SES mainly through infrastructure management and public-oriented benefits such as recreation and landscape aesthetics. Although biodiversity concerns are acknowledged, they are not always central to local agendas and often emerge reactively in response to environmental challenges rather than through proactive strategies. Ecological expertise at this level is largely concentrated within **regional environmental authorities**, who manage an extensive range of responsibilities. Financial and human resource constraints, along with limited institutional capacity, further restrict the pursuit of more ecologically ambitious initiatives.

Local politicians, often personally connected to the river as residents, occasionally raise environmental themes within their agendas. However, their focus typically reflects a balance of multiple priorities. In discussions concerning the river and dam, more ambitious ecological proposals have faced limited community support and criticism, resulting in a stronger emphasis on visible social or maintenance-related actions, such as vegetation management.

Technical and infrastructure specialists tend to approach the SES through a functional and engineering-oriented perspective, emphasizing infrastructural concerns. Environmental considerations are integrated primarily through technological solutions rather than ecological approaches.

The influence of SES dynamics on **local businesses** is uneven. Recreational enterprises—such as canoeing, camping, and nature tourism—view environmental changes as both opportunities and risks. Other businesses, especially those not directly linked to the river, experience minimal impact.

Civil society and community groups represent a diverse and evolving sphere. Environmental NGOs and informal associations actively express concern for the river's condition, though their influence is often limited by resource constraints, uneven expertise, and occasional apprehension regarding political or social repercussions.

Among **local community members**, some adopt a cautious stance toward change, influenced by past experiences with public infrastructure projects and the ongoing need to rebuild trust. This trust depends on the assurance that any intervention related to the river will be implemented professionally, with technical competence, and with respect for the

community’s history and values. For new practices or governance strategies to be accepted and to strengthen SES resilience, processes must demonstrate inclusivity, transparent expertise, and a credible commitment to long-term stewardship.

The **cultural and media sectors** engage with the SES primarily through event-based activities. While the river features prominently in festivals and artistic events, ecological themes receive less emphasis. Cultural narratives often highlight recreational and aesthetic aspects rather than biodiversity or ecosystem health.

Finally, **unaffiliated residents**—those with personal and emotional ties to the river through activities such as swimming, fishing, and walking—experience environmental changes most directly. However, they are seldom represented in governance processes. Some rely on **environmental authorities, national NGOs, and politicians** to advocate on their behalf, yet these same actors are sometimes perceived as external to the community, creating a tension between representation and local ownership.

Across all these actor groups—**authorities, scientists, NGOs, politicians, businesses, and residents**—the SES is shaped by a fragmented and hierarchical governance system. While environmental considerations are acknowledged, they are often secondary to socio-economic priorities. As a result, the river itself tends to remain a background element in governance and public discourse, with its ecological complexity and biodiversity insufficiently integrated into broader decision-making.

Figure 4. Visualisation of SES in Anykščiai.

4.4.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

Decisions regarding the state of the Social-Ecological System (SES)—particularly those concerning the future of the Šventoji River and the Anykščiai dam—are shaped by a multi-level governance process. The overall objectives are defined by **national authorities**, who set strategic directions in alignment with broader environmental policy goals and expert assessments. At this level, **authorities and policymakers** rely on data-driven analysis and scientific evaluations to guide decision-making. The **Anykščiai dam**, however, has been widely recognized by the **NGOs, academic** and **angler communities** as a priority site for ecological restoration. Dam removal remains an emerging topic in national contexts, with limited public discussion and implementation to date. In the case of Anykščiai, however, the issue has a longer history of debate, driven by sustained attention from multiple communities and stakeholder groups. Among more than a thousand dams in Lithuania, it is frequently highlighted for its ecological potential. **Scientific findings** have underscored the feasibility of restoration, while sustained attention from **non-governmental organizations (NGOs)** has generated national momentum around the issue.

National-level authorities—including **policy makers and environmental managers**—approach the issue through established regulatory and administrative procedures while also facilitating local consultations. These occur primarily through **municipal council meetings**, where **local representatives, politicians, experts, and other stakeholders** are invited to contribute. Despite these efforts, discussions are often constrained by limited time and supporting materials, and the inclusion of **local environmental voices** remains modest. This can create the perception that decision-making reflects primarily national interests, while the absence of strong local narratives further undermines community trust and a sense of ownership in the process. To enhance the legitimacy and effectiveness of such policies, **complementary measures**—including awareness raising, local engagement initiatives, and capacity-building—are essential to strengthen local understanding and readiness to take environmental action.

Local governance and municipal authorities act as intermediaries between national frameworks and community realities. They are responsible for implementing strategic objectives while balancing local social and infrastructural needs. These institutions form a crucial link in ensuring that high-level policies translate into tangible outcomes. However, **local communities** often remain outside the formal planning process and may have limited familiarity with governance mechanisms. This can contribute to scepticism and reduced trust in environmental initiatives. To unlock the potential of these strategies, emphasis should be placed on **public awareness, transparent communication, and participatory planning**, bridging the gap between expert knowledge and community experience.

Local politicians frequently acknowledge the significance of ecological health but strive to balance environmental objectives with community welfare. Such a pragmatic approach seeks compromise and social cohesion, yet it may fall short of achieving the most ecologically effective outcomes. In some cases, **political actors** explicitly oppose environmental interventions, reflecting divergent priorities and values within local and national governance.

Scientific experts play a vital role in generating and interpreting data that inform decision-making at higher policy levels. However, this knowledge often remains within academic or institutional circles, communicated through technical reports not easily accessible to local authorities or the broader public. As a result, valuable insights rarely reach those most affected by SES dynamics. Improved **science communication**—through simplified materials, local forums, and interactive dissemination—could facilitate mutual understanding and empower communities to participate more effectively.

Local businesses, civil society groups, and unaffiliated residents exhibit diverse and occasionally conflicting interests regarding the SES. While some actors actively engage, others lack the resources or environmental literacy needed for meaningful participation. **Civil society organizations** are often fragmented, and discussions tend to migrate to **social media** and informal settings. In smaller communities, concerns about social or political repercussions can also discourage open advocacy. Strengthening **local environmental education** and supporting **community-based organizations** could enhance civic participation and foster collective stewardship.

Power dynamics within the SES remain complex. Although environmental action is largely driven by **top-down initiatives**, its success depends on **public acceptance and cooperation**. When **national authorities, local governments, and communities** share environmental values but differ in expertise or priorities, implementation gaps can arise. **Local knowledge**, while rich and context-specific, is seldom systematically incorporated into formal policy frameworks. Bridging this divide requires establishing **mechanisms for multi-level coordination, mutual learning, and joint decision-making**.

Ultimately, while the governance landscape remains fragmented, it also contains the foundations for more integrated and adaptive management. Harnessing the strengths of all actors—**authorities, scientists, NGOs, businesses, and communities**—could transform the current diversity of perspectives into a collaborative model of **inclusive and sustainable river stewardship**.

4.4.1.3 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

In this case study, multiple forms of **knowledge** about the biodiversity challenges linked to the dam and the Šventoji River's ecological condition circulate within the community, though their influence on governance remains uneven. **Science-based expertise**, produced by **national-level experts and academics**, informs the official framing of biodiversity issues, identifying impacts such as blocked fish migration, ecosystem fragmentation, and biodiversity loss. While scientifically robust, this knowledge largely remains within policy and administrative processes, with limited engagement at the community level.

Complementing this are **traditional/experimental insights** from **non-governmental organizations (NGOs)** and **angler communities**, rooted in direct experience with the river. These **grassroots actors**, often organized nationally, play an important role in advocating for environmental restoration and keeping dam-related issues (and other environmental issues) on the public agenda.

At the **local level, experiential knowledge**—based on daily observations of fish, riverbanks, and ecological patterns—reflects close ties with the river but is rarely integrated

into governance. While initiatives like local urban greening plans could include these perspectives, river biodiversity concerns are overlooked.

Bridging **scientific**, **local**, and **cultural** perspectives can strengthen ecological restoration and community cohesion. Integrating these knowledge systems into governance would improve ecological outcomes and sustain social connections to the river. When restoration efforts focus only on ecological metrics, they risk weakening these ties; success depends on maintaining both ecological integrity and the community relationships that underpin long-term stewardship.

4.4.1.4 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

In this case study, the river exemplifies the intertwined ecological, social, and political dynamics characteristic of a social-ecological system (SES). Ecologically, the river once supported diverse aquatic communities within a high-quality natural environment shaped by fluvial processes such as unobstructed sediment transport, connectivity (with longitudinal connectivity being most relevant here), natural flow dynamics, and good habitat quality. These processes and characteristics have been altered by the dam (in combination with other dams on the Šventoji River), with longitudinal connectivity in Anykščiai playing the most critical role for aquatic organisms—particularly migratory fish species that depend on continuous river habitats (and access to tributaries) for breeding. The resulting artificial impoundment has transformed the river section in Anykščiai into a slower, more static system, favouring less diverse biological communities. These have been further modified by artificial fish stocking, involving both the reintroduction of lost native species and the introduction of species preferred by anglers. Collectively, the dam, along with other anthropogenic pressures, has simplified and homogenized the river ecosystem, diminishing its natural distinctiveness.

The social and institutional dimensions of the SES are equally significant. Community perspectives often emphasize recreation, aesthetics, and infrastructure, while ecological functions receive comparatively limited attention or are addressed through technical solutions that seek engineered rather than systemic ecological outcomes. Potential interventions—such as dam removal—reveal tensions between cultural values and long-term ecological objectives, with uncertainty about the results of restoration influencing public attitudes and support.

Advancing biodiversity restoration in this context requires stronger ecological awareness and inclusive dialogue among scientific, institutional, and community actors. By integrating ecological functions with social and cultural values, governance can pursue long-term strategies that balance human use with ecosystem needs, thereby promoting both ecological recovery and sustained community stewardship.

4.4.1.5 Values underpinning decision-making processes

Policy- and decision-making processes in this case study are often organized around specific problems, with different policies targeting environmental, economic, or infrastructural concerns. Expert, local, and traditional knowledge may be considered within governance structures, yet integration tends to follow established procedures rather than co-creative practices, which limits opportunities for joint exploration and dialogue. Local perspectives reflect a careful approach to environmental change, emphasizing the need for responsible, well-planned actions. The dam illustrates this complexity: for many, it carries

symbolic and practical significance as a familiar element of the landscape and a marker of stability and security, while also altering ecological processes and reducing the biodiversity.

Biodiversity concerns are expressed by residents, NGOs, and local actors, though they are often viewed alongside other priorities such as recreation, tourism, and infrastructure. Although the river is part of the town's identity, the dam is now viewed as something artificial and unnatural, it has been naturalized within the landscape. A different perception exists toward the forests; forests have long been seen as the defining natural feature of the region, and forest cutting is perceived as a problem both locally and nationally. These dynamics mean that while ecological issues are recognized, they are often addressed within a broader set of social, cultural, and economic considerations.

Strengthening biodiversity restoration therefore calls for approaches that are broader and more integrative, addressing ecological challenges in ways that also connect to community values and practical needs. This can be supported by developing co-creative processes that bring together scientific expertise, institutional actors, and community knowledge, and by fostering ongoing community relationships with the river. Such strategies can ensure that ecological objectives are pursued in parallel with social and cultural priorities, supporting both effective environmental management and long-term stewardship.

4.4.1.6 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

The governance of local social-ecological systems in **Anykščiai** is significantly shaped by the interplay of **political, institutional and cultural power dynamics**, which in turn affect the types of knowledge, values, and overarching narratives employed in decision-making processes.

Politically, river sustainability questions, although visible, are not systematically addressed within mainstream politics. Issues such as dam removal and other river-related topics (e.g., navigation, hydropower) enter national political discourse mainly through pro-environmental politicians, together with NGOs, proactive experts, academics, or the media, who bring them to public attention. However, these discussions remain sporadic rather than systemic and largely outside the core of national political priorities. At the local level, river-related topics are even more rarely discussed or prioritized.

Institutionally, governance operates in a top-down manner, where national authorities and agencies set goals and seek cooperation from local authorities for their implementation. Locally, this may create a perception that environmental interests represent the concerns of narrow, non-local interest groups, undermining trust in environmental projects. Local-level initiatives are financially dependent on national and particularly EU funding. Proactive local political initiatives on opening up Šventoji river did not gain support within the community, creating favorable environment for compromises such as the construction of fish passages. Governance structures often lack sensitivity to local contexts, applying national norms and procedures without adapting to the area's unique socio-cultural and ecological realities. This further creates an environment that excludes local communities and, as a result, reduces community support for environmental projects. Consequently, biodiversity challenges are often framed through infrastructural lenses, prioritizing solutions that achieve easier social acceptance over those that ensure long-term ecological resilience.

Culturally, there is a values conflict. Although many community members value ecology, knowledge about the dam's impacts is uneven. Some are aware of its ecological consequences, others underestimate them, and a few dismiss them entirely. The dam also embodies cultural meanings, e.g. historical, human achievement, which complicate efforts toward ecological change. As a familiar landmark, it symbolizes permanence even amid environmental degradation. This dual significance often leads to compromise-based decisions, favoring technological solutions that address a narrow range of problems (such as fish migration) while neglecting broader ecological functions like sediment transport.

In summary, the interwoven political, cultural, and institutional power dynamics shape governance narratives and do not facilitate the inclusion of local knowledge and values, costing both local support for ecological action and the success of such actions, as well as limiting the transformative potential of progressive ecological values.

4.4.1.7 Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector

National institutions (particularly environmental authorities) initiate actions to address biodiversity challenges at the national level. They view fish migration and longitudinal river connectivity restoration as key elements of national water policy, and through it they interact with Šventoji river and Anykščiai dam. These institutions cooperate with local authorities to implement measures and drive change, but their approach rarely involves direct collaboration with local communities.

Local institutions operate under their own norms and focus mainly on local issues, often without considering the broader national dam landscape. As a result, dams are seen less as ecological problems and more as unique pieces of infrastructure for which they are responsible—maintenance, safety, and operation included. Local institutions engage more directly with communities, seeking to balance ecological objectives with socially acceptable compromises.

4.4.1.8 Economic structures' impact over the SES

The dam is no longer directly linked to economic activity. It was once used for hydropower, but operations have ceased due to low energy potential—a small reservoir and limited flow. In more productive river systems, hydropower can constrain environmental action.

Indirectly, the dam still influences local economic activity. Restaurants and small businesses in the surrounding area may benefit from the landscape, and investments are directed toward riverside infrastructure that supports recreation for both locals and tourists. Although the dam itself is not seen as a tourist attraction or a defining symbol of Anykščiai, current infrastructure has been developed in relation to the current river landscape.

Dam removal has been discussed—though not formally evaluated—as a potential way to boost angling tourism, with fishing licenses possibly generating some revenue. There were respondents who viewed this as an opportunity, but, local attitudes remain mostly skeptical. Some kayakers viewed dam removal as an opportunity to expand kayaking routes, and improve safety for paddlers, while others believed the dam had little impact on either their operations or the overall kayaking experience.

It is worth adding that water management and environmental development are often tied to EU financing mechanisms. While some projects may receive state funding,

environmental protection remains underfunded within the national budget, making EU support the primary and most crucial source of funding for environmental initiatives.

4.4.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

In this case study, the locally identified biodiversity challenge centres on the ecological impacts of the Šventoji dam—particularly its obstruction of fish migration, disruption of habitats and river connectivity, and alteration of the natural fluvial ecosystem.

Biodiversity assessment is carried out through the national river monitoring scheme that is set as part of national implementation of EU Water Framework Directive. This framework identifies pressures and corresponding measures using a wide range of indicators, including biological parameters such as the fish index. These biological indicators are the key determinants of a river's ecological status. Data and measures related to ecological status are integrated into River Basin Management Plans, which set the overarching goal of achieving good ecological status in all rivers.

Supplementary scientific reports have identified the Šventoji dam as one of Lithuania's top priorities for improving fish migration, due to high ecological impacts, given its large upstream section that could be reconnected to the lower river if longitudinal connectivity were restored, and also low socio-economic benefits (e.g. no power production). The issue is further reinforced by national-level environmental organizations and NGOs, which consider the Anykščiai dam a key site for river restoration.

Locally, biodiversity challenges are recognized mainly by anglers who prefer natural river systems and by residents more aware of ecological issues. Older generations often recall past fish abundance, better water quality, and a more aesthetically pleasing river, noting visible declines in species diversity, fish numbers, and habitat availability over time—trends consistent with scientific monitoring data.

However, a large part of the community has limited personal or experiential connection to the river's biodiversity and therefore does not perceive ecosystem degradation as an immediate local issue.

4.4.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

The current SES both enables and constrains transformative innovation through a complex interplay of institutional, cultural, political, and economic factors.

At the national level, recognition of the issue and strong incentives from environmental authorities—supported by political actors and NGOs—create clear opportunities for transformative ecological change. This institutional momentum brings willingness, resources, and policy support for restoration efforts.

However, major constraints arise locally. Transforming a top-down initiative into a genuinely community-centered process requires meaningful integration of local needs and values. Barriers include deeply rooted cultural attitudes that prize human-made structures and engineering achievements over natural systems, as well as a strong attachment to preserving built heritage. A general lack of environmental awareness limited personal connection to the river, and few people directly engaged with biodiversity further weaken local support.

Uncertainty surrounding the consequences of dam removal—changes to landscape, safety, and aesthetics—fuels scepticism. Distrust in externally led projects, often seen as serving narrow interests, further limits participation and acceptance.

Despite these constraints, several leverage points exist. True transformation must emerge from within the community to ensure durability and legitimacy. Encouraging residents to reconnect with the river’s ecological and cultural significance could foster shared ownership and stewardship. Trust can be strengthened through transparent engagement: involving credible experts, presenting before-and-after visualizations, organizing participatory workshops, and genuinely embedding local priorities in project design.

Open communication, inclusive decision-making, and attention to broader social needs—especially of vulnerable groups—can turn scepticism into active engagement. Strengthening local environmental voices and granting them greater influence in governance remain key levers for lasting, community-rooted change.

4.4.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

Building on a nuanced understanding of the socio-ecological complexities revealed through interviews, this vision for the future of the local Social-Ecological System outlines a path toward inclusive, adaptive, and culturally grounded environmental governance. True transformation must emerge from within the community to ensure durability and legitimacy. It acknowledges the community’s values that shape human–nature relations in the case study area.

The river—both physically and symbolically—stands as the central axis of potential transformation. Reconnecting with its ecological and cultural significance can foster shared ownership and stewardship, turning passive acceptance into active engagement.

Such transformation depends not only on technical interventions but on collective, ongoing processes of reimagining and restoring relationships between people, place, and environment. Building trust is essential: involving credible experts, offering before-and-after visualizations, hosting participatory workshops, and embedding community priorities directly into project design. Through this open and inclusive approach, meaningful and lasting transformation can take root.

Reimagining Relationships Between Social and Ecological Actors

In this envisioned future, communities relate to the river and recognize it as an integral part of their community with its own identity. The Šventoji River, once viewed merely as an infrastructural utility for power generation or a backdrop for occasional events, is reinterpreted as a living ecological entity and a member of the community. Emotional and place-based attachments are embraced as vital entry points for ecological education and stewardship.

The vision includes the creation of participatory forums where local residents, municipal authorities, businesses, cultural actors, environmental NGOs, and academic researchers engage in regular, structured dialogue. These gatherings would promote knowledge sharing, collective reflection, and joint decision-making on the management of local ecological assets. The very process of co-creating these forums fosters a culture of dialogue, trust, and collaborative problem-solving—grounded in awareness, collective effort, and social inclusion.

Pluralizing Knowledge Systems and Governance Practices

A core tenet of this vision is the recognition that plural knowledge systems—scientific, local, traditional, and experiential—are essential for resilient SES governance. This involves both acknowledging and, where possible, integrating existing knowledge into the shared vision for the river. Equally, it requires fostering new experiential knowledge through direct engagement with the environment to strengthen connections with biodiversity.

Schools might establish outdoor biology classrooms along the riverbanks, merging ecological education with local history and storytelling. Oral histories could document elders' memories of the river before dam construction, alongside young people's visions for its future. Such initiatives challenge epistemic hierarchies and democratize knowledge creation, nurturing ecological awareness and a sense of shared ownership across generations.

Institutionally, governance structures could evolve toward genuinely community-centred arrangements. This entails including ecological actors into decision making processes—individuals and groups who interact directly with the environment. These actors could inform local decisions, lead environmental awareness initiatives, and strengthen the bridge between community and nature. Local NGOs and youth groups, acting as mediators, can help ensure transparent communication between residents and authorities. Together, these efforts lay the foundation for community-driven governance in which residents are active stewards of their river's future.

Reframing Economic Structures Around Ecological Values

Economic drivers have long shaped river damming and remain central to other environmental pressures. This vision proposes reframing local economic development to embed ecological values and align prosperity with environmental restoration.

Sustainable opportunities emerge along the riverside through eco-tourism, artisanal markets, and nature-based retreats. The former hydroelectric station is transformed into a Museum of Rivers and Dams, showcasing the history and future of river restoration. It becomes both a cultural hub and an economic catalyst—creating jobs, attracting visitors, and sharing stories of renewal.

Participatory budgeting and municipal green investment funds channel resources into community-led ecological projects and nature-based businesses, tourism. These mechanisms help ease local perceptions about financial instability by promoting transparency, shared responsibility, and long-term resilience.

Local businesses begin to integrate sustainability into their operations. Canoeing clubs, cafés, fishing cooperatives, and wellness retreats centre their activities around a restored and ecologically vibrant riverfront. Economic narratives shift from extraction and short-term profit toward regeneration and community-driven growth.

Cultural Transformation and Community Identity Renewal

This vision places cultural transformation at the heart of SES change. Recognizing the historical conservatism and emotional attachment to tradition, it seeks to revitalize local identity through ecological narratives. Annual River Festivals, storytelling competitions, environmental art installations, and seasonal ecological rituals are instituted, reweaving the river into the cultural fabric of community life.

A community-driven Šventoji River Journal project documents daily ecological changes, personal reflections, and historical anecdotes, creating an evolving communal artifact that strengthens place-based identities. The inclusion of the river in local theatre, poetry, and school curricula fosters intergenerational dialogue about ecological futures.

The revitalization of the river as both ecological asset and cultural symbol breaks the perceived binary between environmental care and community prosperity. It positions ecological restoration not as a technocratic imposition but as a deeply rooted cultural practice aligned with local values of heritage, continuity, and collective well-being.

Institutional Adaptation and Participatory Decision-Making

Institutions embrace to embrace participatory and culturally sensitive practices. Regular open assemblies enable residents to articulate concerns, propose initiatives, and engage in policy deliberations without fear of professional or social reprisal. Informal intermediaries, such as local NGOs and educational institutions, serve as trusted facilitators of dialogue and knowledge exchange.

Municipal employment practices are evolving to prioritize civic engagement and ecological stewardship. The goal is to create an environment where public servants and residents work together to address ecological challenges. Leadership programs for youth and community activists are nurturing a new generation of environmentally conscious and civically engaged leaders.

Ecological Restoration as Cultural and Social Healing

Ecological restoration projects, focused on habitat restoration and reintroduction of lost species — are reframed as acts of cultural healing and community renewal. Restoration milestones are marked by communal celebrations and educational activities, reinforcing emotional ties to ecological processes.

The visible ecological benefits — improved water quality, restored biodiversity corridors, increased fish stocks — enhance local recreation, health, and well-being. These ecological gains, coupled with cultural and economic revitalization, transform the river from a neglected infrastructural relic into a dynamic, living protagonist in the town's collective narrative.

Conclusion: Realizing a Culturally Embedded, Inclusive, and Resilient SES Future

This expanded vision recognizes the current dynamics within the community, including a limited connection to river biodiversity, gaps in ecological understanding, perceptions of hierarchical governance, and the insufficient integration of community perspectives into decision-making. At the same time, it highlights meaningful opportunities for change—particularly the potential for ecological transformation emerging from within the community itself, rather than being externally driven.

Although supportive national and international frameworks are already in place, there remains a pressing need for locally grounded initiatives that foster momentum and strengthen collective commitment to environmental action, while minimizing resistance and ensuring shared ownership.

Through sustained dialogue, the inclusion of diverse knowledge systems, transparent governance practices, and the integration of ecological values into local economic and

cultural life, the community can evolve from passive participants to active partners in shaping their ecological and social futures.

This is a pragmatic yet optimistic vision—rooted in local realities and community resilience—that affirms sustainable, inclusive, and culturally resonant transformation is both necessary and attainable through collaborative, adaptive, and participatory processes.

4.4.3 Discussion

The *Free-Flowing Rivers* case study highlights the dynamics of the social-ecological system (SES) in Anykščiai, shaped by the interplay between national policymakers, scientists, local authorities, and community actors. National institutions influence the system through EU-aligned environmental policies and scientific expertise, while local governance emphasizes infrastructure, recreation, and community well-being, though often within limited ecological capacities. Businesses and cultural sectors contribute in diverse ways, yet their focus tends to remain on recreational and social dimensions rather than ecological restoration.

The SES underscores the importance of strengthening locally grounded collaboration, nurturing the community's experiential connection with the river and its biodiversity, and fostering more community-centered practices. Building trust, inclusion, and meaningful participation in decision-making is essential for effective engagement. Encouraging a shared sense of ownership and care for the river can enable transformative change—where environmental outcomes emerge from an internalized commitment to stewardship and a deeper awareness of ecological interdependence.

Multi-Level Governance and Knowledge Integration Challenges

A defining feature of the Šventoji River social-ecological system (SES) in Anykščiai is the diversity of actors and knowledge systems that shape its governance. National authorities, policymakers, and scientific experts play a leading role in defining biodiversity-related goals through EU-aligned frameworks and environmental assessments. Their expertise provides an essential foundation for understanding ecological pressures such as disrupted connectivity and species decline, yet engagement with local communities remains limited, and scientific knowledge often circulates primarily within institutional and policy settings. This reflects a broader governance tendency in which technical and scientific approaches, while robust, are not always effectively connected to local experience or community dialogue (Turnhout et al., 2016).

Local authorities and municipal representatives act as intermediaries between national institutions and the community. While positioned to interpret local concerns, their autonomy is constrained by financial dependencies, administrative structures, and the need to balance ecological aims with priorities such as infrastructure, recreation, and visible public benefits. Consequently, ecological restoration is frequently pursued through technical or engineering measures (such as building and improving fish passages) rather than integrated, ecosystem-based strategies.

Civil society organizations, local residents, and businesses contribute valuable experiential knowledge and play an active role in maintaining public attention on river issues. However, limited resources, uneven access to decision-making, and cautious community attitudes toward change reduce their influence. Historical experiences of externally driven projects

have reinforced a preference for stability and predictability in local governance. Together, these dynamics create a system characterized by fragmented coordination and uneven integration of knowledge, underscoring the need for trust-building, transparent communication, and the inclusion of diverse perspectives to strengthen shared stewardship of the river.

Scientific Frameworks and the Need to Integrate Local Values

The governance of the Šventoji River SES is strongly influenced by science-based approaches to understanding biodiversity challenges. These frameworks—focused on issues such as barriers for fish migration, habitat fragmentation and deterioration, and ecosystem degradation—provide essential analytical clarity and guide national and local environmental planning. However, their communication often remains confined to policy documents and technical assessments, with limited translation into locally relevant or culturally meaningful narratives (Wyborn et al., 2019).

Alongside these formal frameworks, the river is also understood through local and experiential knowledge, shaped by generations of direct interaction. This perspective provides valuable ecological insights and reflects deep cultural and emotional connections to the river, yet it remains largely absent from institutional decision-making. The uneven inclusion of different knowledge systems contributes to a gap between ecological policy objectives and community perspectives, often resulting in reduced local support for environmental initiatives.

This gap also reflects differences in how the river’s significance is understood. For many residents, the dam remains a familiar and stable part of the landscape—associated with stability, familiarity and local well-being—whereas ecological restoration initiatives may appear uncertain or disruptive. Strengthening dialogue between scientific and community perspectives can help align biodiversity goals with social values, fostering a shared understanding of both the ecological and cultural dimensions of the river.

Institutional, Cultural, and Economic Barriers to Transformative Change

The case study identifies several institutional, cultural, and economic factors that constrain transformative innovation within the local social-ecological system (SES). Institutionally, governance remains largely top-down. Although many initiatives are pro-environmental, limited participatory engagement, low public trust, and the absence of a shared community-driven vision for biodiversity create significant barriers to long-term change. This dynamic often leads to the pursuit of compromise solutions—such as the construction of fish passages—that appear practical and socio-politically acceptable but deliver limited ecological benefits and fail to foster genuine community involvement.

Culturally, the community’s preference for stability is reinforced by past experiences with projects that were either poorly implemented or misaligned with local needs and values. These experiences have contributed to skepticism toward new initiatives, particularly those perceived as externally imposed or serving narrow interests. As a result, open dialogue about the river’s future remains limited, and proactive advocacy for ecological restoration is rare.

Economically, barriers are less pronounced but remain relevant. The dam no longer serves an energy-producing function, and the reservoir provides only modest benefits, such as limited angling activities. However, the river’s restoration could create new economic opportunities—particularly through enhanced recreation, kayaking routes, and angling

tourism—if supported by strategic planning and community engagement. At present, local investments primarily focus on riverside infrastructure that sustains existing recreational uses, while broader ecological projects rely heavily on EU funding. Strengthening local capacity to leverage these opportunities and connect ecological restoration with sustainable economic development could help overcome existing financial and institutional constraints.

Opportunities for Transformative Governance and Local Engagement

Despite existing constraints, the case study highlights several opportunities for advancing transformative governance within the local social-ecological system (SES).

There is already a strong institutional foundation for action, with national and EU policy frameworks supportive of river restoration. This favorable policy environment could be reinforced by improving technical capacity for preparatory activities and strategically combining financial mechanisms. Aligning funding streams from different sectors—such as public infrastructure, rural development, and regional planning—could enable larger-scale, integrated projects that address both ecological restoration and broader community needs, rather than focusing solely on dam removal.

Facilitating deeper community engagement represents another key opportunity. Moving toward more community-centered decision-making, strengthening local connections to river biodiversity, and fostering a shared sense of ownership and care for the river can help generate long-term, durable change. Establishing participatory structures—such as community assemblies, biodiversity councils, or cross-sector working groups—would support inclusive dialogue, trust-building, and joint problem-solving (Newig et al., 2023).

Economic diversification further reinforces these prospects. Linking biodiversity restoration with sustainable local development—through eco-tourism, recreation-based businesses, and small-scale artisanal initiatives—could create new incentives for ecological stewardship. Realizing this potential requires a gradual shift from short-term, growth-oriented planning toward regenerative, community-centered models that integrate environmental restoration with local prosperity and social well-being.

Toward Inclusive SES Governance

The findings from this case study align with broader discussions in social-ecological systems (SES) research: effective biodiversity restoration depends on policy support, sustained financial investment towards environmental action, and genuine community engagement. Transformation cannot rely solely on technical solutions—it must also take place within communities, through processes that reimagine and redefine the relationship between people and nature. Such engagement is essential for achieving lasting ecological and social sustainability.

Within this context, relational approaches to SES governance—those that emphasize emotional connections, place-based identities, and intergenerational knowledge—hold significant promise for fostering enduring stewardship. Building trust between communities and experts through transparent preparation, professional competence, and open communication can empower residents to take ownership of their environment and embed their values and needs into the shared vision for the river's future.

Transformative governance, therefore, calls for institutionalized participatory decision-making and the integration of ecological values into cultural, social, and economic life. Only

through these inclusive and culturally grounded processes can ecological restoration translate into long-term resilience and community-driven stewardship.

Conclusion

This discussion highlights the interdependence of multi-level governance, scientific frameworks, and community engagement, shaping the Šventoji River social-ecological system (SES) in Anykščiai. At present, environmental governance related to free-flowing rivers in the region remains fragmented, with limited participatory capacity within the community and a predominance of technical solutions—such as fish passages—that foster good environment for compromises: they neither meaningfully integrate community perspectives nor deliver the most effective outcomes from an environmental standpoint. However, opportunities emerge from strong institutional support for environmental action, existing local connections to the river, and the potential to develop nature-based economic activities. Future efforts should focus on integrating scientific and local knowledge, strengthening participatory decision-making, and linking biodiversity restoration with sustainable economic and cultural development, ensuring that river governance evolves through shared ownership, trust, and long-term community stewardship.

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4.5 High Nature Value Farming, Romania

Authors: Andreea Ocrain (UBB)

The Romanian case study examines how biodiversity conservation can coexist with sustainable rural development in the Sighișoara-Târnava Mare region, one of Romania's largest Natura 2000 areas, covering approximately 85,000 hectares. This landscape boasts remarkable biodiversity, featuring over 1,000 plant species, 55 endangered bird species, and 23 endangered mammal species, including wolves, bears, and wildcats. It also reflects centuries of coexistence between people and nature through traditional farming, grazing, and cultural practices.

Today, these high-nature-value farmlands are increasingly threatened by land abandonment, agricultural intensification, depopulation, and economic inequalities that particularly affect marginalized groups such as Roma communities. At the heart of the case study lies the challenge of aligning biodiversity protection with the social and economic realities of rural life. Traditional land management once ensured both ecological and cultural balance, but changes in policy and market structures have weakened these systems. The decline in small-scale farming, the loss of communal herding, and the erosion of traditional knowledge have disrupted ecological processes. At the same time, migration and aging populations have reduced the number of active land stewards. As a result, pastures are overgrown, water resources are drying up, and biodiversity tied to open landscapes is in decline.

Research combining participatory workshops (implemented in June 2024) reveals that local people understand nature through relational and emotional experiences rather than technical definitions. They value the landscape for its beauty, productivity, and significance, seeing it as an integral part of their identity. However, their knowledge and perspectives are often excluded from decision-making dominated by top-down policies. Building inclusive governance requires revaluing traditional ecological knowledge and fostering cooperation among farmers, scientists, NGOs, and policymakers. Several community-led innovations demonstrate potential for transformative change. Efforts to restore hay meadows, protect native species, revive orchards, and reintroduce buffalo grazing have not only enhanced biodiversity but also strengthened local identity and tourism.

Education, shared learning networks, and environmental awareness initiatives are proving effective in engaging both adults and children. Yet, obstacles such as climate change, weak policy enforcement, and short-term economic pressures continue to hinder progress. The case study shows that enduring biodiversity regeneration depends not only on ecological restoration but also on revitalizing the human communities that care for nature. Sustainable transformation emerges where conservation supports local livelihoods, respects cultural traditions, and empowers people to act collectively. In these Transylvanian villages, human resilience and ecological renewal are inseparable foundations for a sustainable future.

4.5.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

4.5.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

The territorial SES in the Romanian study case region impacts different actor groups in various ways, as SES influences access to land, resources, identity, and governance. Small-scale farmers are one of the most visibly impacted groups. Many of them still practice slow, traditional farming methods, such as haymaking and low-input livestock husbandry, which are integral to the area's biodiversity and landscape character. Their livelihoods are tied

firmly to the ecological health of grasslands, forests, and water. However, changes in agricultural policy, land ownership, and youth migration have weakened material connections to the land. Farmers are now often farming to access subsidy programs rather than to meet the needs of their community, a phenomenon also observed by Fischer et al. (2012).

The older community members have a strong connection to the land, one that has been cultivated over decades of embodied experience with the environment, such as tending an orchard, harvesting herbs, or managing hay pastures, often alongside their family members. These relationships convey a profound connection that underpins both traditional ecological knowledge and cultural identity (Balázs et al., 2019). Older residents, as noted among interviewees in the Hartel et al. (2023) study, frequently spoke of the landscape as home, part of themselves, or even as sacred.

By contrast, younger people experience cognitive and affective disconnection. Their lesser material dependence on the land, as well as greater digitization and out-migration, have led to a decline in interest in local ecological and rural continuity. However, this disconnection is not irreversible - some returning youths connect with the land in new ways through tourism, food, or the practice of permaculture, often transforming tradition into hybrid innovation (for example, a tea house opened by a woman in one of the villages).

Marginalized communities, particularly Roma people, present and experience vulnerabilities as well. Frequently lacking official land rights or political representation, they rely on the informal use of natural resources, such as foraging, and are particularly vulnerable to environmental degradation and institutional neglect. Their interests are commonly excluded from conservation and land use planning, perpetuating systematic exclusion.

Other players, such as NGOs, scientists, and local authorities, play various roles in shaping the SES. NGOs and conservationists, often operating within institutional frameworks that prioritize measurable outcomes and biodiversity targets, tend to approach the SES from a technocratic or scientific perspective. While they are essential actors in channeling funding, promoting conservation, and legitimizing scientific knowledge, the broader institutional systems within which they operate can limit their deeper engagement with local values and experiential learning. Through activities like those organized by BioTraces, gaps between different ways of understanding nature can be bridged as they bring together diverse actors who might not otherwise have a space to collaborate or engage in dialogue.

The more-than-human agents, such as pollinators, wild plants, and protected animals, are also conditioned by the SES. Their health is closely entwined with traditional farming systems, which present the open, species-diverse spaces they need. When these systems change or break apart, habitat quality declines, and biodiversity loss consequently emerges (Bignal and McCracken, 1996).

Overall, the SES is a complex web of interdependencies and vulnerabilities. When it changes under social, political, or economic pressures, it not only alters the landscape but also affects relationships, knowledge systems, and identities. Appreciation of these impacts across actor groups is necessary for constructing interventions that are both sustainable and equitable.

4.5.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

Decision-making regarding the SES in the RO study case occurs within a complex and often fragmented governance system, where institutions, traditional practices, and external

policies overlap, interact, and frequently clash. Local officials, such as mayors and municipal councilors, are formally responsible for rural development and land-use decisions. However, their ability to actively support sustainable SES pathways is often limited by underfunding, limited ecological expertise, and reliance on broader national and EU policy frameworks that they do not directly control.

The Common Agricultural Policy is one of the most influential drivers of land-use decisions (Bignal and McCracken, 1996; Plieninger et al., 2015). Its structure tends to prioritize herd size and land ownership, which can unintentionally favor practices like overgrazing, monocultures, or subsidy-oriented production [6]. As a result, actors with larger landholdings and stronger administrative capacity (often external investors or agribusinesses) are more likely to shape land management decisions. This dynamic can marginalize traditional farmers and smallholders, despite their crucial role in maintaining High-Nature-Value farming systems.

Civil society actors, such as ADEPT, and cultural institutions, like Muzeul Etnografic al Transilvaniei (MET), play various but complementary roles in governance. While ADEPT performs the technical intermediary function, enabling biodiversity monitoring and providing support to farmers with conservation-friendly practices, MET helps in retaining and transmitting traditional knowledge, cultural values, and customs closely tied to High Nature Value farming. Their influence, even if it is very significant, is often limited by a lack of structural integration into formal governance processes.

Power asymmetries are reinforced through social and cultural structures. Older women, though principal custodians of traditional knowledge, are not involved in strategic decision-making. Formal planning processes are almost bereft of Roma communities because there is systemic discrimination, and institutional inclusion is weak. Participatory workshops with BIOTraCes and other initiatives demonstrate that decision-making is often perceived as being “done to” local people rather than “with” them.

Additionally, ecological actors, including species, habitats, and ecosystem processes, are significantly impacted by human decision-making. Despite the use of formal policies, such as the Natura 2000 network, to represent their interests in governance, designations are often made in a top-down manner (Roellig et al., 2018). While there is a legal obligation to consult with local communities and interested stakeholders when preparing plans for the management of Natura 2000, this is often poorly adhered to in practice. Many locals are unaware of the activity or choose not to participate, perhaps because they see little relevance or connection between the proposed conservation actions and their everyday realities and priorities. Consequently, the substance of these plans is largely unknown to many, and local input is not effectively incorporated. Hence, priorities for conservation may not align with local values or practices, and biodiversity relies on the performance of human institutions to express and respond to ecological needs. This generates a paradox: biodiversity-rich habitats rely upon traditional practice, while the actors who perpetuate them are excluded from decision-making. Meanwhile, species, habitats, and ecosystems are significantly impacted by these choices, as they lack direct presence or agency in decision-making structures. Although policies such as those for Natura 2000 are intended to meet their needs, the success of these frameworks relies on how effectively human institutions interpret, implement, and integrate them with local realities.

In summary, the governance of the SES is characterized by institutional fragmentation, unequal power relations, and limited communication between decision-makers and those most directly affected by their choices. Addressing this imbalance requires more than just institutional reform; it calls for epistemic justice, which involves recognizing and

integrating diverse knowledge systems, cultural identities, and place-based relationships with nature into governance frameworks that are inclusive, grounded, and contextually relevant.

4.5.1.3 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

In the RO case study, various kinds of knowledge intersect to shape how biodiversity is understood, valued, and governed. Science- and policy-led framings are mostly dominant, and these are carried forward through EU conservation models such as Natura 2000. These are represented by ecological indicators, species checklists, and expert judgments to shape management priorities and designate protected sites. Whilst scientifically robust, these framings are often disconnected from local people's everyday experience.

Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK), rooted in generations of place-based practices, continues to play a significant role in shaping the perceptions of and responses to biodiversity shifts among local stakeholders. This includes practices like rotational grazing and seasonal mowing, as well as understanding the ecological importance of pastures and hay meadows. TEK has supported high levels of biodiversity long before the concept was recognized in formal policy. However, it is often overlooked in official governance structures or acknowledged only in a symbolic way rather than being meaningfully integrated into decision-making.

PAR methods employed throughout the BIOTraCes workshops demonstrated that locals perceive biodiversity not only in terms of the number of species or types of habitats but also through relational and emotional experiences. For example, participants described biodiversity not in abstract scientific terms, but through vivid sensory and emotional experiences, such as the visual beauty of flower-rich hayfields, the distinct taste of wild fruits gathered by hand, and the deep emotional resonance of working the land in rhythm with the seasons.

These interpretations, though less quantifiable, reflect deeply embedded values that motivate conservation-minded behavior. These insights from the workshops illustrate the contrast between local knowledge and dominant scientific framings, highlighting the need to integrate multiple ways of knowing into biodiversity governance.

Ultimately, the governance in the case study environment is presently biased towards institutional and specialized knowledge, with traditional and experiential knowledge still under-integrated. It's not just the challenge of translation between systems, but also the task of rebalancing authority and creating enabling conditions for truly co-producing knowledge.

4.5.1.4 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

The Sighișoara-Târnava Mare landscape is a historically co-evolved social-ecological system sustained through low-intensity, multifunctional agriculture. Traditional land-use activities, including the management of hay meadows, pastoral grazing, and crop rotation, have traditionally provided high biodiversity support through a mosaic structure of the landscape. These activities help support soil health, water retention, and habitat diversity, which are critical ecological processes essential for sustaining the system's resilience.

Ecologically, the SES comprises an active mix of orchards, pastures, spring-fed areas, forest patches, and meadows. These habitats are primarily High Nature Value farmland and are home to threatened plant and animal species, which are protected under national and EU conservation legislation. The health of the system relies on how seasonal patterns and spatial variety are maintained. For example, mowing late, grazing just enough, and avoiding overuse of chemicals are all crucial in conserving the rich natural capital.

Still, several direct drivers are now clearly undermining these ecological processes. The most significant ones include:

1. Overgrazing, which is partly promoted by CAP subsidies that reward numbers of livestock but lack adequate ecological guarantees, causes soil compaction, lowered plant diversity, and degradation of habitats.
2. Abandonment of the traditional farming practices, particularly in remote or unproductive regions, facilitates shrub encroachment and loss of open habitat specialists.
3. Intensification of agriculture, i.e., increase in monoculture crops (e.g., maize), application of chemical inputs, and mechanized land conversion, tends to disrupt the ecological balance.
4. The locals described climate impacts, such as extended droughts and changing precipitation patterns, as increasingly interfering with water availability and vegetation dynamics.
5. Infrastructure growth and fencing, particularly in forested environments, break up ecological corridors and restrict wildlife movement, further fragmenting the network.

Locals have noticed changes in the timing of flower blooms, the availability of water, and the presence of species, as well as the disappearance of others. These observations suggest a decline in the balance between human use and ecological recovery. Most notably, the loss of traditional practices impacts not just the continuity of culture but also undermines the subtle feedback relationships that sustain ecosystem function.

Understanding this SES thus requires both ecological indicators and local experiential knowledge. Results from the BIOTraCes workshops in Apold, Biertan, Boiu, Malancrav, Saschiz, and Soard further underlined perceived local ecological stressors and processes. Drying out of springs and shrub invasions were identified as direct consequences of unsustainable actions. The abandonment of traditional mowing and the decline of crop rotation were both highlighted as concerns for landscape biodiversity. In some areas, the spread of mechanized agriculture and the loss of traditional knowledge passed down between generations have weakened the local community's ability to manage the land in a way that maintains ecological balance.

Another profoundly felt driver is climate, particularly through drying and declining water tables, both of which affect vegetation cycles and grazing regimes. Local actors also pointed out that in many places, ecosystems are no longer protected and stabilized by traditional land-use practices, such as clearing springs, rotating grazing areas, or drying hay in stacks. These methods, once essential for maintaining balance in the landscape, are now disappearing due to labor shortages, limited economic incentives, and shifting attitudes toward farming and manual labor.

Thus, the SES's operation depends not just on ecological patterns but also on the continuity of low-intensity practices that co-evolved with the landscape. Without active maintenance, these practices and the biodiversity they support are vulnerable to irreversible loss. Re-establishing this equilibrium is imperative for stopping biodiversity loss and assuring long-term system vitality.

4.5.1.5 Values underpinning decision-making processes

The three value categories from our case study (relational, instrumental, and intrinsic) have a subtle but significant influence on the local community's interactions with land use decisions. These values do not directly influence formal policy, but they can influence people's responses to policies, including whether they trust them and whether they get involved (Tieskens et al. 2017). Local biodiversity has a profound impact on daily existence: wild fruits are sweeter, grassy fields are picturesque, and traditional cultivation practices are meaningful. These values stood out clearly during the workshops and reflect the kind of knowledge and motivation that most ecological indicators fail to capture.

Natura 2000 or CAP tend to emphasize scientific and economic concerns rather than relational and cultural values, which are underrepresented in these formal policies. Disconnection can lead to mistrust or conflict if locals perceive that their traditions are being marginalized. However, there are also positive indicators. Ecotourism, branding of local products, and community programs are areas where emotional and cultural values align with biodiversity objectives. These programs suggest that governance can incorporate more diverse values beyond those based on science. Local values need to be viewed not as secondary but as key in developing accepted and sustainable land-use decisions.

4.5.1.6 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

Sighișoara–Târnava Mare (Saschiz) SES governance is conditioned by intertwined sets of political, cultural, and institutional power relations that shape what kinds of knowledge and values are considered legitimate and whose voices prevail in decision-making.

Politically, the SES is regulated by a top-down model, mainly through the national implementation of EU policies, including the Common Agricultural Policy and Natura 2000. These institutions determine priorities and allocate resources based on ecological and economic indicators created at upper levels of governance. Local political stakeholders, including municipal councils and mayors, often lack environmental knowledge and tend to act more as administrators of outside policies rather than facilitators of place-based governance. Consequently, the valuable knowledge that local people possess is often not utilized or respected when decisions are made. Marginal populations, and particularly Roma communities, are politically invisible and excluded even from local processes. This political unevenness constricts the range of values and knowledge included in SES governance.

Culturally, SES has roots in balancing traditions that include manual haymaking, rotational grazing, and spring care, but are increasingly devalued. Agriculture in younger age groups is often perceived as burdensome or outdated, fueled by formal education systems and mainstream socio-economic ambitions that devalue rural livelihoods. The cultural disconnect has eroded the intergenerational transmission of ecological knowledge. On the other hand, people in the older generation have strong identity-based values and relational values regarding the landscape. Still, they are rarely recognized in mainstream narratives that often reinforce biodiversity as a technical or policy tool. As a result, local values and cultural knowledge systems are either marginalized or superficially incorporated into project reports, yet not fully embedded in the structural contexts.

Institutionally, power is held by outside agencies, funding institutions, and intermediaries, such as NGOs. These actors play essential roles in mediating between the scientific and local worlds, but they do not alter the deeper power dynamics or who controls agendas and resources.

All these factors combine to shape a system of governance where scientific and institutional knowledge tends to dominate, while local, lived, and traditional perspectives are often overlooked or included only superficially. For governance to be fairer and more effective, it's not enough to involve more people; it's essential to respect and act on the value of different ways of knowing and connecting with the land.

4.5.1.7 Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector

Broader policies, particularly EU environmental and agricultural regulations, largely shape the way the Saschiz area is managed. These policies will determine the boundaries under which decisions are made locally, limiting the actual freedom local people and officials have.

Within such external systems, the loss of biodiversity is typically viewed as a scientific or technical issue, to be managed through tools, legislation, and economic incentives. While such an approach enables programs like Natura 2000 to be implemented, it often overlooks local cultural understandings of nature and sustainability. CAP rewards eligibility and compliance rather than ecological quality or local engagement. As a result, local governance usually follows external templates, limiting innovation and responsiveness to local values. Even where traditional approaches (like low-density grazing or maintaining hay meadows) are essential for nature, they are poorly funded unless they fit within the parameters of subsidy schemes. This mismatch can make people feel left out and discouraged.

Organizations such as NGOs and Local Action Groups (LAGs) are attempting to bridge the gap between local needs and broader policy goals. Yet, they continue to operate within the same top-down systems. For governance to truly improve, there needs to be a greater balance that reflects not just environmental data and targets, but also the cultural and social ways in which people care for and relate to nature.

4.5.1.8 Economic structures' impact over the SES

Economic structures in our case study put both direct and subtle pressures upon land use and biodiversity. The most powerful economic driver is the CAP, which provides subsidies for land eligibility and herd size but disregards ecological value. This compels many farmers to adopt practices that rely on subsidies, such as overgrazing and the expansion of monocultures, despite their detrimental ecological consequences.

Market structures often fail to support small producers. Furthermore, across almost every workshop, the profile of those most adversely affected by environmental changes (specifically, changes in socioeconomic status) often corresponded to that of small-scale farmers. The area is rich in traditional knowledge and high-value products; yet many marginal producers encounter difficulties entering the macro-markets due to poor infrastructure, inadequate branding, and limited marketing channels. Therefore, their products remain underpriced in the economic system, making traditional land management practices financially nonviable.

Economic marginalization affects smallholders and marginalized communities most strongly, as they often lack access to capital and formal land titles and have inadequate financial support. The groups are more likely to rely on informal economies, face systematic exclusions, or disengage from a range of formal governance and conservation initiatives.

There are promising but still small-scale support measures linked to local production, such as ecotourism or HNV product branding. Without institutional support and further investment, however, their influence cannot hope to challenge the dominant economic situation.

4.5.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

Biodiversity in the Saschiz region is assessed through both formal institutional methods and local observations. Institutions and authorities adopt systematic approaches, such as habitat mapping, species monitoring, and remote sensing, primarily to implement European Union policies, including the Natura 2000 initiative. These methods are based on scientific indicators and thus often disconnect from the way biodiversity is experienced and interpreted locally.

Communities, according to workshop findings, monitor biodiversity through their lived experiences, including the observation of fewer pollinators, risks to flowering, and a lack of water. This knowledge is informal and specific to the places concerned.

Although the value of local knowledge is recognized, it rarely enters formal assessments. Consequently, many more people believe that the planning of biodiversity is somewhat detached from what they see. In practice, a more effective approach would be to integrate scientific data with local relationships, which are then used for an assessment that is both feasible and grounded in a social perspective.

4.5.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

Workshops, participatory research, and institutional analyses have shown that the present socioeconomic status (SES) of the Saschiz region is both an enabler and a constraint towards transformative change. Key constraints:

1. Policy lock-ins of the CAP rewarding scale and intensity over biodiversity.
2. Weaknesses in marketing and capitalization of traditional products.
3. Reduction in the intergenerational transfer of traditional knowledge due to migration and cultural change.
4. Social and economic marginalization of the disadvantaged groups, in particular the Roma communities.
5. Fragmented governance with participation that often has no real influence.

Conversely, opportunities can act as levers for change:

1. The existence of Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) and cultural values, at least among the elders.
2. A strong attachment to their landscape and a place-based identity.
3. Committed local NGOs, cultural institutions such as MET, and active academic partners.
4. Local interest in biocultural products and ecotourism, linking the economy with incentives for biodiversity protection.

Insights from the workshops suggested that many local actors are motivated by the relational and intrinsic values of nature, which can be harnessed through a supportive system. For example, small-scale farmers and rural households could take on active roles in biodiversity stewardship if they were supported not just through financial incentives but through approaches that strengthen their emotional and cultural connection to nature. Initiatives rooted in ecotourism or local product identity provide more durable and meaningful motivations than compliance-based subsidies alone [3].

To conclude, the SES has real transformational potential, but only if governance and economic systems change to enable bottom-up innovation, plural forms of knowledge, and socio-inclusivity. If the SES stays the same, opportunities will remain isolated, and

systemic change is unlikely. Participatory research processes have enabled the connection of diverse research voices and perspectives, made common or shared values visible, and validated the importance of local knowledge. There remains social cohesion and landscape identity in many locations that may be tapped to capture existing motivations and community connections to the land. Existing practices, such as late mowing and low-intensity grazing, can support biodiversity and may be sustained and increased with the appropriate policy environment and economic incentives. Transformative change is highly likely to depend on the system's willingness to accept and incorporate diverse knowledge systems, redistribute power in decision-making, and develop interrelated policies that simultaneously support ecological, cultural, and economic resilience. If these changes do not occur, innovation will continue to be fragmented or, at the very least, insufficient in driving systemic change. However, the SES has the potential for biodiversity-sensitive and socially just transformation if the right structural barriers are tackled and local capacities are activated.

4.5.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

Based on the dynamics, power relations, and tensions articulated in the previous analysis, this vision further develops what a more just, resilient, and locally grounded Sustainable Energy System (SES) might look like in the Sighișoara-Târnava Mare region. Instead of following the trajectory implied by top-down policy, short-term economic gain, and a symbolic form of participation, this vision imagines a system of relations grounded in everyday interaction, awareness, and shared knowledge between people and the landscapes they inhabit and shape.

In this system of relations, biodiversity is not only a distinct element aimed to be 'protected'; it is the expression of identity, memory, and lived experience. Traditional practices such as rotational grazing, spring maintenance, preserving ancient, isolated trees on pastures, and manual haymaking are revived not just through compensation schemes but also because they are once again valued by the community, embedded in local economies (e.g., ecotourism, biocultural products), and integrated into education as well. For younger generations, they return or stay; they no longer view farming as an indicator of failure, but rather as a part of a meaningful way of life that combines love for nature, day-to-day creativity, and social cohesion. Many no longer desire to migrate to cities because they prefer the tranquil lifestyle of the village surrounded by beauty and history. Young people can stay involved and connected to nature through rewarding and community-driven work, thanks to employment options in the local economy, which include booming tourism sectors, vital local government organizations like Local Action Groups (LAGs), and environmental NGOs. They are no longer viewed as foreigners in their own villages, feel empowered, and participate in decision-making. Some decide to join in small-scale farming associations, which help their communities become more resilient by combining traditional expertise with modern equipment. Youth are not only present in this vision but also play a key role in maintaining and redefining the SES's future.

Governance is transformed: participation is no longer symbolic but structural. Local actors not only respond to policies; they actively participate in their creation from the beginning. Platforms for making decisions are diverse and multilingual. Historical, emotional, and experiential types of information are discussed alongside scientific indicators. Natura 2000 evolves into a shared framework that can be interpreted locally, allowing for flexibility and adaptation rather than a checklist. Through constant presence and involvement with community-defined priorities, institutions gain trust by being open and accountable. Women, Roma, and youth are not only participants in governance spaces but also leaders within them. Locals collaborate to develop adaptive land-use regulations and biodiversity

monitoring instruments, resulting in a governance structure that incorporates ecological knowledge and local experience.

This SES is no longer economically reliant on extractive models or on subsidies for compliance. Instead, networks of cooperation between farmers, conservationists, tour guides, educators, and craftspeople who jointly create value rooted in the landscape are what create economic resilience. Biodiversity-friendly practices are rewarded by markets not only because they are branded as “green”, but also because they help communities and consumers reconnect with the sources of their food and customs. As regional income streams diversify, new opportunities emerge, including year-round cultural events and sustainable tourism, which draw tourists and generate steady employment. While digital connectivity and infrastructure help local businesses, media coverage and narratives raise awareness of the community and landscape. Carbon sequestration programs generate additional revenue by compensating for traditional practices such as crop rotation or maintaining isolated ancient trees on pasture. By creating and retaining value locally, local economies become increasingly circular, promoting the welfare of both ecosystems and people.

Ecosystem services, such as pollination, soil fertility, water regulation, and climate moderation, among others, are acknowledged as essential components of both ecological health and economic resilience. These services are actively preserved through community stewardship, sustainable practices, and context-specific policies tailored to the local environment rather than being taken for granted. Land users who maintain and improve these functions are directly rewarded by mechanisms such as payments for ecosystem services (PES). At the same time, practices such as small-scale farming and maintaining a mosaic landscape structure represent indirect outcomes. The SES adopts a more comprehensive and integrated view of value, recognizing that biodiversity conservation, food systems, human well-being, and climate action are all interconnected through the health and functionality of the ecosystems that sustain them. By allowing communities to share ownership of the protection and benefits of local nature, this reinterpretation also promotes a more democratic allocation of accountability and advantages.

Nature-positivity in this vision does not imply separating nature from people but rather acknowledging humans as integral parts of the environment. It represents a way of life in which human well-being and environmental regeneration are mutually reinforcing objectives rather than antagonistic ones. According to this viewpoint, nature is valued not only for its benefits and economic potential but also for its capacity to uphold relationships, meaning, and identity. Instead of focusing on control and extraction, it redefines prosperity through coexistence and harmony with natural boundaries. Secure access to land, intergenerational knowledge spaces, ecological monitoring conducted by locals, and support for cultural continuity are some of the conditions that local institutions provide for the new Sustainable Economic System (SES), which is founded on care and respect.

The balance of power is also rebalanced. With the help of specific inclusion mechanisms and cultural recognition, Roma voices are no longer marginalized and are now actively involved in local and regional governance processes. In addition to being valued, women's knowledge actively influences governance and land management choices and is frequently reflected in routine activities. To transition from a top-down to a community-driven SES model, local youth take on leadership roles in associations, advisory councils, and ecotourism projects. Institutions are now more accountable and transparent, and they are working with those who will be impacted to co-create solutions rather than relying on

administrative hierarchies. There is a more equitable distribution of power among generations, genders, ethnic groups, and occupations.

The biodiversity challenge is no longer presented as a remote or exclusively technical problem in this vision. For communities that depend on the land for their livelihoods, identities, and futures, it becomes something that is deeply felt and constantly checked. In addition to being quantified through indicators, biodiversity is also observed, discussed, and cared for in everyday activities, such as through the cycles of farming, the celebration of seasonal abundance, and the collective responsibilities of stewardship. By using their emotional, historical, and experiential knowledge to inform their decisions, local actors actively co-define what thriving ecosystems look like. Built on place-based ethics and shared futures, transformation is a continuous collective practice rather than a one-time endeavor. Continuity and change coexist in this new SES, as new forms of sustainability and care are established alongside respect for traditional knowledge. Through this continuous process, the integrity of the local social-ecological fabric is restored, enabling communities to confidently, creatively, and resiliently envision and implement shared futures.

The “roots” of this changed SES are trust and cooperation, which are gradually restored through inclusive decision-making, shared accountability, and a reciprocal understanding of each actor’s function within the system. This collective imagination was also captured in a visual representation (Figure 1), co-created from the insights gathered during the workshop. By reviving collective action, neighbors once again join forces, rebuilding a sense of community and mutual support. When individuals recognize that they can accomplish more as a team than they can individually, a collaborative culture develops. The “trunk” of this new system is traditional knowledge, which gives it strength and stability through customs and perspectives that have endured for centuries. Instead of being silent, this knowledge is now shared in mentoring circles, school gardens, workshops, and everyday land practices, where it is revived, reappreciated, and adapted. The system’s “leaves” are community engagement, where everyone has a role and a place through peer-led environmental monitoring, seasonal festivals, and regular participatory forums. All of this is made possible by education and awareness, the “sun”, both in formal and informal settings, such as schools, where people connect, share stories, and reinterpret nature as a living, co-creating partner. Education becomes a source of energy that fosters a sense of purpose in all individuals.

Innovation is encouraged in this system, but not just in the form of technological advancement. Instead, it is based on action, directed by town halls, youth councils, and local leaders who thoughtfully and determinedly initiate solutions rather than waiting for them from above. Knowledge, values, and imagination are mobilized collectively in the SES, creating a new civic energy. Through shared responsibility and co-creation, damaged relationships between people and nature, between generations, and between institutions and citizens will be healed in this vision, which extends beyond simple resilience.

The SES transforms into a system of possibility, solidarity, and sustainability. It is a place where people feel like they belong, where nature is preserved out of love rather than duty, and where futures are shaped collectively rather than separately. This vision is the actual, cumulative outcome of deciding to stay, work together, adapt, and develop; it is not a utopia.

Figure 5. Community traits of a healthy Social-Ecological System (SES), based on workshop reflections.

4.5.3 Discussion

As the analysis progressed, it became clear that the SES is shaped by somewhat unequal relationships between policy and practice, scientific and experiential knowledge, and among social groups. The dominance of CAP rationale and Natura 2000 bureaucratic processes has constrained the space for local agencies and marginalized key actors such as small-scale farmers, Roma communities, and elderly holders of traditional knowledge. At the same time, institutional fragmentation and symbolic participation have undermined the feedback loops on which adaptive governance relies. Governance is often reactive, externally led, and compliance-based, rather than being driven by co-learning or reciprocal accountability. And despite such constrained conditions, elements of transformation can be identified. Local actors possess rich ecological knowledge, strong affective attachments to land, and cultural practices with implicit pro-biodiversity values. The workshops revealed a shared desire for change, not through disruption but through reconnection.

A recurring theme is the discrepancy between dominant biodiversity framings and local knowledge practices. While institutional assessments rely on technical indicators, locals discuss biodiversity in terms of taste, beauty, rhythm, and intergenerational memory. Closing this knowledge gap requires more of these participatory moments; it requires a structural transformation in who decides value and how decisions are made. It requires a shift from a logic of inclusion as an invitation to that of inclusion as a foundation. The vision developed in Section 5.3.2 is not just a product of abstraction. It is grounded in values, practices, and lived contradictions expressed by local actors within the BIOTraCes workshops. It resonates with an alternative system of relations where diversity of knowledge, affective belonging to place, and collective agency are central pillars. Rather than proposing top-down solutions, the vision suggests bottom-up pathways rooted in existing practices, such as "clacă" (a traditional form of communal labor or mutual help in rural communities), community seed exchanges, or local ecotourism endeavors. Importantly, this vision neither romanticizes tradition, but seeks to revive and reimagine it via intergenerational learning, inclusive governance, and plural economies. Youth are

not passive bystanders but active actors, and marginalized voices, including Roma and women, are pulled into positions of influence and co-creation. The SES is a site not only for sustainability but for care, justice, and reimagined prosperity.

However, the vision is dependent on more than imagination. Structural barriers, such as stringent subsidy regimes, a lack of long-term funding, and extractive policy cycles, for example, must be addressed. The current system prioritizes technical compliance over relational and cultural dimensions. Without institutional flexibility and trust-building mechanisms, many of the proposals are in danger of being aspirational. From a methodological perspective, this analysis demonstrates the effectiveness of employing participatory and narrative approaches in unlocking local knowledge and reimagining futures. The BIOTraCes workshops not only mapped existing tensions, but also generated new imaginaries through dialogue, shared storytelling, and ethical reflection. These tools helped reveal the relational fractures within the SES, as well as the pathways through which they might be healed.

Sustainable transformation in high-biodiversity rural communities requires more than technical fixes. The SES of Saschiz is on the verge of transformation, but only if transformation is grounded in care, equity, and collective agency. On a more fundamental level, the SES vision also challenges prevailing assumptions about what transformation should look like. Policy and scientific interventions increasingly seek measurable outcomes, including conserved hectares, counted species, and sequestered carbon. Despite these metrics being important, they overshadow the emotional, ethical, and historical entanglements that support human-nature relationships in lived landscapes. The citizens of local communities do not view biodiversity as a checklist but rather as something interwoven with taste, memory, rhythm, and presence in everyday life. In this context, change begins not in targets but in relations.

Perhaps one of the most valuable lessons of the BIOTraCes process is that trust is essential. Trust among institutions and individuals, trust across generations, and trust between communities themselves. To rebuild that trust (undermined by top-down policies, loss of control, and social dissolution), there must be a regular presence, transparent processes, and a desire to listen and learn together. The eagerness of the participants to imagine other futures is evidence of a civic reservoir of potential energy present in the population, waiting to be tapped if only institutions will make space for it.

The workshops also revealed the importance of emotional and relational spaces. Activities like telling stories, drawing maps together, sharing meals, and working as a group weren't just methods for gathering information; they were also ways to build community. They became moments of healing. In these places, people regained voice, visibility, and care. These types of knowledge, though often intangible, are key to building longer-term resilience and co-ownership of sustainability transitions.

These reflections also point to the need for policy co-evolution. The kind of transformation described in this report cannot be achieved solely by local communities. It should also encompass the broader impact sector, including EU programs, national governments, NGOs, and donors, becoming more responsive to locally determined capacities and values. This includes embracing policy agility, co-designed funding initiatives, and measurement that incentivizes not only conformity but also relational care, cultural continuity, and co-produced knowledge.

Another critical element is the role of young people in sustaining cultural continuity. As the vision highlights, young people are not merely returning to their homes. They are remaking it. They are combining tradition and innovation, land husbandry and digital fluency, and

local rootedness and global outlook. Investment in youth participation, mentorship programs, rural innovation hubs, and place-based education would ensure that change is not only imagined but also implemented with intergenerational strength.

Finally, this SES narrative extends beyond Transylvania. It addresses more abstract questions regarding the future of rural Europe. Can we develop policy models that are sensitive to complexity, conflict, and cultural nuances? Can we reorient governance away from fragmented project thinking and toward an integrated, relationship-centered, place-based approach to change?

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4.6 Bottom-UP Forest Biodiversity, Sweden

Authors: Oscar Jacobsson (UGOT)

The study examines focusing on biodiversity dynamics among private forest owners in three Swedish parishes—Säve, Istorp, and Ambjörnarp.

Geographical and Historical Dimensions

Säve (near Gothenburg) features flat farmland and forested hills shaped by glaciation. Historically dominated by farming, deforestation peaked in the 19th century, followed by regrowth and spruce planting. Today, urban expansion pressures forests, with most residents working outside agriculture. Istorp is characterized by agricultural valleys and forested uplands, once communal grazing lands. Fires and 19th-century land reforms fragmented ownership, leading to conifer plantations. The population has declined since the 19th century, and current employment spans agriculture, construction, and services. Ambjörnarp is predominantly forested, with continuity since the 17th century. Poor soils constrained farming, fostering self-sufficient animal husbandry. Logging accelerated in the late 19th century, reducing deciduous cover. Population peaked around 1900 but later stabilized at low levels.

Key Actors and Worldviews

Swedish forestry debates pit industry (productive forestry) against conservationists (protection of old-growth forests). Private forest owners—diverse in background and rarely professional foresters—occupy a middle ground, valuing both ecology and practice. Local differences emerge: in Ambjörnarp, biodiversity is tied to forestry practices; in Istorp, to species variation and protection; and in Säve, to informed reasoning. Companies like Sveaskog, Derome, and Skanska integrate biodiversity unevenly, while associations such as Södra promote certification and voluntary conservation. Government actors (Swedish Forest Agency, Environmental Protection Agency, County Boards) enforce legislation and monitor biodiversity, with municipalities playing varying roles—minimal in Istorp/Ambjörnarp but significant in urbanizing Säve. Non-human “actants” such as capercaillie, trees, soils, and topography also shape forest use and conservation debates.

Drivers of Biodiversity Loss

Key direct drivers include: reforestation (conversion of heathlands and open landscapes to conifers); even-aged silviculture (clear-cutting and monocultures, replacing diverse forest structures); and urban expansion (notably in Säve, where housing and logistics displace forests). Indirect drivers stem from industrialization, urbanization, and reinforcement of production forestry.

Cultural and Identity Dynamics

Forest owners emphasize relational values (recreation, heritage, stewardship) over economic returns. Conflicts arise with authorities and industry over management and aesthetics. Gender dynamics show women’s growing yet marginalized role, with networks like *Dryaderna* providing support. Age influences stewardship, especially succession planning.

Political/Institutional Dynamics

Swedish forestry is locked into even-aged silviculture due to long-standing policies, industrial interests, and infrastructure. This entrenched model shapes both national forestry culture and Sweden’s role in European policy, creating barriers to biodiversity-friendly alternatives.

4.6.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

Our case study departs from a landscape geographical analysis of SES, where a given landscape is seen as the local result of coalescing processes and entities over space and time (Stenseke, 2018). An important difference between a landscape approach and SES is that landscape focuses on physical proximity, local variation and local contexts in which a unique combination of social and ecological processes are at work (Stenseke et al., 2012). In this context, we approach our different case study areas as local landscape arenas with differing activities and processes occupying the same space and producing local complexities which are also dependent on intricate relationships across scales (Stenseke, 2023).

4.6.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

The different actors described under section 3.2 are all part of shaping and being shaped by the landscape with which they interact. On a conceptual level, the landscape is not an entity separate from the actors but can instead be considered the sum of divergent actors and processes, a sum which also has consequences for the effects and conditions of wider decision-making. In this section, we therefore focus first on describing how the key actors from 3.2 are impacted by the *physical* landscape and the organization of its practical use.

The different actor groups – private forest owners, forest-owner associations (Södra skogsägarna), companies, state agencies, NGOs and nonhuman actants – are all intimately part of the historically developed landscape in which their actions play out, which is also constrained by institutional, economic and material path-dependencies connected to policies, markets, infrastructure and the physical development of the forest and the surrounding landscape over time.

Forest owners depend directly on the physical conditions for forestry on their properties (e.g. topography, soils and forestry legacies) and are generally also restricted by industrial market logics, certification systems, forest legislations as well as local knowledge networks and norms. In Säve, since few forest owners are conducting active forestry or are members of Södra, they are less bound to these restrictions, but their capacity to use the forest actively (also for alternative purposes) is constrained by less knowledge (e.g. due to being new and inexperienced forest owners) as well as the physical topography with steep slopes making modern forest machinery less usable.

Companies such as Sveaskog and Derome depend on the local forest landscapes for raw material for the forest industry and are also dependent on following established environmental principles and regulations. The current challenges that companies face in doing so under rising forest yield challenges and environmental concerns is marked by the tension between major forest owning companies such as SCA and the certification organization FSC.

Forest-owner associations are driven by the interests of their members and to pursue profits with the use of their industries, for which the resources come from the forests owned by their members. They are thus dependent on regular outtakes of forest, and in turn the physical conditions for doing so plays an important role in this.

NGOs like the Swedish Society for Nature Conservation (SSNC) are generally monitoring the interactions between logging and ecological conditions, but in our case they do not have a large local presence in our case study areas, at least not as expressed in either interviews or workshops.

Government agencies like the Swedish Forest Agency (SFA) or the County Administrative Board (CAB) regional are primarily locally encountered either through the enforcement of environmental regulations (e.g. for biodiversity) or in the case of SFA through communication and advisory services. While the conditions of local landscapes play a part of larger regional or national landscapes or sectors that these agencies are obliged to handle, it is highly likely that they seldom encounter our specific case study areas in their daily work.

Municipalities play only a limited role in Istorp and Ambjörnarp but is a major actor in SÄve where Gothenburg Municipality owns large amounts agricultural land and forests. The municipality is affected by the conditions of the landscape for future development purposes, where some land (such as forest) is more easily motivated for development while other land has a larger protection status. In SÄve, and in a wider sense the entire island of Hisingen, the municipality also balances residential and industrial development on arable and forested land, since the city needs new residential areas for a growing population but also to cater to industrial interests also in connected to the nationally important harbor of Gothenburg.

Non-human actants, such as animals, birds, vegetation are directly impacted by the physical conditions of the local landscape and its connected management, since they are dependent on that landscape for direct survival. The moose is a good example of this, which was brought up in several interviews with forest owners. Many of them perceive that the moose are threatened in their areas due to overhunting being incentivized by the CAB. The CAB is in turn affected by industrial forest interests, primarily from the north of Sweden where moose is perceived as a threat to new pine plantations due to browsing.

4.6.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

Formally, direct decision-making capacity is in the hands of the forest owners, both private, corporate or other types of organizations (such as the Swedish church). Especially since the new forest law in 1993, under the parole of "freedom with responsibility", the forest owners have a large degree of freedom in choice of management and directions with their forestry, as long as they adhere to current environmental considerations (regarding biodiversity, cultural heritage, water and soil) and ensure long term sustainable forest yields through replantation. In practice, however, the decision-making capacities of private forest owners are constrained by economic structures, advisory systems, knowledge access and market demands (see section 4.2 on exclusionary mechanisms). In practice, many practical decisions about forest land use are delegated to a large degree to forest consultants who are also connected to industrial actors and to the certification system. Most of the forest owners we have interacted with primarily own forests as a supplementary activity and income, which means that their everyday interests are largely connected to other questions. Larger actors, both companies, forest owner associations and certification organizations thus have a large power over what occurs in practice in privately owned forests. The Swedish state, both the government and government agencies, to certain degree holds *less* power over the state of the forest than these large forestry actors, since legislations which also steers the supervision of forestry serves mostly reactive purposes. Just as the forest legislation from 1993 was a reaction to increased environmental awareness in combination with a general neoliberal political call for deregulation (Enander, 2007), the ongoing reworking of the legislation by the current government has been accused of primarily reacting to calls from the forest industry for decreased regulation and control (Westholm, 2024: 58-62).

4.6.1.3 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

Official and more overarching governance processes are primarily informed by formal and science-based definitions of biodiversity and wider forest policies through EU directives, certification systems and national legislations. This was revealed in the case study when interviewed forest owners were asked about their perception of biodiversity, which to a large extent was seen as a policy and media-related concept rather than something tangible. Forest owners instead rely on other types of knowledge related to their own experiences, their relation to the forest property, emotional/aesthetic aspects and practical dimensions of land use. This generates a certain friction when official implementations of environmental policies conflict with forest owner perception of the values (including biodiversity) on their forest properties, where the owner may question the local relevance and applicability of the policy, or its implementation.

Furthermore, the general impression is that policy rarely interacts with the wider group of forest owners in a participatory manner, but rather with representation limited to forest owner associations with industrial ties, which are also regional actors with regional types of knowledge. While these associations have a high degree of professional knowledge concerning the productive and environmental values of the forests of their members, more locally oriented knowledges tend to be obscured in the wider forest governance system, for practical reasons.

4.6.1.4 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

The forests of our three case study areas are situated in the northern temperate forest zone. Temperate forest ecosystems are shaped by the interplay of soil processes, disturbance, species interactions, and animal influences. Nutrients cycle through decaying litter and dead wood, with climate and tree species affecting decomposition. Disturbances – from storms to fire – create varied successional paths, while treefall gaps sustain diversity by enabling regeneration. Plants adapt to shade through seasonal strategies or root associations, and animals – from squirrels to deer and insects – disperse seeds, pollinate, graze, or defoliate, influencing forest structure and composition over time (Frelich et al., 2015). In this context, and especially in Sweden, forestry is often considered as a type of disturbance.

Disturbances come in many different forms and frequencies. Certain forest ecosystems generate rather stable local environments due to the interaction between different processes creating a multi-layered forests. Larger disturbances such as forest fires or massive storms may however eradicate such landscapes in a short time-span, and often occur with some frequency when looking at a forest landscape across centuries (Angelstam & Holmer, 1997). Forests of various kinds in a “natural state” has certain patterns of disturbances over time, and the specific variation of forests within a given landscape or region thus means a certain pattern of disturbances. The human use of a forest over time strongly contributes to these patterns and affects the forest in similar ways.

The direct drivers of biodiversity loss in the case study varies between the studied areas. In Sävle the processes of reforestation and urbanization are the most dominant causes of biodiversity loss, while even-aged silviculture is more dominant in Ambjörnarp and Istorp. Urbanization is not a direct driver of biodiversity loss in these study areas, while reforestation in Istorp is also a driver. These drivers are described more fully under section 3.3, including their underlying causes.

4.6.1.5 Values underpinning decision-making processes

Policymaking in Swedish forestry is primarily guided by instrumental and intrinsic/ecological values, where the current Swedish forest legislation to a certain extent aims to balance wood production with environmental values through acknowledging both values as important. While these values are still very much active in policymaking, it is also clear that future policies will need to account for the undesired effects of granting considerable decision-making freedom to forest owners, both private, state and commercial actors. This is not the least marked by the fact that both the forest industry and environmental NGOs are dissatisfied with the current situation.

Forest owners, on the other hand, are more often guided by relational values such as emotional attachment to land, feelings of stewardship toward past and future generations, aesthetic preferences and recreational aspects. These values are especially prominent among owners with multigenerational ties to their properties or who live near their forests. While policymaking, especially when related to instrumental values of forests, tend to be focused on short-term gains, the relational values that forest owners hold encourage long-term thinking, more sensitivity to local conditions and in some cases an opposition to externally imposed obligations and management practices. While many forest owners also recognize the instrumental values of their land, such values are rather often framed as supporting a supplementary income where the forest only plays a minor role in their household economy. However, economic pressures and market incentives still influence management choices, especially when infrastructure, advisory services, and buyer systems are geared toward conventional forestry.

4.6.1.6 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

Governance of the local SES can be divided into multiple levels. The forest owners are the ones who formally holds much of the governing capacity over the forest, through the Swedish forest model focused on 'freedom under responsibility'. Power over the forest is largely manifested by those actors whose knowledge, values and narratives have materialized in concrete forest practices. This means that power is overall concentrated to control over or have large access to the systems by which forestry is actually carried out: advisory services, market structures, machinery, certification and policy implementation.

For example, even though forest owners often possess detailed knowledge about their land, they still rely to a large degree on knowledge produced and communicated through the forestry advisory system, especially with forest owners in Istorp and Ambjörnarp who are more inclined to actively use their forests for timber production. Advisory knowledge (e.g. through Södra or Derome) by necessity reflects standardized forestry systems with a focus on timber production and forest growth metrics. Forest owners who attempt alternative approaches often find it difficult to access to reliable guidance or material support, which limits the practical influence of non-dominant knowledge forms. In Säve, specific knowledge about forest management is not as well developed, which is related both to the practical difficulties of conducting conventional forestry in the area, as well as the higher turnover of properties in the area. On the one hand, the lack of knowledge and practical engagement with forestry limits the potential for an increased alternative use of the forest, and on the other the practical difficulties in the area limits the interest from the forest industry.

Values connected to care, continuity and biodiversity are commonly expressed among forest owners, regardless of their management style. In most cases, owners view their current practices as already aligned with these values, likely based in familiarity with the land, historical use and local norms. Management decisions are not only shaped by

individual convictions and advisory knowledge but also by the surrounding management of the forest landscape and practices of neighboring landowners. A smaller group of owners express a desire to shift towards alternative approaches, such as continuous-cover forestry, based on personal values or ecological concerns. However, these intentions rarely translate into broader change, partly due to uncertainty around practical implementation, economic outcomes, and conflicting information in public debates.

The overarching narrative around biodiversity among private forest owners is shaped by political and institutional frameworks that emphasize individual responsibility and continuity with existing practices. Since 1993, biodiversity has been treated as one consideration among others, to be balanced within the prevailing model of production forestry. Institutional actors have largely supported this framing by promoting biodiversity measures that fit within conventional management, which reinforces the view that major changes are neither necessary nor expected.

4.6.1.7 Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector

The overarching narrative in forestry, although challenged by environmental actors, frames biodiversity as something that can be integrated into existing production patterns and not as something that may require a different way of organising forestry. Forests are seen as resources that should be managed effectively, with biodiversity as a secondary consideration rather than as a starting point. For private forest owners, the sector's overarching narrative has primarily functioned to legitimise existing forestry practices rather than to change them. The relatively uncritical view many owners have of their own management reflects how the dominant framing of biodiversity has succeeded in presenting conventional forestry as already adequate. The narrative does not drive forest use directly, but helps justify a form of use that continues for other, often economic or practical, reasons. At the same time, there is a clear distinction between company-owned forests and those managed by small-scale private owners, where a wider range of values tends to result in more diverse and more environmentally varied practices.

4.6.1.8 Economic structures' impact over the SES

In **Ambjörnarp** and **Istorp**, forestry remains a secondary income source for most owners, but decisions are still strongly shaped by how markets, technologies, knowledge systems, and regulations have developed in close alignment with the forest industry. Owners who express interest in alternative methods – such as high-quality timber production or more selective harvesting – face structural barriers, including a lack of established markets, limited infrastructure, and uncertainty around long-term returns. While there is demand for certain niche products, such as timber for historic building restoration, the broader system offers little support for such production.

In **Säve**, the situation is different. Forestry products have little or no role in the local economy, apart from firewood or occasional timber used for private construction. Instead, land value and real estate dynamics dominate. Proximity to Gothenburg has made property value – and not forest production – the primary economic factor in owning forest properties. Several interviewed owners describe parceling land for housing or engaging in speculative ownership as central components in the areas land use. The workshop in Säve reinforced this picture, with much of the discussion focusing on development pressure. Further to the south, with areas of national infrastructure linked to Göteborgs Hamn – which handles around 20% of Sweden's foreign trade – logistics development and industrial expansion increasingly compete with ecological and cultural values, often to the detriment of the latter.

Across all areas, the structure of the economy, what is profitable, what is logistically possible, and what is institutionally supported, has a clear influence on how the forest is used, even when not directly central to household income. The regional stakeholder workshop further emphasised this point, since both markets and infrastructures for alternative economic incomes from the forest on a general level are largely missing, which strongly constrains the viable options for the forest owner (Stakeholder workshop, Gothenburg, August 2025).

4.6.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

In the broader forest sector, biodiversity is assessed using a combination of regulatory frameworks, certification systems, and internal monitoring by major forestry companies. The Swedish Forest Agency evaluates ecological values in connection with harvest notifications and maintains a national register of key habitats, though systematic inventories have largely been paused. County Administrative Boards use such data for regional planning and oversight but do not conduct field-based monitoring themselves.

Certification schemes such as FSC and PEFC structure biodiversity assessments through checklists and audit routines. FSC applies more detailed criteria and, in some cases, supports scientific monitoring, while PEFC relies on broader sustainability standards. Large forest companies like SCA, Holmen and Södra track biodiversity using selected indicators, such as volumes of deadwood, the presence of old or broadleaved trees, and mapped conservation areas. These indicators are followed over time and reported to demonstrate ecological responsibility.

4.6.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

The main constraint to transformative innovation is the relatively passive role that forest owners assume over decision-making on their own forest properties, primarily due to a lack of alternative knowledge and access to practical alternatives. Conventional forestry relies on industry advisors, access to large machinery and, especially under current circumstances due to high wood prices caused by the war in Ukraine among other things, such forestry provides a reliable if supplementary type of income to the forest owner without any requirement for practical engagement or knowledge in forestry. The independent decisions that most forest owners make are limited geographically and often align with or do not contradict conventional forest management. In Säve, where little forestry is practiced, a further constraint is the topography itself with steep slopes and shallow soils on the hills which are more or less unfit for conventional forestry. In turn, there is a lack of knowledge or interest in using the forest beyond recreational purposes and the collection of firewood. The proximity to Gothenburg, with pressure on properties for development and high property prices, means that the forest is systematically undervalued as a land use in economic terms.

When it comes to the enablers or opportunities for transformative change the relational values that forest owners rely on seem to be the aspect with the largest potential, combined with the fact that forestry does not constitute an important income for these owners. These values often do not align with economic or industrial values, although the aspect of stewardship or heritage often include path-dependencies to conventional forest management, since traditional clear-cut forestry has been the predominant model in Sweden since the early 20th century. There is considerable potential to mobilise forest owners for alternative practices, if those practices can be shown to align more closely with relational values and are economically viable and practical options also for forest owners with little to no interest in doing forestry work themselves. In turn, this relies largely on

building alternative infrastructure, value-chains, knowledge-sharing networks and pockets of local organization for alternative practices. The case study has shown small embryos of such processes, particularly in Istorp, and there are larger ongoing developments towards this from the advisory side as well, for example through the network Plockhugget.

4.6.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

This alternative vision for the SES is formulated through our workshops and interviews, with the specific aim to detail how different types of forest owners with different needs, wishes and uses of the forest could potentially coexist and collaborate in a system which promotes biodiversity more fully and efficiently than today. Here, we divide the forest owners into four different categories: the passive steward, the innovative ecological manager, the production-oriented owner and the inactive peri-urban owner. The section ends with an analysis of how these different owners collaborate and interact in this alternative vision.

The Passive Steward

This forest owner do not manage their forest very actively, instead relying on advisors and conventional forestry practices through hired services from a forest owner association or a forest company. However, they still often have deep personal connections to their forests: walking, hunting, berry and mushroom picking, heritage etc. These forest owners want their forest to remain an accessible and recreational environment for future generations, and also provide a small income with minimal effort. In the alternative SES, this owner has access to simple and tailored management options – such as selective thinning or conservation agreements – that allow biodiversity to increase without requiring high activity or incurs larger risks. They are supported by clear, long-term policy frameworks that allow a trustworthy delegation of forestry decisions.

The Innovate Ecological Manager

This owner is deeply engaged with their forest. They prefer continuous cover forestry, selective harvesting and allowing diversity in tree species and age. They use the forest for high-quality timber, fuelwood and materials for on-farm use or building restoration. These forest owners collaborate with neighbors, test alternative methods and sometimes organize shared machine use or other collaborative initiatives. In the alternative SES, their creative practices are more fully supported. They can access grants for ecological restoration or innovations and have their own networks to promote peer learning. Their forests become inspirational sites for other forest owners.

The Production-Oriented Owner

This owner relies on forestry as a key part of their livelihood, practicing clearcutting and replanting according to industry standards, optimizing for yields and timber/wood markets. In the alternative SES, their role still remains vital but the system incentivizes transitions towards long-rotation forestry, mixed-species stands and climate-resistant strategies. Certification schemes value both production and biodiversity and are more fully adapted to allow for a diversity of set asides geographically. New markets for ecosystem services, biocredits and high-quality timber support profitability while allowing for a higher diversity of economically viable practices which supports biodiversity in the forest. These owners thus remain largely competitive in this alternative SES.

The Inactive Peri-Urban Owner

This forest owner has typically bought a property, often for horse keeping, consisting of an older farm with both arable land and forest. By this owner, the forest may be viewed as land that simply exists without any need for maintenance, as a future development potential (often for housing) or that is used for recreational purposes. In the alternative SES, these owners are offered low-threshold alternatives to make use of their forests, for example through long-term leasing schemes where others manage the forest for biodiversity or cultural values. They may eventually choose to participate or invest in further development of biodiversity, for example through landscape restoration grants.

Summary

In this alternative vision of the SES, the diversity of ownership types is seen as an essential foundation for diversity in the forest and builds on structures and arguments already put forward in the contemporary debate. Each type of forest owner contributes in different ways: some by stewarding, others by production of renewable materials and others by simply allowing nature to develop on its own. The system is supported by reliable institutions that value multiple goals in the forest, offer different type of support depending on local and individual contexts and facilitate diverse arenas of knowledge exchange.

Increased biodiversity emerges not primarily by formal regulations, but through collaboration between individuals, organizations and public authorities. Passive stewards conserve biodiversity structures and continuity, innovative managers refine it, production owners contribute to societal resource needs and inactive owners may offer spaces for experimentation or preservation. Policies, advisory systems and markets allow and incentivize a diverse range of practices and a move away from conformity.

4.6.3 Discussion

Our case study, departing from a landscape approach and emphasizing the interaction between human intention, relational processes, material practices and the conditions of the physical (socionatural) landscape, illustrates how private forestry does not occur in non-occupied space but in a wider landscape arena shaped by the coalescence of social and ecological processes over space and time. Such a coalescence means a problematizing of decision-making as an entirely contemporary practice, since choice of forest management today is often the result of historically and spatially conditioned possibilities constrained by available infrastructure, markets, knowledge practices and earlier decisions. The landscape is not primarily there to be governed but is part and parcel of the governing conditions themselves.

Furthermore, our case study shows that while forest owners in Sweden have a large formal freedom in decision-making, their decision-making capacity is varied and circumscribed by access to material recourses such as access to machinery, household economy and the physical conditions of the forest, in combination with practical access to advisory services of different kinds and directions. It is not only primarily the intention of the forest owner that decides action and behavior, but rather how such intentions interact with access to material, infrastructural and knowledge-wise resources. Power in this case should thus be understood as both the practical ability to shape material outcomes in the landscape as well as influence over decision-making.

Another important result is that the access to alternative practices in private forestry is largely constrained by the reproductive processes of the current Swedish forest industry. Knowledge, infrastructure and material practices that are easily available to most private

forest owners, along with the politics and institutions that regulate forestry, are mostly conditioned to serve the functions of the forest industry and in turn the economically important function of this sector for Sweden as a whole. This includes current certification schemes, such as FSC, which complement conventional forestry rather than challenging the status quo. Alternative forestry knowledge exists, which on paper is more and more promoted also by state agencies under certain international and environmental pressure, but a public infrastructure where this knowledge materializes into action through implemented directives is largely missing.

To a certain extent, our case study complements earlier research by putting larger emphasis on the importance of material practices and constraints. For example, Tiebel et. al (2024), through using the IPBES framework of transformative change and an approach informed by the leverage point framework by Abson et. al (2017), have identified several key leverage points for transformative change for biodiversity among private forest owners in north-west Germany. According to these authors, the leverage points with largest potential for transformative change lie in the intent (values, norms and goals) and design (institutional structure, power and information flows) domains. The most influential leverage point is considered under the domain of intent, since “[c]onservation action requires forest owners to recognize the importance of biodiversity conservation as well as to act accordingly (Tiebel et al., 2024: 348).”

While we agree that the relational values that many forest owners hold has a certain transformative potential, we also argue that the main barriers to transformative change for biodiversity among private forest owners in Sweden is not cognitive but structural. The possibility for transformative change is not accelerated through more knowledge or improved personal values, but through building an infrastructure and formal material support for alternative practices in privately owned forests. As shown by this case study, there is some potential to build and locally accelerate such a process through bottom-up initiatives which practically engage forest owners in alternative forestry by local collaboration. Considering the pressure on achieving national and international environmental commitments, it is also likely that this must eventually be met by more formal official practical support on a national level.

Understanding the Landscape through the Eyes of the Capercaillie

Days passed. I remained in the new forest. Its silence was different, alive and promising. Here the light did not blind me, but scattered gently across the ground, tracing the curve of moss and root. I had found my stage again. Not the same, never the same, but good enough.

Each morning, I tested the air. Damp with dew, rich with the scents of bark and blossom. I walked with care, wings low, feathers brushing against bramble and dead branches. The forest spoke in a language I knew: slow decay, soft growth, the rhythm of things and beings returning over the seasons.

But I also felt the edge. Not far from here, the sound of metal biting wood still echoed. I could sense it in the tension of the birds around me, the way the squirrels paused too long. There, the forest frayed, and the ground hardened. I did not go there. I stayed in the shifting places, where spruce gave way to birch, where pine stood tall over fields of bilberry. I followed the ants, the beetles, the hens. We knew the safe paths. We remembered.

Now, in the twilight hours, I return to my stump. The forest is quiet, and I rise. Wings spread, chest lifted, the bubbling call rises from me again, steady and full. I am here. I am

still here. And while no trees last forever, I hope this forest will remain ours for generations to come.

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4.7 Fluvial Eco-Partnership, Italy

The deliverable was produced through differentiated contributions within the research unit, covering overall coordination, field research, data collection, data analysis, text drafting, and final content revision.

Overall Coordination: Mara Benadusi

Main authors: Erika Garozzo, Samadhi Lipari, Domenico Pappalardo

Others contributors: Davide Arcidiacono, Mara Benadusi, Maria Olivella Rizza, Luca Ruggiero

Located in inner eastern Sicily, the Simeto River and its Valley constitute a territory of high ecological, cultural, and historical value currently facing profound socio-ecological challenges. Extending over about 4,200 km² and including the fertile Plain of Catania, the valley is shaped by a dense interaction between natural and human systems. Its riverine corridor – fragmented by dams, weirs, and extensive irrigation infrastructure – reveals how biodiversity loss interlaces with industrial agriculture, energy production, and governance fragmentation. This makes the Simeto Valley an exemplary case for studying how local actors understand and address biodiversity decline through innovative, participatory and transformative practices.

Three interdependent pressures define the crisis: (1) the fragmentation of aquatic ecosystems caused by heavy engineering, which disrupts ecological corridors and habitats; (2) the persistence of intensive monoculture farming reliant on agrochemicals and mechanisation, leading to soil depletion and pollution aggravated by drought and wildfires; (3) and the conversion of farmland into industrial-scale photovoltaic fields enabled by the collapse of citrus monoculture and declining land values. Together, these processes reveal a socio-ecological system dominated by extractive dynamics but also animated by civic mobilisation and experimentation.

The case study, grounded in Participatory Action Research, was conducted by the University of Catania in close collaboration with the Participatory Praesidium of the Simeto River Agreement a long-standing civic network uniting municipalities, communities, and associations across the basin. This partnership ensured inclusiveness, co-design, and the translation of research findings into collective action. The study engaged a diverse set of actors, such as farmers (both conventional and alternative), livestock breeders, water authorities and infrastructure managers, multinational energy companies, civil-society organisations, and local institutions. Their interactions shape the ecological and governance dynamics of the Simeto system.

Research activities developed along three interlinked strands:

1. Re-inhabiting the river through historical and ethnographic analysis of dwelling and agroecological practices.
2. Investigating irrigation governance and farmer cooperation around water infrastructures.
3. Mapping the socio-ecological and spatial impacts of industrial photovoltaic expansion through collaborative GIS.

The process fostered sustained co-learning between researchers and local actors, deepening mutual understanding of biodiversity-related challenges and enabling the co-production of actionable knowledge. Participatory outcomes – such as a permanent exhibition and a two-week territorial festival in 2025 – contributed to public debate and institutional dialogue.

Overall, the Simeto Valley case highlights how place-based alliances, civic participation, and plural knowledge systems can sustain more just, democratic, and biodiversity-oriented forms of territorial governance, aligning with BIOTraCes Theory of Transformative Change.

4.7.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

4.7.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

The Simeto Valley socio-ecological system (SES) is shaped by a dense web of human and more-than-human interactions, structured through unequal power relations, economic dependencies, and divergent socioecological imaginaries. Within this system, multiple actor groups engage in complex relations of interdependence and conflict.

Conventional farmers represent the most influential actor group in land-use terms. They cultivate cash crops—mainly citrus and wheat—on holdings ranging from a few to several tens of hectares, generally employing monoculture and relying heavily on chemical fertilisers and pesticides. Their relationship with the SES is predominantly extractive: soil fertility is treated as a resource to be exploited for productivity under the constraints of wholesale markets that dictate prices and volumes. This dependency results in overuse of agrochemicals, soil depletion, and declining fertility, aggravated by chronic water scarcity and recurrent droughts intensified by the climate crisis. Low bargaining power and predatory pricing further reinforce their reliance on public subsidies, reproducing a cycle of environmental and economic vulnerability. The reliance on pesticides leaves visible traces across the landscape, though not all of them are immediately apparent; rather, most are revealed through conversations emerging from fieldwork. One such trace is, for instance, the exposed soil visible around orange trees. This feature holds particular significance for conventional farmers: maintaining bare soil between the trees is regarded as a sign of a “clean” field. Conversely, plots where grass is allowed to grow in the absence of herbicides are considered “dirty” (Garozzo 2024, Fieldwork notes).

Figure 7. The “Ciappe Bianche” informal settlement of migrant workers in Paternò. (ph. D. Pappalardo)

In contrast, **alternative farmers and dwellers**—often small-scale producers managing plots of about two hectares—adopt practices that challenge the agro-industrial model. Few possess traditional farming backgrounds; instead, they engage in organic or agroecological agriculture, frequently uncertified, avoiding pesticides and focusing on soil regeneration, sustainable water management, and crop diversification. Their interaction with the SES is regenerative and adaptive yet constrained by the residual contamination of soils affected by decades of chemical use and by unequal access to irrigation water, which threatens the economic viability of small-scale farming as a livelihood option.

Migrant Agricultural Workers form a group that is composed mainly of young male labourers, predominantly from Maghreb countries, often employed under irregular or informal conditions. They represent a flexible and low-cost workforce that sustains both farming and livestock production across the Simeto Valley. Recruitment typically occurs through gangmasters (*caporali*), frequently of Italian or Eastern European origin, who mediate access to work and pay extremely low daily wages—sometimes under €20. Living conditions are precarious, with workers housed in temporary shelters, shanties, or abandoned vehicles near agricultural centres such as Paternò. Despite their invisibility and marginal social position, these workers occupy the frontline of the local agro-industrial system. Their relation to the Simeto socio-ecological system (SES) is marked by dependence and marginalisation. Occupying the most precarious positions in the agro-industrial chain, these workers face environmental degradation, unsafe conditions, and economic exploitation. Active mainly in citrus cultivation and seasonal harvesting, they operate within ecosystems already depleted by chemical use and soil exhaustion. Their labour sustains extractive agricultural practices—monoculture, pesticide reliance, and excessive water use—without any real decision-making power. This condition illustrates how biodiversity loss and labour exploitation are intertwined, reflecting the deep social and ecological inequalities that shape the Simeto Valley SES.

Water authorities, organised as irrigation and soil-improvement consortia, play a decisive role in managing access to and distribution of water resources. The largest, the Land Reclamation Consortium No. 9 of Catania, originated in post-war infrastructural interventions aimed at controlling the Simeto River and draining wetlands. Today, its operations are hampered by water shortages and institutional inefficiency. Smaller soil-improvement consortia, by contrast, rely on *water guardians*—local workers responsible for maintaining canals and regulating flow—whose local knowledge and hands-on maintenance make them comparatively more effective. Fieldwork conversations revealed that these water guardians act as de facto mediators between the resource and the farming community. In several informal exchanges, they described the intricate structure of relations that shapes local water distribution, emphasising that their work is not merely technical but also a form of social brokerage aimed at preventing conflicts, ensuring equitable access, and avoiding both waste and abuses. Beyond these relational skills, often described as the ability to “meet everyone needs, their role also depends on an intimate familiarity with the irrigation infrastructure, which in the smaller consortia still reflects a dense and fragmented medieval layout. This situated knowledge constitutes a second defining element of the effectiveness of these consortia and of local water governance. (Pappalardo 2025, fieldnote works).

Water infrastructure owners and managers include both public and private entities such as Enel, the Basin Authority, the Domain Authority, and the Regional Environmental Protection Agency (ARPA). Enel, which owns six hydropower plants along the river, controls most of the weirs and dams and thus acts as a de facto regulator of the water system. Public authorities, despite holding formal regulatory mandates, have struggled to

counteract the valley's ecological degradation, revealing longstanding deficiencies in governance and coordination. This fragmentation, exacerbated by an overly bureaucratised administrative system, emerged clearly during fieldwork. Following repeated drought episodes, a farmer attempting to request an extraordinary water withdrawal described the process with bitterness: "[...] *to claim a basic right, to irrigate my own land, I need authorisations from three different offices. Everyone is responsible, and no one is responsible.*" Although the regional government had formally enabled exceptional withdrawals due to severe climatic conditions, the authorisation pathway had effectively become an obstacle course, shaped by overlapping requests, cross-vetoes, and conflicting mandates among the various authorities involved in river and water infrastructure management (Pappalardo 2024, fieldnote works). The configuration of the socio-ecological system (SES) reinforces these imbalances: hydropower operations, river fragmentation, and institutional compartmentalisation shape actors' capacities and priorities, limiting their ability to pursue integrated water management or biodiversity restoration, even where political or administrative willingness exists.

Photovoltaic energy companies and investors. This group includes all companies investing in the various segments of the photovoltaic energy value chain. Specifically, these actors comprise energy utilities, plant developers, and operation and maintenance companies. The socio-ecological system (SES) affects them primarily as the source of solar radiation to be converted into an energy commodity for sale and profit. Yet, on closer examination, these actors are also influenced by the chronic crisis of the local agricultural sector, which has made extensive farmland available at low cost for the development of industrial-scale photovoltaic plants.

Municipalities in the Simeto Valley are deeply affected by the territory's socio-ecological system, which continuously shapes their capacities and priorities. Environmental degradation, water scarcity, agricultural crisis and long-term budget cuts limit administrative action, forcing local governments to operate within conditions of ecological and economic vulnerability. At the same time, civic mobilisation and participatory experiments—such as the societal partner Participatory Presidio and the Simeto River Agreement—challenge municipalities to reorient their governance practices. The pressures and opportunities arising from this complex system compel local administrations to move toward participatory and biodiversity-conscious approaches that recognise ecological interdependence as a foundation for territorial well-being.

Finally, **civil society organisations**—diverse in scale and scope but united by an ethic of territorial stewardship—mobilise in response to the valley's degradation and its conversion into a sacrifice zone for extractive activities. The SES impacts these organisations in two ways: first, as the source of the ecological problems that legitimise their action, and second, as a space where they confront institutional inertia, illicit practices, and competing values that often render them marginal within the formal governance landscape.

4.7.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

The decision-making process over the Simeto Valley's socio-ecological system (SES) is mainly shaped by conventional farmers, water infrastructure owners and managers, photovoltaic companies and investors, and local institutions. These actors either make or enable key decisions on land use. Conventional farmers and, more recently, photovoltaic energy companies and investors determine the use and cover of extensive areas of land. As those who own or lease most of the Valley's productive terrain—whether for cultivation or for the installation of photovoltaic plants—these actors directly shape socio-ecological

relations, influencing which human and more-than-human communities can inhabit and prosper in specific parts of the Valley. Water infrastructure owners and managers decide on the management and distribution of irrigation water, a resource that sustains agriculture. Local institutions also act as decision enablers, particularly for energy companies investing in photovoltaic infrastructures, since they preside over authorisation and permitting procedures for new plants.

4.7.1.3 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

The types of knowledge related to the biodiversity challenges in the Simeto Valley can be grouped into two broad categories. On one side are profit-oriented knowledge systems, grounded in a capitalist rationale that views the territory and its ecosystems as resources to be exploited for profit. Within this logic, socio-ecological relations are monetised and translated into assets or liabilities in relation to investment opportunities. Biodiversity protection is not a central concern; it becomes relevant only when mandated by law or regulation. Agroindustry and industrial-scale photovoltaic energy exemplify fields of action shaped by such knowledge types.

On the other side are relational and non-extractive knowledge systems, based on coexistence with the territory and its ecosystems rather than their exploitation. Although these practices also involve agricultural and energy production, they do not prioritise profit-making as their primary rationale. Instead, they are grounded in collective dwelling—communities living among other communities, human and non-human alike. Because they do not rely on commodification or capitalisation of nature, these forms of knowledge are better positioned to legitimise and sustain biodiversity conservation. They are embodied in alternative agriculture initiatives inspired by permaculture, and in community-based renewable energy projects.

It should be noted, however, that these two categories represent ideal types that often coexist and overlap in practice. This is especially true for the second category, where biodiversity-oriented rationalities may coexist with limited, though not insignificant, profit-seeking tendencies. This tension is particularly pronounced in the case of farmers engaged in regenerative agriculture. Although many of them maintain parallel professional careers, they generally regard their relationship with the land and the possibility of growing their own food as both a politically “revolutionary” practice (Garozzo, interview with Giovanni, pseudonym, 27.11.2024) and an economic horizon to be pursued with considerable effort in the hope of eventually achieving an ideal of economic autonomy and full self-sufficiency (Lipari 2024, fieldwork notes).

4.7.1.4 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

The biodiversity of the Simeto Valley is critically compromised by a combination of interconnected factors. The main drivers include mismanagement of hydraulic infrastructures and flood-control systems, intensive citrus monoculture dependent on pesticides and agrochemicals, the uncontrolled expansion of agro-photovoltaic plants, and weak environmental planning. Together, these pressures have produced desertification, fragmentation, pollution, and the progressive degradation of agro-ecosystems.

Large-scale agriculture, excessive use of fertilisers, urban runoff, and inadequate waste treatment have altered river flows and degraded water quality. Waste mismanagement remains a major issue: scattered dumping, illegal burial, and open burning of domestic and industrial waste create “fire lands,” contaminating soils and groundwater. These practices reflect a broader structural disconnection between urban and rural areas.

The replacement of the historically diversified “Sicilian Garden” model with monoculture has eroded biodiversity, reduced soil resilience, and homogenised citrus landscapes. Recurrent droughts and structural agricultural crises prompt farmers to lease or sell their land to photovoltaic corporations, resulting in “silicon monocultures” with high ecological and social costs. It is worth noticing that there is a widespread perception amongst inhabitants of the Simeto Valley that it is the worsening of ecosystem health, including a reduction in biodiversity, that paved the way to investment in large-scale photovoltaic plants by rendering agriculture increasingly unviable as a business. This, in fact, casts large scale photovoltaic plants as an effect of biodiversity rather than as a cause.

Water resources are further stressed by dam mismanagement, unauthorised withdrawals for citrus irrigation, and illegal wastewater discharges, all of which diminish flows essential to aquatic and migratory species. Land abandonment increases wildfire and desertification risks, while urban expansion and limited public access further entrench the cultural and ecological marginalisation of the Simeto River.

4.7.1.5 Values underpinning decision-making processes

In the context of the Simeto River Valley, policy and decision-making processes are deeply shaped by a plural and often conflicting value system, reflecting enduring tensions between extractive development models and emerging paradigms of socio-ecological sustainability. At the core of dominant policy orientations lies a narrative resonating with colonial discourses, portraying marginal areas such as the Simeto Valley as “empty spaces”—abandoned, underdeveloped, and in need of modernisation. This framing legitimises external intervention, often justified in the name of efficiency and progress, while reinforcing perceptions of local communities as incapable, backward, or corrupt.

Such narratives have historically supported instrumental and utilitarian values that prioritise agricultural modernisation, resource commodification, and infrastructural expansion (Kaika 2006). Major interventions—such as river canalisation, large-scale hydraulic works, and the diffusion of intensive citrus monocultures—have been implemented through centralised, top-down policies overlooking the ecological complexity and cultural richness of the territory. More recently, the spread of large photovoltaic plants follows the same logic: the land is viewed as marginal and underused, and therefore open to exploitation in the name of ecological transition, while continuing to reflect an extractive and technocratic approach to land use.

These dynamics have contributed to long-term socio-ecological degradation and have further alienated communities from their territories. In response, over the past two decades, new actors—ecologically conscious farmers, civic organisations, university-based initiatives, and returning or new rural residents—have mobilised to promote an alternative value framework grounded in relational, regenerative, and intrinsic principles. Within this perspective, biodiversity is not merely a resource but a vital component of identity, memory, and local resilience.

Initiatives such as the Simeto River Agreement and the community-based Ecomuseum embody these shifting values, seeking to institutionalise participatory and place-based forms of governance. Yet, despite their growing legitimacy, these alternative regimes continue to face resistance from dominant institutions. Governance remains conditioned by institutional inertia, power asymmetries, and weak mechanisms for value integration. Nevertheless, these contested arenas sustain the coexistence and potential co-evolution of more inclusive, biodiversity-oriented governance models rooted in local knowledge and ethics of care.

4.7.1.6 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

Political, cultural, and institutional power dynamics in the Simeto Valley case study play a decisive role in shaping what is recognised as legitimate knowledge, which values are privileged, and how governance narratives are constructed. Historically rooted in centralised, top-down policy traditions, local governance has been dominated by technocratic logics and a developmentalist imaginary. These frameworks prioritise technical and scientific expertise—particularly in hydraulic engineering, land-use regulation, and agricultural modernisation—while systematically excluding or devaluing situated forms of knowledge such as local ecological practices, cultural memory, and affective relations with place.

This asymmetry of knowledge mirrors a wider power structure in which efficiency, infrastructural expansion, and resource optimisation are presented as primary solutions to ecological and economic challenges. The longstanding valorisation of river canalisation and water control exemplifies this logic, symbolising progress through the transformation of a historically marginal rural economy. More recently, the proliferation of large-scale photovoltaic installations on agricultural land has reinforced an extractive and technocentric model of land use—promoted as green innovation yet often disconnected from local needs and ecosystems. These projects reproduce post-colonial narratives that frame the Valley as a “void space”—a marginal, underutilised, and even corrupt territory—thereby legitimising external interventions and further disempowering local actors. Interviews revealed that the nimbyism trope is widely used by investors to counteract opposition or resistance to new photovoltaic plants. In a crucial interview, a local activist explained how the narrative that “opposition [to plants] only defends particularistic interests while harming collective interest in that plants would allegedly boost local development in what is an underdeveloped area” works actually as a rhetorical device delegitimising opponents by alleging their political shortsightedness, while hiding the fact that there no unique way to local development (interview with Savatore, local activist, 10/01/2025).

Against this backdrop, grassroots initiatives such as the Simeto Ecomuseum and the Contratto di Fiume have emerged as counter-hegemonic efforts to reconfigure territorial governance. These initiatives aim to pluralise environmental decision-making by foregrounding alternative value systems grounded in care, reciprocity, and territorial stewardship. They foster collective learning and knowledge co-production despite structural vulnerabilities, including scarce institutional support and limited formal recognition.

Ultimately, navigating the governance of the Simeto SES requires confronting entrenched power asymmetries and epistemic hierarchies. Although dominant narratives remain resilient, new coalitions of farmers, civic actors, and engaged researchers are gradually opening spaces for more inclusive, place-based, and biodiversity-oriented governance practices.

4.7.1.7 Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector

In the context of the Simeto Valley, the institutions —conceived as the constellation of norms, rules, bureaucratic procedures, and dominant narratives—play an ambivalent yet decisive role in shaping the governance of the local socio-ecological system (SES). On the one hand, global and European commitments to biodiversity protection have introduced frameworks such as the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, intended to harmonise environmental priorities across scales and redirect local governance toward more

sustainable and inclusive models. On the other hand, their practical impact remains limited due to the structural weaknesses of local institutions.

Local administrations are characterised by insufficient technical capacity, chronic underfunding, and a lack of strategic vision. These limitations impede their ability to interpret and implement complex supranational agendas, resulting in fragmented policies, implementation delays, and formal rather than substantive adherence to biodiversity objectives. Administrative cultures remain anchored in technocratic and growth-oriented approaches that leave little room for integrated, adaptive, or participatory forms of governance.

This institutional inertia is reinforced by political and cultural factors, including the persistent undervaluation of biodiversity as a collective and relational good. Dominant narratives continue to portray rural and marginal areas such as the Simeto Valley as empty, backward, or underutilised territories—thus legitimising top-down interventions, from large-scale infrastructure projects to industrial photovoltaic installations. Framed as efficient uses of abandoned land, these interventions reproduce extractive logics that neglect local ecological knowledge, social practices, and cultural attachments.

Against this backdrop, grassroots initiatives such as the Simeto Ecomuseum and the River Contract seek to counterbalance institutional shortcomings by fostering collective learning, co-production of knowledge, and place-based environmental governance. Yet their transformative potential remains constrained by weak institutional support and the absence of mechanisms for value integration and democratic accountability. Bridging this gap requires a paradigmatic shift in how institutions conceptualise and implement biodiversity governance—moving beyond compliance-based models toward participatory, relational, and multi-scalar frameworks capable of embedding biodiversity within territorial decision-making.

4.7.1.8 Economic structures' impact over the SES

In the Simeto Valley case study, economic structures play a decisive role in shaping the local socio-ecological system (SES), profoundly influencing land-use patterns, knowledge systems, and the distribution of power and value. The valley is increasingly defined as a production landscape, where economic activities are subordinated to the imperatives of capital accumulation and large-scale market logics. Two dominant and extractive trends—agro-industrial monocultures and industrial-scale photovoltaic development—are emblematic of this dynamic.

In agriculture, most farmers remain structurally bound to global value chains and large-scale distribution systems. Their production is geared towards standardised, low-priced goods, a model that erodes local autonomy and resilience. In this context, the act of purchasing—largely controlled by retail monopolies—becomes the mechanism through which markets suppress small-scale and diversified production. Fieldwork conversations further revealed how this dynamic operates through the system of intermediaries (*mediatori*) who negotiate between farmers and large distributors. According to several farmers, these intermediaries act with no ethical concern and consistently align with the interests of major retail groups. Their practices not only depress farmgate prices but also contribute to creating the conditions for the failure of small and medium-sized agricultural enterprises, enabling the subsequent acquisition of their land and the gradual reconstruction of new forms of latifundia. (Pappalardo 2025, fieldnote work). The weakening of traditional markets and the marginalisation of alternative circuits, such as direct sales or community-supported agriculture, make it increasingly difficult for new farmers and valley residents engaged in regenerative practices to succeed.

A growing concentration of land ownership further amplifies these inequalities. A “new latifundium” has re-emerged, with a few large landowners controlling hundreds of hectares and dominating local agricultural economies. Their influence extends beyond production, shaping policy priorities, public discourse, and the perception of land as an extractive resource. Fieldwork confirmed how these dynamics unfold across multiple scales. In one interview, a young farmer, who himself manages more than ten hectares, described feeling like a *small farmer* despite his relatively large extension of land. To survive in an increasingly hostile market, he explained, he had been compelled to expand his holdings by gradually acquiring plots from even smaller farmers, those cultivating less than three hectares. This incremental accumulation, he noted, is replicated at higher scales: medium-sized farmers absorb smaller ones, and large landowners then absorb them in turn. The result is a progressive reduction in the number of independent landholders, many of whom either abandon agriculture altogether or become employees of the very companies that purchase their land, perceiving salaried work as more stable than family-based farming. (Pappalardo 2025, fieldnote work). This concentration increases the vulnerability of smallholders, particularly those engaged in citrus monoculture or experimenting with innovative, place-based farming models. Similar mechanisms underpin the expansion of industrial photovoltaics, where financial and energy capital occupy agricultural land in the name of the green transition. Both agro-industrial and photovoltaic systems are reshaping the valley into a site of intensified value extraction, eroding ecological knowledge, local ties, and cultural values. Niche actors such as the Simeto Ecomuseum attempt to counter these dynamics, yet dominant market structures continue to constrain their transformative potential.

4.7.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

The biodiversity challenge in the Simeto Valley is recognised by multiple local actors, yet its assessment and monitoring remain partial, fragmented, and often detached from the socio-ecological context. At the institutional level, biodiversity evaluation is conducted primarily by technical agencies using standardised quantitative indicators derived from national and EU frameworks, such as ISPRA (Superior Institute of Environmental Protection and Research) and the Habitats and Birds Directives. However, these methods frequently fail to capture local complexities, particularly those linked to agricultural practices, land-use transformations, and the erosion of traditional ecological knowledge.

In contrast, niche actors, including our societal partner, are experimenting with more inclusive and participatory forms of biodiversity monitoring. These initiatives encompass community mapping, shared field observations, citizen science, and the co-production of knowledge among citizens, farmers, and researchers. They generate a more situated and relational understanding of biodiversity, one often challenging dominant narratives grounded in efficiency and extractive logics.

Despite the existence of European policy frameworks advocating the integration of local knowledge into decision-making—such as the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030—their influence on institutional practice remains limited. Data fragmentation, weak inter-institutional coordination, and the lack of formal recognition for bottom-up initiatives continue to undermine the effectiveness of biodiversity monitoring. Consequently, a dual system persists one based on detached technical indicators, and another emerging from efforts to anchor biodiversity assessment within the everyday social and ecological life of the Valley.

4.7.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

The current socio-ecological system (SES) of the Simeto Valley simultaneously enables and constrains transformative innovation, revealing a complex interplay between opportunities and barriers. The territory remains deeply conditioned by entrenched extractive dynamics: large-scale agro-industrial monocultures and industrial photovoltaic plants define it as a “production site” subordinated to capital-intensive logics. This economic structure, reinforced by processes of land concentration and the resurgence of new latifundia, limits the autonomy of farmers and communities. Producers—whether tied to citrus monocultures or engaged in experimental farming—are subordinated to global value chains and retail monopolies that capture most of the economic value. These mechanisms act as systemic barriers, eroding ecological knowledge, fragmenting communities, and weakening the connection between production, culture, and territory. Institutional conditions further consolidate these constraints. Local institutions are fragmented, under-resourced, and often unable to translate European frameworks or national plans into locally adapted strategies. Ineffective governance structures allow external actors—large landowners, agro-industrial operators, and energy investors—to consolidate their dominance. This governance vacuum not only weakens institutional responsiveness but also legitimises narratives of marginality, portraying the Valley as underutilised and therefore open to external exploitation.

Within this constrained environment, several opportunities for transformative change nonetheless emerge. Niche innovators such as the Simeto Ecomuseum and local civic networks are experimenting with alternative governance practices, relational economies, and community-based management of common goods. These initiatives foster social learning, strengthen local capacities, and re-embed knowledge and values that counter extractive logics. The Valley’s biodiversity, cultural heritage, and strong sense of place attachment among residents represent further levers for transformation, sustaining narratives that link ecological care with social justice.

A key example of this counter-movement is the collaborative mapping of photovoltaic plants, developed through partnerships among researchers, citizens, and the societal partner. This participatory process makes visible the scale, distribution, and socio-ecological impacts of industrial photovoltaic installations across the Valley. By transforming technical data into collective knowledge, mapping reclaims public agency over land-use decisions and exposes the unequal distribution of costs and benefits associated with the energy transition. It functions both as a diagnostic and a political tool, enabling communities and municipalities to envision alternative, biodiversity-conscious pathways for renewable energy development.

Building on this foundation of collective awareness, Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) have emerged as a complementary and proactive response. Developed through collaboration among citizens, small producers, and local institutions, they reframe energy transition around principles of equity, participation, and territorial regeneration. RECs integrate social and ecological objectives, democratising energy governance while reducing dependence on external investors. By redistributing energy benefits locally and reinvesting surpluses in community welfare and ecological restoration, they demonstrate how renewable energy can strengthen rather than erode socio-ecological relations. Together, participatory mapping and RECs illustrate how territorial knowledge and civic innovation can converge to reclaim control over the energy transition and embed it within a broader agenda of environmental justice and biodiversity protection.

In this light, the Simeto SES can be described as both restrictive and generative: restrictive because economic and institutional configurations perpetuate dependency and value extraction; generative because it nurtures resilient niches of innovation capable of reorienting development trajectories. The Valley's transformative potential ultimately lies in consolidating these niches, enhancing institutional capacity, and building bridges between local knowledge systems and multi-scalar policy frameworks. The central challenge is whether these opportunities can overcome entrenched power asymmetries and reconfigure the Valley from a site of extraction into a laboratory of socio-ecological innovation.

4.7.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

Alternative imaginaries concerning the socio-ecological system (SES) in the Simeto Valley revolve around three interrelated domains: agriculture, energy, and water. These sectors form the analytical core of the case study and are deeply entangled with power asymmetries, marginalised knowledge systems, and regenerative potentials operating across both formal institutions and informal practices. A profound rethinking of these domains is urgently needed, as they are the spaces where the human–nature divide has produced the deepest fractures. The following sections explore how alternative SES visions emerge through socio-ecological relations, narratives, and frames of meaning, illustrating the BIOTraCes principles of pluralising, empowering, politicising, and embedding transformative practices within the local socio-ecological context.

Agriculture: Planting Past and Future

In the agricultural domain, alternative visions are articulated through agroecological experiences that contrast sharply with conventional monocultural practices. These imaginaries integrate multiple knowledge systems and ethical values that position biodiversity as a central socio-ecological principle. They express a re-embedding of humans within ecosystems, rejecting framings of the environment as a mere tool of production. This process of integration exemplifies the pluralising principle, as it brings together scientific, experiential, and traditional knowledges to reframe agriculture as a shared socio-ecological practice.

This reintegration unfolds through both material and ethical choices, shaping new configurations of human–nature relations and alternative SES narratives. Regenerative agricultural practices prioritise renewed relationships with soil, water, animals, and vegetation, reversing the extractive logic of monoculture. In contrast to citrus farming only intended to maximise nutrient uptake, regenerative approaches aim to return nutrients to the soil, shifting from extraction to reciprocity. Such reciprocity and care practices directly align with the empowering principle, strengthening farmers' agency to regenerate ecosystems and redefine their roles within the SES.

These practices also reveal a different relationship to time, enacted through specific spatial and temporal strategies. By reintroducing pre-monoculture species and restoring the "Sicilian Garden"—a diversified, year-round agroecosystem designed for subsistence—farmers perform an ecological and political act of selective remembrance, bringing a "good past" into present practice. Simultaneously, they look forward by selecting species resilient to climate stress, responding to rising temperatures and water scarcity. These practices thus traverse past, present, and future, reweaving the fractured relationship between nature and humans. Through such regenerative cultivation, new interspecies relations emerge, engaging a wider range of non-human actors and enriching the SES with plural and dynamic relations. In doing so, these agricultural practices embed new socio-ecological

ethics in everyday action, contributing to the long-term institutionalisation of biodiversity-friendly governance.

Energy

Energy has long been a structural dimension of the Simeto Valley, dominated by hydroelectric and, more recently, agro-photovoltaic infrastructures. Both forms of production have profoundly shaped the landscape, especially along the river axis, and reflect a legacy of technocratic engineering rooted in urbanisation and agro-industrial modernisation. The dominant framing views water as a resource and the river as a servant of human activity, privileging economic utility over ecological continuity.

Emerging alternative narratives challenge this utilitarian paradigm. While the shift toward renewable energy is widely acknowledged, the ecological legitimacy of existing infrastructures is questioned. Hydroelectric installations disrupt river connectivity, harm aquatic biodiversity, and externalise environmental costs to non-human actors. In this light, energy transition cannot proceed “at any cost”: its pursuit must be ecologically embedded and socially just.

Hydropower also exposes key governance asymmetries. The ENEL corporation—which manages most hydroelectric plants—exerts a dominant influence over the river’s governance, often in conflict with farmers and local institutions. Although formal authority lies with the River Basin Authority, ENEL’s power renders governance opaque and exclusionary. This reflects the necessity of politicising governance processes, a BIOTraCes principle aimed at confronting power asymmetries and fostering accountability in resource management. An alternative SES narrative reframes the river as a socio-ecological actor and energy as a co-produced good, aligning technological innovation with territorial care. This vision calls for hybrid, inclusive governance arrangements, where democratic participation is expanded to include civil society, farmers, associations, municipalities, and institutional authorities. Such inclusive arrangements illustrate the embedding principle, as they institutionalise participatory governance mechanisms that ensure long-term ecological justice.

Similar concerns surround photovoltaic and agro-photovoltaic installations, whose rapid proliferation—driven by the crisis of conventional agriculture and the entry of multinational corporations—has deeply transformed the landscape. These developments raise issues of democratic legitimacy, territorial extractivism, and decision-making opacity. Yet, through participatory research and collective mapping, local communities are gaining agency, demanding greater accountability from institutions and challenging dominant energy narratives. This empowerment of local actors reflects a practical application of the empowering principle, as knowledge co-production translates into community capacity to influence territorial governance. Within the Simeto Valley, energy transitions are thus inseparable from broader struggles for territorial justice, where power, ecology, and democracy intersect.

(Not Only) Water

An alternative SES vision necessarily includes water, though it is essential to distinguish between water and the river as distinct, yet interdependent non-human entities that co-constitute the Valley’s socio-ecological fabric. Dominant discourses tend to conflate them, reducing the river to mere “flowing water” and erasing its socio-ecological complexity. Such reductionism excludes other inhabitants—animals, plants, and human communities—from the symbolic and material dimensions of the river’s life.

Restoring the autonomy of the river as a subject, rather than a resource, means recognising its central ecological and cultural role, which is foundational for inclusive and regenerative processes. Focusing on water, an alternative vision highlights the informal networks that structure its use and access. Water provision across the Valley relies on consortia and micro-infrastructures sustained by everyday relationships among landowners, technicians, and farmers. These informal systems form a territorial knowledge network, an invisible yet vital socio-ecological infrastructure. This recognition of informal governance pluralises environmental knowledge, a direct application of the BIOTraCes principle of pluralising.

In an alternative SES, this distributed intelligence could be acknowledged as a collective actor, enriching plural environmental governance and producing place-based, situated knowledge crucial for adaptation to water crises. Regarding the Simeto River, an alternative SES framework must recognise power asymmetries and knowledge pluralisation. Grounding a new SES means understanding the river as a living entity, embedded in human and non-human relations. This entails rebuilding connections based on non-extractive principles and embracing its multiplicity. Conventional conservation frameworks, such as protected areas or Natura 2000 sites, remain insufficient to capture this relational ecology. Politicising environmental governance thus becomes essential to confront institutional inertia and address the hidden power dynamics shaping river management.

A broader biodiversity narrative must instead view the Simeto as a living common, connecting communities, livelihoods, and species—including marginalised and criminalised practices like fishing and riverine herding. Archival and ethnographic research shows how such traditional ecological knowledge has historically tied communities to the river and continues to persist. Recognising these practices as part of the living heritage of the SES affirms that biodiversity regeneration also depends on memory, reciprocity, and coexistence. Embedding these values within participatory institutions reflects the BIOTraCes principle of embedding, ensuring long-term transformative integration of biodiversity and governance.

Concluding remarks

The alternative SES visions emerging in the Simeto Valley articulate plural pathways toward transformative change. Through agroecological innovation, energy democracy, and water commons, local actors demonstrate that biodiversity regeneration is inseparable from participatory governance and collective learning. Together, these practices enact the BIOTraCes principles: they pluralise knowledge, empower local agency, politicise socio-ecological conflicts, and embed new forms of democratic governance. Rooted in care, reciprocity, and memory, they reveal how transformative change can be grounded in everyday practices, aligning ecological restoration with social justice and cultural renewal.

4.7.3 Discussion

The analysis of the socio-ecological system (SES) of the Simeto Valley highlights the complexity of interactions between agriculture, energy, water, institutions, and local communities, as well as the persistent tensions between extractive dynamics and emerging regenerative practices. At the heart of this SES lies a structural contradiction: while conventional agriculture, hydraulic infrastructures, and the expansion of photovoltaic energy reproduce logics of extraction and commodification of the territory, niche actors—including agroecological farmers, civil society organisations, and community initiatives—seek to reconfigure human–nature relations along more inclusive, care-oriented, and biodiversity-enhancing lines. The result is a contested socio-ecological landscape, where

divergent values, knowledge systems, and governance arrangements both constrain and enable opportunities for transformative change.

A first key finding concerns the dominance of monocultural agriculture and its far-reaching socio-ecological implications. The so-called conventional farmers, who still represent the majority in the Valley, remain tied to the production model established in the post-war period. Citrus monoculture—once the economic engine of the region—continues, despite its growing economic and climatic unsustainability, to shape the Valley's landscape, practices, and multispecies relations. The SES thus remains anchored to this model, which exerts strong ecological impacts through chemical fertilisers, pesticides, and intensive irrigation. Evidence indicates that these practices perpetuate a cycle of soil depletion, disconnection from the river, and increasing vulnerability. This model also entrenches dependence on subsidies, accessible mainly to large producers who benefit from greater technical and bureaucratic capacity, thereby reinforcing local power asymmetries. In addition, large producers depend heavily on informal and exploited migrant labour, reproducing systems of social and ecological exploitation. The replacement of the diversified Sicilian Garden with monocultures has therefore entailed not only ecological degradation but also a cultural rupture, eroding relational modes of inhabiting the landscape and weakening practices of care.

By contrast, farmers adopting alternative practices—often younger and managing smaller plots—experiment with organic, regenerative, and diversified cultivation that challenges the dominance of monocultures. Although limited in scale, these initiatives act as socio-ecological innovations with the potential to transform the broader SES. They express inter- and multispecies ethics, conceiving agriculture as a regenerative practice grounded in reciprocity. In these experiences, the river acquires renewed importance as a non-human actor: rather than being treated as a resource to be exploited, it is recognised as a living element that sustains both biodiversity and community resilience. This worldview materialises in practices such as open-soil irrigation systems inspired by traditional saje channels, demonstrating how plural knowledge systems can support biodiversity regeneration and empower local agency.

Water more broadly constitutes a second central axis of the SES and one of its most contested fields. The mid-twentieth-century hydraulic infrastructures that regulate the Simeto River continue to shape relationships between humans, ecosystems, and institutions. The functioning of irrigation consortia and the network of water wardens reveals both the importance of governance structures and the extent of their informal operation. Smaller consortia, maintaining close relations with farmers, tend to ensure more effective management and maintenance than the larger Consorzio di Bonifica No. 9, whose bureaucracy often limits responsiveness to local needs. Alongside these bodies, ENEL's control over hydroelectric plants exemplifies how large economic actors dominate the management of natural resources, prioritising energy production over ecological continuity. These dynamics expose institutional weaknesses and the lack of participatory river governance, evidencing the need to politicise water management and embed plural governance models that integrate local and ecological knowledge.

The energy sector constitutes a third arena where extractive logics and transformative possibilities coexist. Large-scale hydroelectric and agro-photovoltaic plants, although framed as green solutions, often reproduce forms of ecological exploitation and territorial impoverishment. Hydroelectric infrastructure disrupts river continuity, while industrial photovoltaic plants convert farmland into silicon monocultures, intensifying land abandonment and agricultural crisis. These developments are justified by narratives

depicting the Valley as an empty or backward territory available for large-scale interventions in the name of ecological transition. Yet these processes are increasingly contested by grassroots networks, civic organisations, and participatory research initiatives. Through actions such as community mapping of energy infrastructures, local actors are empowered to challenge extractive models, claim energy democracy, and foster transformative governance aligned with biodiversity protection.

Across these sectors, the findings confirm that narratives, values, and knowledge are decisive in shaping governance and enabling transformative change. Dominant discourses—rooted in modernisation paradigms—portray the Valley as underutilised or marginal, legitimising external interventions and extractive policies. By contrast, counter-narratives articulated by farmers, associations, and civic movements emphasise care, memory, and identity, framing biodiversity as both a social and ecological good. This conflict of values lies at the heart of the SES: institutional inertia and power asymmetries sustain the status quo, while grassroots actors attempt to pluralise governance and embed more inclusive, care-based approaches.

The transformative potential of the Simeto SES is therefore ambivalent. Deeply entrenched economic and institutional structures continue to constrain innovation: land concentration reinforces inequality; global market dependencies restrict autonomy; and fragmented institutions fail to integrate local knowledge. Yet niches of innovation—including the Simeto Ecomuseum, Presidio, small agroecological farms, and community energy projects—demonstrate viable alternatives. These initiatives foster collective learning, place attachment, and plural knowledge exchange, offering tangible examples of the BIOTraCes principles in practice: pluralising knowledge, empowering communities, politicising ecological challenges, and embedding participatory governance.

Ultimately, the Simeto SES confirms that socio-ecological systems are contested arenas where power, knowledge, and values are constantly negotiated. Narratives of territorial marginality obscure ongoing social and environmental injustices, legitimising extractive interventions. Yet alternative framings—rooted in care, reciprocity, and biodiversity—are re-emerging from below, reshaping collective imaginaries of transformation. Institutional inaction remains a major obstacle to transformative change, but grassroots innovation continues to move through informal channels that sustain democratic experimentation.

Concluding remarks

The Simeto Valley SES exemplifies the tension between extractive dynamics and regenerative alternatives, between institutional inertia and grassroots innovation, and between dominant narratives of emptiness and emerging narratives of care and biodiversity. Agriculture, energy, and water appear not merely as economic sectors but as arenas of socio-ecological negotiation, where future pathways are co-produced. Strengthening innovation niches, addressing structural inequalities, and creating participatory governance arrangements that value biodiversity, local knowledge, and care are essential steps toward transformative change in the Valley and beyond.

4.8 Foodpark Against Industry, Netherlands

Authors: Tamalone van den Eijnden, Corelia Baibarac-Duignan, Esther Turnhout (UT)

Foodpark Amsterdam is a grassroots organisation that aims to protect an area in the city of Amsterdam (the Lutkemeerpolder) from industrialization. Their approach consists of three interrelated strategies. The first strategy is protest. The movement protests the plans to develop the area and build warehouses on them through banners and flyers and by using public consultation. The second strategy is to frame a broader narrative. In this narrative, they present the development plans as representing an unsustainable economic worldview that is based a separation between people and nature, overconsumption, and property, and they contrast this with an alternative worldview that conceives of land not as property but as commons and that considers humans as entangled with nature. The third strategy is prefiguring and building an alternative. Specifically, they aim to create a foodpark that will be governed as a commons and that will foster enhanced human nature relationships, and they also prefigure this model of the commons in the inner workings of the grassroots organisation. The case study demonstrates how these different strategies work together to not only protect a specific area, but also build an alternative, commons based, society.

4.8.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

4.8.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

The primary actor for our research has been the initiative Foodpark Amsterdam. The original aim of Foodpark Amsterdam is to reverse the municipality's current plans of turning the land into an industrial area for the building of distribution centres and transform it into an agroecological commons. The aim is to show how different agroecological entrepreneurs (ranging from food foresters to urban farmers, to herbalists, and cooks) can cooperate and share the land as a Commons and make it a place for learning, food, culture, and recreation for the neighbourhood and other engaged participants.

The most important cluster of counter players are the municipality, the Schiphol Area Development Company (SADC), and the Gemeenschappelijke Exploitatie Maatschappij (GEM) company. In practice, this means that for Foodpark Amsterdam the focus is often on the municipality, specifically the section of land and development [*in Dutch Afdeling Grond en Ontwikkeling*], since the municipality is part of the Schiphol Area Development Company – together with Schiphol airport, the municipality Haarlemmermeer, and the province of Noord-Holland. The Schiphol Area Development Company, on its turn is part of the Gemeenschappelijke Exploitatie Maatschappij company (GEM BV) – together with the municipality of Amsterdam.³

Besides these actors, during a workshop held in summer 2023 in which we mapped the Social Ecological System with seven members of the initiative FPA, the following stakeholders were identified:

- organic and agroecological enterprises that are located in the Lutkemeerpolder (e.g. CSA Pluk, the Stadsgroenteboer, Alies Natuurlijk and the Boterbloem)
- residents of the neighborhood Amsterdam Nieuw West
- cultural organizations in Amsterdam, e.g. Waag Future Lab

³ An explanation of the SADC and the GEM (and more) can be found on the Behoud Lutkemeer website: [Save the Lutkemeer polder! – Behoud Lutkemeer!](#)

- IVN (a Dutch nature education organization)
- the Tuinen van West (adjacent area to the Lutkemeerpolder).
- Grond van Bestaan
- Toekomstboeren
- Aardpeer
- Land van Ons
- Lenteland
- the Donut coalition
- the Schumacher Center for new economics
- community land trust networks (which mostly focus on housing)

Another way in which stakeholders can be mapped, can be found in a report that was written by Foodpark Amsterdam member Natasha Hulst together with Annelies van Herwijnen and David Bollier.⁴ In this report they address the issue of multivalue creation, which at the same time gives an important insight into a type of stakeholder classification. As can be seen in the figure below that is taken below from the said report, here they classify stakeholders as earth, municipality, entrepreneurs, and citizens. We could understand this classification of stakeholders as a classification that concerns various civic roles stakeholders can fulfil. Perhaps most relevantly, this shows that the earth is recognized as an important stakeholder within this social-ecological system in Amsterdam.

Figure 8.1. Categorization of Stakeholders from "Building a financial ecosystem for thriving commons in Amsterdam" (2024).

⁴ The report is titled "[Building a financial ecosystem for thriving commons in Amsterdam](#)" published on the [openresearch.amsterdam](#) platform, research is shared with civil servants in collaboration with knowledge institutes in Amsterdam. For more information on [openresearch.amsterdam](#) see [Nieuw platform deelt onderzoek en kennis over Amsterdam | Website Onderzoek en Statistiek](#).

We categorized relevant partners into Economic Initiatives, Food Initiatives, and Arts initiatives. For more detail see D2.2, what follows is just a summarized list:

Economic Initiatives

- Stichting Grond van Bestaan
- Schumacher center for new economics
- Waag Futurelab
- And the People
- the Commons Network
- the MeentCoop
- commons agenda of the municipality

Food Initiatives

- the Slowfood movement
- Futurefarmers [*in Dutch Toekomstboeren*]
- the Foundation for urban agriculture [*in Dutch Stichting Stadslandbouw Amsterdam*]

Arts Initiatives

- Waag Futurelab
- Lumbung Curatorial Program
- de Appel Curatorial Programme
- International Architecture Biennale Rotterdam, *Nature of Hope* exhibition

To sum up, there are different ways to think, categorize and map the different actors relevant for the case of the Lutkemeerpolder. It becomes clear that Foodpark Amsterdam is exceptionally well-connected with other organizations in the immediate neighbourhood and nationally. Moreover, their network involves a broad spectrum of types of organizations and partners, that simultaneously show the multidimensionality of the initiative Foodpark Amsterdam.

4.8.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

While we have seen above that various actors are involved, when it comes to decision making processes and power dynamics, it helps to focus on two key (groups of) actors. On the one hand, we have Voedselpark Amsterdam, on the other hand, we have the developers of the Business Park Amsterdam Osdorp, the SADC, which, as we have shown above, involves the municipality in multiple ways, specifically the section of Land and Development [*Afdeling Grond en Ontwikkeling*]. As the municipality is a democratically elected organization that stands for the public good of its residents, the main focus of FPA has been to convince the municipality of their alternative plan for the place.

The conflict around the Lutkemeerpolder is in fact a conflict of power around the issue who is able to decide what happens with the 'green environment' within Amsterdam. Land prices are an important factor in how decisions regarding the social ecological system are being made and implemented. For the municipality it is one way to receive money from lease contracts. As the municipality – almost per definition – will always struggle to manage their budget (there are always important investments to be done on a municipal level), there is a strong incentive to lease out the land for a high price.

Affordable access to land for small ecological entrepreneurs is a very important aspect of the mission of Foodpark Amsterdam, which is particularly relevant in the context of the Netherlands. This is because, today, the Netherlands has the highest land prices for

agricultural land within Europe and in fact also worldwide.⁵ It is about eight times above European average.⁶ Such high land prices make the hurdle for starting agroecological farmers who did not inherit land very high. This in fact limits the decision-making power of aspiring agroecological farmers as it firstly limits their access to land and secondly provides very strong incentives to engage in intensive farming to make ends meet.

It is the aim of Foodpark Amsterdam to counter this imbalance and support small scale ecological, regenerative urban agriculture by taking the land out of the market and turning it into a Commons. This is not only to support the farmers, but also to ensure that locally grown, organic, and healthy food is accessible for everybody and not just for elites. In such a way, Foodpark Amsterdam is looking for ways to increase the autonomy in terms of decision-making power for agroecological entrepreneurs and ultimately also the residents that will benefit from being able to choose locally grown organic and healthy food.

4.8.1.3 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

In the case of the Lutkemeerpolder, there are two dominant – and largely opposing types of knowledge on biodiversity, namely a modernist perspective and a relational perspective. The modernist worldview understands nature as something that can be calculated and managed, that provides either intrinsic or instrumental values and that needs to be balanced against human and economic interests. Within the case of the Lutkemeerpolder, instrumental values provide the dominant lens according to which the Lutkemeerpolder is evaluated. In other words, the polder is not understood as a valuable in itself, but as a resource to be used in the most efficient way. Within the dominant standard economic paradigm, what is then ‘the best use,’ is primarily evaluated in financial terms. As we have seen above, for the municipality more income is gained from leasing land to industry.

During a Joint FactFinding session in February 2024, Foodpark Amsterdam and the municipality both explained and challenged each other’s vision on the Lutkemeerpolder. When making the case for the necessity of a business park, the municipality was referring to the growth of the city as providing the imperative for industrial expansion. As they explained, this growth of the city is about population growth and job opportunities and it is the growth of job opportunities that is growing quicker than expected (Joint Fact Finding

⁵ “Nowhere in the world is agricultural land more expensive than in the Netherlands” (Joosten 2024, own translation). In a footnote Joosten nuances this, conceding that certain agricultural lands for luxury grapes for culturally protected brands exceed this price, as well as small plots of land in dense urban areas (Joosten 2024). Joosten continues, “According to figures from the Land Registry and Wageningen Economic Research, the average price of a hectare of farmland broke the 95,000 euro mark for the first time in August. Ten years earlier it was about 53,000 euros. That’s an increase of 80 percent. By comparison, the general inflation rate during the same period was 27 percent. In Flevoland, an acre of arable land now costs almost as much as a Porsche 911” 2024, Translated with DeepL). For more information see: [Agrarische grond - actuele vastgoedcijfers - Kadaster.nl zakelijk](https://www.kadaster.nl/zakelijk). Also see [Agricultural land prices and rents - statistics - Statistics Explained - Eurostat](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&code=sdg_12_10), [Agricultural land prices: huge variation across the EU - Products Eurostat News - Eurostat](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&code=sdg_12_10). This shows, compared to other countries, the Netherlands certainly have the highest land price. It also has the regional highest land price, if island regions are not included.

⁶ For this, Joosten also uses this source: [Agricultural land prices and rents - statistics - Statistics Explained - Eurostat](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&code=sdg_12_10).

report 2024, p. 2, 12).⁷ Implicitly, the growth of job opportunities (that is the prospect – not the actual reality – of more jobs) serves as the major reason for industrial expansion. In other words, more job opportunities require more opportunities for industry. This then presents the circular logic of capitalist growth, where the prospect of more economic growth continuously requires also more resources. There is discussion on the nature of the jobs and how this would benefit society.

Yet, even as the business park exemplifies a modernist logic of value extraction and expropriation, they simultaneously do not want to be seen like this. This becomes clear in the way they appeal to the natural and social values of the Business Park Amsterdam Osdop. During the Joint Fact Finding meeting, the municipality, for instance, was appealing to the public good of more municipal revenues. They also go into great detail explaining their vision on biodiversity emphasizing the ecological experts they have been working with.⁸ In an interview that celebrates the “outstanding” certificate for spatial planning by the Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) the Business Park Amsterdam Osdorp has received, Hein Veldmaat, Business Leader sustainability and urban development at the advisory and engineering office Technisch Adviesbureau van de Unie van Waterschappen (TAUW) says about biodiversity within the business park:

Biodiversity is often viewed primarily as something that looks nice and has some useful functions. Soil biodiversity receives little attention in this regard because knowledge about it is limited and it is less visible. Therefore, it is often skipped when designing and managing.

The construction of business parks often assumes “dead soil,” using sterile soil and planting standard plants. This leads to boring business parks that contribute little to biodiversity and disrupt the landscape. It is also unsustainable because few ecosystem services are provided. We wanted to do that differently.

By using the original soil, we not only preserve the identity of the area, but also ensure a good start with the existing soil biodiversity. This matches the soil types and habitats in the wider environment.

This requires courage, because we are increasingly discovering how important soil life is for everything that grows above it, while we still understand little about it. We are taking a progressive approach, focusing on the preservation and restoration of the original soil (2025, DeepL assisted translation).⁹

⁷ The Joint Fact Finding report (2024) can be found here: [Joint Fact Finding - Voedselpark Amsterdam](#).

⁸ For instance, they write: “In close consultation with experts, such as the city ecologist, soil life specialist from Naturalis and the landscape manager of Spaarnwoude, we searched for robust and diverse biotopes for the originally arable land in the area” (DeepL assisted translation). For the full interview, see [Achtergrondinterview BREEAM-Outstanding certificering Business Park Amsterdam Osdorp fase 2 - SADC](#).

⁹ They are also proud of the impact they make on water quality: “In the water park – a high-quality urban park that includes aqueducts- the rainwater from the roofs and grounds converge and an ecological design provides increased water quality. Strategically placed groups of trees, with their foliage, not only provide meeting places with light and shade, but also form the route for bats in the connection between Westgaarde Cemetery and the western nature reserve the Green Axis. Which again is a very nice walking route for people, with bridges and beautiful native plants and trees. Instead of building traditional hard infrastructure like storm sewers or frame walls to hold back water, we use Nature Based Solutions. These are flexible and have the ability to adapt to changing environmental

In such a way, and nearly analogous to the arguments of Foodpark Amsterdam, the business park assumes almost the role of a guardian of the marine clay soil of the Lutkemeerpolder. Moreover, they foresee an important social role of the Lutkemeerpolder. According to project manager Sheila van Vliet:

...we also looked at how this business park can contribute to social cohesion in the area. How does the area fit into the environment and how can we design it so that it becomes a place where much more happens than just work? That it becomes a place where people like to come together and are a logical part of it? And how do we connect existing local initiatives like 'Gardens of West' with the entrepreneurs who are here? Those are questions that the design really answers beautifully (2025, DeepL assisted translation).¹⁰

Veldmaat further adds

Partly to achieve this cohesion and connection between people, we designed the public space as a fruit orchard with 1,500 fruit trees and created a water park as the heart and meeting place" [...] "The fruit trees provide a meeting place to pick and shape a community process (2025, DeepL assisted translation).

The sincerity of these ambitions may be doubted as no business park is necessary for this purpose. Organic farming has been a great way to sustain and nurture the marine clay for many generations, and there already exists an orchard and community within the Lutkemeerpolder, which are now erased from the plans of the business park. This then presents a clear instance of greenwashing. As mentioned in section three of this document, Vanessa Machado de Oliveira understands modernity as something that is unevenly distributed. In light of the rhetoric of the project developers of the business park Amsterdam, something similar could be said about a rationalist view. While the business park clearly represents the dominant logic of modernism, the way 'dresses up' with relational values as well (concerning soil and social life) shows the complex entanglement of these incompatible worldviews. Even if this rhetoric is merely strategic and not connected to a relational practice, it demonstrates that 'modernist project' on its own is considered to be shallow and as such needs to appropriate other than economic values to thrive.

While businesses use mostly empty green language in the hope they can continue as much as possible with 'business as usual,' we can note instances where Foodpark Amsterdam is doing the reverse, adopting a modernist language to make themselves heard within the modernist framework, and in such a way unleash 'unusual business'. For instance, Foodpark Amsterdam argues that the business case of the business park is limited, because it does not take into account the suboptimal infrastructural location of the business park, with no highway exit close by and a road system that was not built for heavy traffic from a distribution centre (Joint Fact Finding report 2024, p. 10).¹¹

Besides, Foodpark Amsterdam also employs the logic of instrumental values to point to other socio-ecological values that are often referred to as ecosystem services. Oftentimes,

factors, such as extreme weather conditions" (DeepL assisted translation). For the full interview, see: [Achtergrondinterview BREEAM-Outstanding certificering Business Park Amsterdam Osdorp fase 2 - SADC](#).

¹⁰ See full interview here: [Achtergrondinterview BREEAM-Outstanding certificering Business Park Amsterdam Osdorp fase 2 - SADC](#).

¹¹ For more information on the Joint Fact Finding report, see here: [Joint Fact Finding - Voedselpark Amsterdam](#).

the value of these ecosystem services is evaluated in financial terms. However, the risk of such financial evaluation is that it makes nature substitutable, because different financial values can be weighed against each other. A good example of such a view of nature are the two scientific reports that were written by the science shop of Wageningen University and Research and were issued by Behoud Lutkemeer, in many ways the predecessor of the initiative Foodpark Amsterdam. The first report *'Discovering the values of the Lutkemeerpolder'* from June 2019 identifies five instrumental values: the agricultural value, the natural value, the recreational value, its care function, and its educational function. The second report from 2020, *Valuing nature*, further elaborates on this and presents the following values (p.3)¹²:

1. Agriculture (117.600-196.400 €/year)
2. Air quality (270.000-915.00 €/year)
3. Aesthetics (450-1.800 €/year)
4. Pollination (18.200-26.500 €/year)
5. Carbon Sequestration (11.800-47.200 €/year)
6. Care Services (52.000-83.200 €/year)
7. Irrigation (1700-7.200 €/year)
8. Biological Pest Control (11.500-16.100 €/year)
9. Recreation (1.5-7.5 million €/year)
10. Water Retention
11. Spiritual
12. Habitat
13. Water Quality
14. Educational Services Raw Materials

This shows, that Foodpark Amsterdam strategically employs scientific knowledge and terminology that is well-accepted in science-policy circles. Vis-à-vis the municipality, this helps them to strengthen their claim that their resistance against the distribution centre is not a 'mere' case of 'not in my backyard' but in fact an instance of opposing the dynamics of biodiversity loss – a matter that has real costs.

Nonetheless, even as Foodpark Amsterdam is capable of convincingly employing an instrumental values perspective on biodiversity, they are also very critical of it, especially when ecosystem services are quantified into financial revenues. Firstly, they have seen that these quantifications of nature always lose out against business, even if on paper they would be higher as the industrial activities that will now take place in the Lutkemeerpolder. The reason for this is that the diverse financial returns that flow from 'ecosystem services' are often more distributive in nature and what Bollier (but also the article by the municipality) thinks of as inalienable.¹³ To put it simply, a flourishing nature

¹² Both reports can be found via this link: [De waarde van ecosystemendiensten in de Lutkemeerpolder - WUR](#).

¹³ Inalienability, as it is also written in the report on "Building a financial ecosystem for thriving commons in Amsterdam" by Natasha Hulst, Annelies van Herwijnen and David Bollier is a key attribute of the commons. As they put it: "*Inalienable Non-extractive Shared Wealth*: In commons, shared wealth is considered inalienable in perpetuity. There are no intentions to liquidate common assets or "cash out" in the future, a feature that ensures their longevity and sustainability. Commons and the value and wealth they create, are not designed to yield financial gain." (Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier 2024, p. 2). This is an idea that Bollier and colleagues have been developing already over many years, see for instance also [Free, Fair and Alive. The insurgent power of the Commons \(2019\)](#).

will benefit the neighbourhood in many ways – ranging from health to community. But the money that is ‘gained’ in such a way is distributed among various actors of the socio-ecological system.¹⁴ If for instance within 30 years, a person needs less medical treatment because they live in a greener environment, move more on a daily basis, eat more healthy food and have a caring community around them that can take care of them when they won’t feel well, certainly a lot of money is saved. Yet this money is distributed and a long-term investment. It won’t provide immediate cashflows to the municipality nor any other pocket.

Secondly, the concept of ecosystem services is problematic since it financializes values belonging to the land, as the 2020 report Valuing nature by the Science Shop of Wageningen University and Research demonstrates¹⁵: And so, while on some occasions

they may employ the language of ecosystem services for strategic purposes, on a more fundamental level they actually oppose it. This is because they object to conceiving of the land in financial terms, overshadowing and extracting all other kinds of values. In fact, their idea of turning the land into an agroecological commons presents an alternative to the financialization of land.

Figure 8.2. LinkedIn post¹⁶.

¹⁴ The issue of health was an issue that came up several times during the *Day of Urban Agriculture 2023* and also was critically reflected on by Foodpark Amsterdam members. The distributed value, as exemplified by increasing the general well-being within one neighbourhood is also something that Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier recognize and discuss as a major challenge. In this context they raise the issue of “avoided financial costs”. As they put it: “Invisible secondary avoided costs: non-financial value that is created oftentimes results in avoided financials costs in a different realm or sector. This is especially true when the non-financial value is created through destruction of financial value. An example: by cutting the number of river cruise boats coming through Amsterdam, the city will lose 63 million of revenues and approximately 700 work places. However, cutting the number of cruise ships will result in cleaner air and a more livable city, reducing long term health care costs for residents and avoiding costs that pollution causes” (Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier 2024, p. 8).

¹⁵ Both reports can be found via this link: [De waarde van ecosysteemdiensten in de Lutkemeerpolder - WUR](#).

¹⁶ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/philippstaudacher_naturecredits-biodiversityfinance-impactinvesting-activity-7348037829786034177-

FPA presents an alternative to the modernist worldview and a relational vision on the Lutkemeerpolder that is based on land as a Commons. In this vision, land is not a property of humans, but something that humans can take care of to provide for their material existence. This alternative foregrounds mutual dependencies and reciprocity. Agroecology is central to the FPA vision because it emphasizes locally situated human-nature-food relations and interdependencies. The yellow cucumber that is now cultivated and promoted by some of the core members of the Foodpark Amsterdam team is an example of reviving local knowledges.¹⁷

To sum up, when it comes to the Lutkemeerpolder, there are opposing worldviews and values at stake, that can be divided into a modernist vs. a relational paradigm. However, even as these paradigms are incommensurate, this does not mean that they are neatly separated within political dialogue. Foodpark Amsterdam, for instance employs a modernist language to convince the municipality of the value of the Lutkemeerpolder. At the same time, the efforts of the project developers to present the integrated greenness of the business park as an outstanding virtue of the park also shows – perhaps – an effort to ‘buy into’ the values of a relational framework. This, however, remains an empty discursive rapprochement and importantly does not make the business park in any way less instrumental and modernist.

4.8.1.4 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

Today, in the case of the Lutkemeerpolder, land-use change is the biggest direct driver of biodiversity loss. It is important to note that in the past centuries, this landscape has been subject to many drastic land use changes. The Lutkemeerpolder changed from peat to a lake, and then in the 1860s to farmland. However, the land use change Foodpark Amsterdam is concerned with today is about the change from agricultural land, which was farmed mainly organically throughout the generations, to an industrial area. The biodiversity that is lost not only concerns the rich soil cultures that are the result of agroecological farming, the diversity of species that are cultivated by agroecological farming and are the byproducts of it,¹⁸ but also the open fields, low ditches, and trees that mark boundaries between fields and have been a home to a host of other species with no direct relation to farming, such as a plethora of insects and meadow birds.

However, it is important to note that that this land use change did not happen ‘on its own’ but is driven by the dominant modernist worldview that seeks to make the revenues of

jXa_?utm_source=social_share_send&utm_medium=member_desktop_web&rcm=ACoAA
DSg4-8BcaXpbgfYUv2vrIKifBigLUJAeWk

¹⁷ For more information see: [De terugkeer van de Gele Komkommer - Slow Food](#).

¹⁸ In 2023, for instance, Colin Anderson, Ernesto Méndez, Patrick Mulvaney, and Faris Ahmed write: “The evidence from FAO, IPBES and IPCC has clearly established that agriculture and land use change are among the main drivers of biodiversity loss. Large scale, monocultural, industrial agriculture threatens 86% of the 28,000 endangered species. In the last century we have also lost most of our genetic diversity in crops and livestock on industrial farms.

Currently, only 12 plant species and 5 livestock breeds make up 75% of the world’s industrial food system, with just 3 species (wheat, rice and corn) providing half the calorie intake.” For more information see: [Agroecology – A promising alternative to the biodiversity crisis in agriculture and industrial food systems - resilience](#).

nature ever more efficient. First agricultural land was more profitable than a lake and now an industrial park is more profitable than agriculture.

4.8.1.5 Values underpinning decision-making processes

As we have seen above (and also in section 3.2 on “Key Actors and their Impact on Worldviews”), we can distinguish two competing worldviews that are underpinned by specific values. The struggle of Foodpark Amsterdam is to move between these two worldviews and the values associated with them. One challenge is that the values of a relational worldview are poorly understood within a modernist worldview. It is for this reason that Foodpark Amsterdam is balancing continuously between making themselves understood within the modernist worldview, while also showing the limitations of this worldview and creating space for relationality. However, as we have seen in the case study, relational values often lose out against modernist values. Not necessarily because they provide less value but because relational values are more distributed among various social-ecological actors (including the human and more than human world) and because they are inalienable and resist exchangeability. As Foodpark Amsterdam initiator and allies Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier (2024) write about the commons in Amsterdam:

...current frameworks, including markets, property law, and regulatory structures, often fail to grasp the value and complex dynamics of commons, undermining their potential for development. The reason for this lack of understanding is that commons operate in a completely different realm from the current frameworks: the value created by commons is typically not transactional or translatable in monetary terms (e.g. fresh air, safe communities, reliable information), (Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier 2024).

Foodpark Amsterdam members are collaborating with municipal actors to seek solutions. For instance, some Foodpark Amsterdam members participated in 2024 in a pilot led by the municipality of Amsterdam on general prosperity scan [*brede welvaart scan*]¹⁹. As Foodpark Amsterdam activists reported, the aim of the pilot was to discuss the assessment framework for evaluating a business vs. Foodpark.²⁰ Moreover, Foodpark Amsterdam also wrote a ‘social paragraph’ in September 2024, after the Joint Fact Finding report was discussed in the commission for spatial planning on July 3, 2024 and they received the question about what the Foodpark would mean for the neighbourhood of Nieuw West.²¹

Foodpark Amsterdam is now also participating in the Community Wealth Building program of the ‘National Program Together Nieuw West’ [*Nationaal Programma Samen Nieuw-West*]. According to Foodpark Amsterdam initiator and allies Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier

Community Wealth Building (CWB) emerges as a significant intermediary between commons and traditional corporations. Community wealth building (CWB) is a people-centred approach to local economic development, which redirects wealth back into the local economy, and places control and benefits into the hands of local people. Local needs

¹⁹ More information on how the municipality understands general prosperity can be found here: [Brede Welvaart Scan - openresearch.amsterdam](https://openresearch.amsterdam/).

²⁰ According to a Foodpark Amsterdam activist, the organizers said that the results will be shared with the commission for spatial planning. Yet it is unclear whether that happened. Moreover, they had some doubts about the methodological rigour of the pilot.

²¹ For this purpose, gathered for 27 points on what Foodpark Amsterdam could mean for Nieuw-West and categorized them into the eight indicators for general prosperity as defined by the three planning offices in the Netherlands. More information on the work of Foodpark Amsterdam on general prosperity can be found here: [Voedselpark Amsterdam: Brede welvaart en Nieuw-West - Voedselpark Amsterdam](https://voedselparkamsterdam.nl/brede-welvaart-en-nieuw-west-voedselpark-amsterdam).

are met by local entrepreneurs, thus eliminating local wealth extraction. CWB initiatives in Amsterdam seek to integrate community interests into economic activities. The main potential distinction between CWB and commons lies in their approach to ownership and wealth distribution. In CWB, ownership structures may resemble traditional corporations, where activities can be sold or profits distributed to owners - who are local entrepreneurs and the employees. Conversely, commons always operate on a self-owned basis, ensuring that wealth generated remains within the collective domain (2024, p. 4).

Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier see community wealth building as one of the practical solutions to make transitions (which Bollier also refers to as OntoShifts²²) from business as usual of a standard economic practice to a commons economy. This then can work as a strategy of transvestment, “the deliberate transfer of value from conventional capitalist circuits of money into commons-based circuits of value” (Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier 2024, p.17).

4.8.1.6 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

As has been shown before, institutional and political power lie primarily with the municipality of Amsterdam, including the GEM company (Gemeenschappelijke Exploitatie Maatschappij bv) and the SADC (the Schiphol Area Development Company), the latter of which on its turn also involves the municipality of Amsterdam. Culturally, these power dynamics show a dominant worldview that prioritizes specific instrumental knowledges and values, which so far we have presented as a modernist worldview.

For the purpose of an exhibit at the International Media Architecture Biennale (2024) Natures of Hope, we theorized these different kind of power in terms of ‘*Managing Green Infrastructures*’ vs. ‘*Commoning Green Intimacies*’. The following narrative was originally submitted to be displayed at the show:²³.

‘Managing Green Infrastructures’ articulates a sterile and technocratic vision on planning and managing land and sees nature as something that is detached from humans, commensurable, and fungible. Its value can be assessed and compared through standardized metrics. This narrative considers green to be important, but holds that green infrastructures should be efficiently designated and managed to optimize functionality and balance economy and ecology. In this vision, Lutkemeerpolder is dismissed as inefficient, messy, and mundane; an area that can and should be sacrificed for industrialization, specifically the building of warehouses.

‘Commoning Green Intimacies’ foregrounds intimate and place-based, relations and principles of commoning and sees nature, land, food, and people as entangled. In this vision, The Lutkemeer is not exchangeable but irreplaceable and unique. Its value is not expressed in standardized metrics but resides in its unique qualities and affordances. These include the diverse human-non human relations that it makes possible, its future potential and contribution to human-ecological wellbeing, and its specific historical and cultural dimensions, such as the unique fertility of the marine clay that has been organically farmed for multiple generations and the socio-economic context of Amsterdam Nieuw West.

In the juxtaposition of these two narratives, Foodpark Amsterdam serves as both a hopeful alternative vision and a grassroots movement that prefigures this alternative vision and that engages in struggle to challenge the prevailing technocratic, managerial and economic logics and values that threaten Lutkemeerpolder.

²² OntoShift is an important concept of in Bollier and also informs how Foospark Amsterdam members think about transition and transformation. Together with Helfrich, he writes about it in the book *Free, Fair and Alive* (2019), where they defines it in the following way: “So to truly understand the dynamics of the commons, one must first escape the onto-political framework of the modern West. One must make what we call an “OntoShift” — a recognition that relational categories of thought and experience are primary” (p. 58).

²³ The version that was displayed in the show is a shortened version of this text.

In spring 2025, Foodpark Amsterdam has won a tender competition for a 9,5 hectares piece of land, adjacent to the land they are fighting to protect. This victory gives Foodpark Amsterdam the opportunity to prefigure on a larger scale their vision on collaboration and collective care for land. At the same time, it is an indication that the municipality recognized Foodpark Amsterdam as a serious party whose relational vision and ideas around commoning green infrastructure are inspiring while at the same time, they could make a serious business and development plan that ultimately could compete and win over a commercial party. Yet so far this shift in the image of FPA, did not lead to revisions of the business park, which remains the ultimate goal of Foodpark Amsterdam.

4.8.1.7 Embedding the local SES in the high impact sector

FPA intervenes most significantly in the impact sector of urbanization. The case reflects the more generally conflicting dynamics that are met within the sector of urbanization, such as the expansion of urban centres, the (perceived) need for economic growth to make the city attractive and profitable, and simultaneously the need to keep cities liveable by allocating enough space for green and maintaining space for small and local enterprises to flourish instead of privileging multinationals. There are some indications, that the latter is becoming more and more important in urbanization processes. In a report written by Foodpark Amsterdam initiator and allies Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier (2024) published on the *openresearch.amsterdam* platform that is connected to the municipality of Amsterdam write:

In the heart of Amsterdam, a quiet revolution is underway. Amidst growing disillusionment with traditional market mechanisms, an increasing number of residents are gravitating towards collective initiatives known as commons. These endeavors, from community gardens to shared childcare and public space management, prioritize community well-being over profit, while at the same time avoiding bureaucratic complexities. (Hulst, Herwijnen and Bollier 2024, p.1).

Foodpark Amsterdam's vision of an agroecological Foodpark also reflects a more general international trend that recognizes the value of urban farming for biodiversity, food sovereignty, community building, and community wealth building, urban cooling, etc. Prominent examples from other European cities involve the R-Urban network in Paris, including the urban farm Agrocité,²⁴ Paris' general greening program,²⁵ another prominent example is the city of Barcelona, that generally promotes urban gardening and also is connected to the big [Parc Agrari del Baix Llobregat](#).

4.8.1.8 Economic structures impact over the SES

Affordable access to land for small ecological entrepreneurs is a very important aspect of the mission of Foodpark Amsterdam, which is particularly relevant in the context of the Netherlands. This is because, today, the Netherlands has the highest land prices for agricultural land within Europe and in fact also worldwide. More specifically, it is about eight times above European average²⁶. The reasons of this all relate to the intensification of agriculture. Changes like "Land consolidation, increasing fertilizer use, concentrated feed and the advent of specialized pesticides provided decades of ever-increasing production", which were factors that contributed to the high land prices as investigative journalist Joosten explains. This is how it is possible that the Netherlands still constitutes the second

²⁴ For more information see: [AGROCITÉ | R-Urban English](#).

²⁵ For more information see: [Paris aims to plant 170,000 trees to keep the city cool | World Economic Forum](#).

²⁶ see: [Agricultural land prices and rents - statistics - Statistics Explained - Eurostat](#).

largest agricultural exporter worldwide²⁷ after the United States while being about 237 times smaller²⁸.

The export of agricultural goods of the Netherlands becomes even more astonishing if one considers not only its surface, but also its population density. The Netherlands has one of the highest population densities on a European comparison, and the metropole area around Amsterdam certainly belongs to the more densely populated areas of the Netherlands. All this gives a general picture about how green areas are under pressure in the Netherlands, particularly green spaces that are not used in intensive ways and make space for biodiversity. In this context, we may also understand that worldwide and on a European level, the Netherlands also registers low in terms of biodiversity. In the Netherlands, “most protected species and habitat types that fall under the birds and habitats directives are currently not in a favourable conservation status” (Balans van de leefomgeving 2023, 74). This includes the loss of fauna in agricultural areas (Balans van de leefomgeving 2023, 75). Moreover, while during 2011 and 2022, there was a small increase in organic farming, the current percentage of 4 % of all agriculture is far below European average (Balans van de Leefomgeving 2023, 87). Finally, the use of resources by the Dutch economy has devastating environmental impacts abroad (see e.g. Balans van de Leefomgeving 2023, p.57)²⁹.

This combination of high land prices and high environmental degradation within an area that is densely populated makes agroecological urban agriculture all the more urgent and difficult. Agroecology is also not supported while unsustainable forms of farming are incentivized among others by means of subsidies. In this context, it is the aim of Foodpark Amsterdam to counter this imbalance, support small scale agroecological urban agriculture by taking the land out of the market and turning it into a commons. This is not only to support the farmers, but also to ensure that locally grown, organic, and healthy food is accessible for everybody and not just for elites. This ambition would also be beneficial for the neighbourhood near the Lutkemeerpolder. Savini describes the neighbourhood as “Peripheral relative to central Amsterdam, the site adjoins one of the city's poorest neighbourhoods, Nieuw West. The area covers a business park for SMEs (Business Park Amsterdam Oosdorp, phase 1) of 26 hectares, a graveyard of 30 hectares and 42 hectares of agricultural land” (Savini 2025).

4.8.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

While generally speaking, greening cities and fostering relations between city inhabitants, nature and sustainable food are increasingly recognized as important, the critical question is how this is done. What we have seen in our case is that the Lutkemeer is not seen as a sufficiently valuable green area to protect. The municipality plans these green spaces and food spaces in a managerial way that ignores the local and historical relations involved in the Lutkemeer.

4.8.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

As we have discussed, the current SES is characterized by opposing and conflicting dynamics underpinned by specific worldviews and values. The ways in which modernist

²⁷ See: [Top exporters of agricultural goods worldwide by country 2020 | Statista](#).

²⁸ See: [Size of Netherlands compared to United States \(mylifeelsewhere.com\)](#).

²⁹ [Balans van de Leefomgeving 2023](#)

values, and vested interests including the market and the financialization of the land are given prevalence forms a serious barrier to transformation. An increased understanding of alternative ways to govern the land may open up opportunities for change. In other parts of this deliverable, we have discussed the different activities and strategies that FPA employs to this end. Here we would like to illustrate this potential opportunity using the role of GreenLeft politician, Marieke van Doorninck as an example.

As shown in the [Documentary: The last Farm of Amsterdam \(2023\)](#) – for the activists of Behoud Lutkemeer (the older sister initiative of Foodpark Amsterdam) Marieke van Doorninck became the face of municipality that ultimately sided with the business interests. Exactly in the period when Behoud Lutkemeer was involved in many public action and resistance (2018-2022) she was alderman for spatial development and sustainability. The documentary showed well the conflict she was facing, since as a GreenLeft politician she had sympathies for the case of Behoud Lutkemeer but saw herself forced to execute the plan of the business park. The documentary ends with a moment of reconciliation between Trijntje, the farmer who used to work on the land where the building activities are now taking place and Marieke van Doorninck, as they found a solution that three hectares of the original farm will be saved. Nonetheless, for many of the activists and supporters who often were themselves affiliated to the GreenLeft party, it was still a disappointment that not even a GreenLeft alderman could change more radically the fate of the Lutkemeerpolder. However, three years later, in 2025, Marieke van Doorninck was one of the main organizers of The Day of Community Economy [*in Dutch Dag van de Gemeenschapseconomie*], an event that brought together various commons initiatives in the city of Amsterdam. It is quite notable that Foodpark Amsterdam was specifically invited to be present with a market stand.

While this is a small step and far removed from the structural changes in the governance of land that Foodpark Amsterdam is advocating for, this example demonstrates how even within the municipality, radical rethinking can take place. All in all, we have seen increased openness to alternative forms of land governance (commons), a dissatisfaction with economic and governance systems, and a recognition that other worldviews might have something to offer. These are powerful leverage points for transformation.

4.8.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

While the current trend within the social-ecological system of the Lutkmeerpolder is mainly characterized by increased industrialization, the alternative vision would be that building activities stop right away. This alternative social-ecological system explores, which other trends would be foregrounded if the building activities would now come to an immediate halt. Lutkemeer would become a space where energies for urban agriculture can be bundled and materials and infrastructures can be shared. It would give agroecological, community-supported urban farming the chance to prove itself as mature and robust alternative option in the food economy, that makes a difference in terms of food sovereignty and capable of catering to a wide range of incomes and tastes. Already today, at the margins of the Lutkemeerpolder, there are two organic CSA farms,³⁰ one organic horticulture enterprise,³¹ and one organic care farm with farmer's shop³².

³⁰ [De Stadsgroenteboer](#) and [boterbloem - plukcsa](#).

³¹ [AliesNatuurlijk – Voor Ecologische Kringlooptuinen](#).

³² [ecoboerderij de boterbloem](#).

In this scenario the landscape of the polder would become more diverse than it has been over many centuries. Today, the land that is destined to become a business park is a fallow meadow that used to be arable and for organic grain and potato monocultures. The adjacent piece of land is currently still a corn monoculture that until last year heavily employed glyphosate and (after Foodpark Amsterdam complained) this year used other pesticides. Against this background, a agroecological food park managed by different entrepreneurs would radically diversity and regenerate the landscape.

We can imagine that within the expanded food park of the alternative social-ecological system, there would be more vegetable gardens and fruit and nut trees.³³ Maybe, there will be people that would like to grow hemp for bio-based and CO₂-negative building materials?³⁴ Probably, there will be also a glasshouse or poly-tunnel dedicated to the growing to exotic produce, like plantain, casava, and okra. There would be also some more secluded spaces that do not serve any immediate purpose to humans but allow different species to find their habitats. For instance, insects, birds, and amphibians would flourish near shallow waters, which is why previously involved landscape architect put much emphasis on drawing shallow shorelines of the ditches.

The Lutkemeerpolder would also become a place for social healing and dialogue, including in relation to slavery and colonialism. There are strong historical indications that the lake of the Lutkemeer was drained with money from compensatory payments after the abolition of slavery in Surinam³⁵. This illustrates how the industrialization of agriculture of the Netherlands was financed through the exploitation and industrialization of people and nature in the colonies. This makes the Lutkemeerpolder a very suitable place to hold broader conversations about coloniality, exploitation, and social justice.

Within the alternative social-ecological system, the current unpopularity for businesses to settle in the Lutkemeerpolder would remain.³⁶ Already today, many of the distribution centers remain empty and are hired out below the market price according to Foodpark Amsterdam activists.³⁷ Some of the already existing distribution centers could be repurposed by Foodpark Amsterdam, serving as tool barns, labs for processing local food (pickles, fermented produce, wine, beer), producing other plant products (tinctures, ointments, soap, cloth), growing mushrooms and managing local food distributions to the local farmer's market and affiliated kitchens.

³³ As one Foodpark Amsterdam activist often reminds us, the high stem fruit orchard next to the Boterbloem can already be seen on maps from 1870. Today it serves as the main place for social outdoor gatherings. For a 50 hectare Foodpark, we can imagine that another place like this will be welcomed.

³⁴ One of the Foodpark Amsterdam members works in sustainable buildings and often makes the case for this.

³⁵ For more information see [De verborgen geschiedenis van de Lutkemeerpolder: een nieuw perspectief - Voedselpark Amsterdam](#).

³⁶ Behoud Lutkemeer writes about the emptiness of distribution halls [Leegstand – Behoud Lutkemeer!](#).

³⁷ They came to this conclusion after having done a search for real estate larger than 10.0000 m² on Funda, (the main websites for renting and buying real estate in the Netherlands) and used a radius of 10 km around the location of the Lutkemeerpolder.

Figure 8.3. Advertisement board reads 'For rent', November 2024. Image by Tamalone van den Eijnden.

We can imagine that in the future entrepreneurs would sometimes struggle with the increasingly irregular seasons that characterize ongoing climate change. Sometimes, there would be intense rainfalls and then extended periods of dryness and heat that used to be quite atypical for the area. Yet, we can imagine that, provisions will be taken to store water during rainy days that could be used in dry periods. Moreover, refraining from heavy tilling and the diverse vegetation of the polder increases in general its capacity to retain water and prevent soil erosion. In times of extreme wetness, the agroecological farmers are happy that they do not depend on heavy machinery that would get stuck in the mud.³⁸ We could even imagine that the farmers set up a solidarity and insurance system among each to ensure that if one entrepreneur would suffer great losses due to weather extremities, they could be supported by the other entrepreneurs since dryness and wetness will affect the different entrepreneurs differently. It is in such ways, that we can imagine that the farmers and agroecological entrepreneurs make the park climate adaptive.

The Lutkemeerpolder would also become a test ground for generating locally relevant ecological knowledge in collaboration with educational institutions ranging from primary school to vocational training to scientific research as it does already today.³⁹ Educational and research activities would address topics like soil life, intercropping, reviving almost forgotten heirloom species, and old and new techniques in food-processing.⁴⁰ There would be a broad interest from artists and students in social sciences and humanities to

³⁸ The CSA farmers now settled in the Lutkemeerpolder do not use any powered machinery.

³⁹ Foodpark Amsterdam has close ties with all kinds of educational institutions locally and nationally for all age groups and educational directions. Students come for fieldtrips and internships, and researchers conduct all kinds of research.

⁴⁰ Like for instance the yellow cucumber, which has been already initiated by current FPA associates, see for instance [De terugkeer van de Gele Komkommer - Slow Food](#).

document processes of transformations, support the community-processes of the place, and imagine alternative futures for the place. It would also not be unusual to see politicians, journalists and research teams to come on tours around the Lutkemeerpolder. Within the alternative social-ecological system, Foodpark Amsterdam has become one of the flagship initiatives for the municipality of Amsterdam that is prolifically used in their PR. Quite likely, the municipality will present Foodpark Amsterdam as *their* idea and vision. While this may raise some eyebrows among members of Foodpark Amsterdam, they also welcome this shift in thinking and rhetoric.⁴¹

When cycling to the Lutkemeerpolder, it would be usually easy to spot the people that are just coming from the place, as their bike bags would be filled with fresh vegetables and more. Sometimes, you would see them cycle on rented electronic cargo bikes, when they have extraordinarily much to transport. On market days of the market on Plein 40-45, at the center of the neighborhood of Nieuw West, there is an electronic truck that brings produce from the different entrepreneurs to the Voedselpark Amsterdam market stand to bring the food close to the people. On its way back and forth, the truck also immediately shuttles less mobile people back and forth to the Lutkemeerpolder.

In order to sufficiently support and accompany the work of the agroecological entrepreneurs, Foodpark Amsterdam would need to professionalize, particularly for the first period. They would need a project manager that would be employed for four days a week for at least four years. Moreover, a dedicated fundraiser would need to be hired. After the first labour intensive years, the Foundation Foodpark Amsterdam would slowly become less important because now the entrepreneurs are capable of running the place on their own.⁴² With new time on their hands, the Foodpark Amsterdam activists would then see where else they could support the growing of agroecological commons. Perhaps in another neighborhood in Amsterdam...perhaps in a neighboring town or village.

The establishment of the foodpark in the Lutkemeerpolder would not put an end to disagreements in the Lutkemeerpolder, but it would change the nature of the disagreements. Some agroecological entrepreneurs may find that the area has become too busy and advocate for reduced visiting hours and quiet hours on the nature camping. Others may find the diverse landscape to be too messy. There may be discussion about what kind of machinery could be allowed to use on the place (e.g. whether electronic, motorized or purely mechanical). Another controversial topic are bonfires. They are seen as unwelcome by some due to Co2 emissions, air pollution, and risk of wildfire. Yet, they are also valued as cozy and they offer a convenient form of waste removal. Moreover, we can imagine that the last word has not been said on what non-native species should be invited into the ecology of the polder. Another point of discussion will be whether or not there should be space for farm animals, and if so, which ones. Moreover, some entrepreneurs more than others, would struggle to make a minimum wage with their work and it would take a long time and many creative solutions to find

⁴¹ To some extent this is already happening with Foodpark Amsterdam after they won the tender and other related initiatives, where it took citizens much time and effort to convince the municipality to take a certain course of action.

⁴² The activists that are now running the Foundation Foodpark Amsterdam, see themselves primarily in the role of helping to get an agroecological commons started. They do this through their political work, moderating and accompanying the processes of forming a community, organizing the legal support and administration, financial support, etc. Ideally, they would like to become irrelevant as soon as possible.

a stable enough market for their products. All these issues would be discussed once a month during the general assembly of the cooperation for all the agroecological entrepreneurs.⁴³ In advance, people expected that it would be impossible to also make time for this assembly next to their working schedule, but they soon got a routine for this. We can imagine that assemblies will be often combined with a simple vegetable stew and freshly baked bread. These monthly meetings would help to forge strong solidarity ties between the different entrepreneurs.

4.8.3 Discussion

In this brief sketch of the social-ecological system around the Lutkemeerpolder, we have discussed the dynamics and conflicts, around a contested piece of land. Given the active communication strategy of Foodpark Amsterdam and the Lutkemeerpolder being located within the city boundaries of the capital city, it is perhaps not surprising that this piece of land involves a large diversity of actors and networks that range from the neighborhood level, to the municipal level to the national and even international one.

The different actors and networks relate to the Lutkemeerpolder and more specifically the vision of the Lutkemeerpolder as articulated by Foodpark Amsterdam from different angles, such as their vision on alternative (commons) economies, their vision on agroecological food, and their vision on the importance of understanding change processes as deeply rooted in culture – and thus the necessity to implicate and involve cultural movements and artists in sustainability transformations.

Despite this diversity of involved actors, the main conflict within the Lutkemeerpolder remains a conflict between Foodprak Amsterdam and the municipality (extended through the Gemeenschappelijke Exploitatie Maatschappij (GEM) Lutkemeer and the Schiphol Area Development Company). The issue at stake are two opposing ideas on land, where Foodpark Amsterdam holds that land (here the Lutkemeepolder) should be dealt with as an agroecological commons and the municipality defends the position where land serves as an economic commodity that is in service of the growth of the city.

This conflict, at its core is a conflict between a modernist and a relational worldview – two worldviews that are fundamentally incommensurate but in political daily practice and strategically mixed into each other. Even as it is increasingly widely recognized that the modernist view plays a large role in biodiversity loss, it still wins over the relational one on an institutional level, since it produces financial value that can be easily channelled to people but also municipal budgets. The relational model, while providing plenty of value, loses out as its value is more distributed within a wider human and more than human socio-ecological system, as such it hardly makes individuals rich and also does not fix municipal budgetary problems, particularly not in the short-run.

These conflicts and dynamics take place within the impact sector of urbanization. Yet interestingly, also within urban development we do note that there is increasing recognition that a narrow capitalist-economic perspective is not sufficient for keeping cities liveable. We see efforts across European metropolises to green cities and support urban and other citizen-led agroecological grassroots initiatives. The fact that Foodpark Amsterdam has won a tender competition for an adjacent piece of land where they can start a small Foodpark perfectly fits into this trend. We are still far from a reality where a relational worldview is

⁴³ Also within the current tender plans, the agroecological entrepreneurs that will be working within the Lutkemeerpolder will form a separate cooperation that is independent from the Foundation Foodpark Amsterdam.

applied more structurally within urban development, yet, there are small indications that slowly recognition of the limitations of the current systems start to grow. Time will tell, whether these positive signals will be the first glimmer of more structural and transformative change or whether they ultimately will be incorporated into a greenwashed modernist worldview. This is why Foodpark Amsterdam continues its struggle.

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4.9 Nature-Inclusive Building, Netherlands

Authors: Roel During, Zoe van Eldik, Amy Wortel, Rosalie van Dam (WR)

The planning, design, and construction of new houses and neighborhoods has a significant impact on nature. Over the past decade, approximately 280 square kilometers have been converted into human habitats, coinciding with a corresponding decline in agricultural and natural areas. The sector is rightly considered high impact. In response to its problematic relationship with nature, efforts have been made to incorporate more nature into human living environments. These innovation programs are referred to as part of the “nature-inclusive agenda.”

The system tasked with building around one million homes in the coming decade is highly complex, involving a multitude of actors, legislation, and political disputes. As a result, it is difficult to change. The power to initiate or resist change is distributed across a vast public-private network. The aim of this case study is to uncover the structures and mechanisms that either block or enable innovations that could improve the sector’s relationship with nature.

This case study focuses on one such nature-inclusive innovation program, *Natuur voor Elkaar* [Nature for Each Other], hosted by the Province of Overijssel. In parallel, it examines an innovative citizens’ initiative called *De Beuk*, which aims to establish an ecovillage and eco-community on the outskirts of Wageningen. The research methods applied are rooted in action research. By engaging directly with the bio-innovative enterprise and collaborating with the citizens of De Beuk and provincial officers, researchers encountered the challenging path of marginalization, blockage, and leverage.

Biodiversity loss is indirectly driven by a narrow view of nature, as merely species and habitats—whose decline is assumed to be compensable by converting agricultural land into new nature reserves. This approach backfires in politics and public opinion, as the public tends to sympathize with farmers. Nature is often blamed for the sector’s current stagnation. The deterioration of nature is countered by an increasingly strict set of regulations. Ironically, these same regulations now hinder the success of bio-innovations. Innovations emerging from new human-nature relationships are seen as potentially harmful to the forms of nature that existing protection frameworks recognize and safeguard. The regulatory and permitting system is unyielding.

The case study reveals that innovation within the sector is primarily driven by goals of efficiency and the adoption of biomaterials. Ideological and moral innovations, however, do not fit within the sector’s systemic boundaries. Although nature-inclusive building is broadly recognized, it is still hard to realize and sometimes more words than practice.

4.9.1 SES dynamics, interactions, and relations

The social-ecological system in the Netherlands is built on rules and regulations designed to protect nature from further deterioration. It resembles the ecological-economic SES conceptualisation described in D1.6. Nature reserves are managed through plans that set biodiversity goals. If management results in biodiversity decline, stronger legal measures must be taken.

Over time, the social and ecological dimensions have become almost separated, as ecological issues have increasingly turned into technical and legal matters. Local pride in national landscapes with high natural value is relatively low. Policies have therefore been

introduced to strengthen this pride, such as national park programmes aimed at fostering local connections and building public support.

Quantitative opinion polls show that natural values are widely regarded as highly important for society, though this recognition tends to remain at an abstract level.⁴⁴ When nature becomes more concrete and local, it is often perceived as a 'party pooper'. The strong technical focus, combined with policies that place responsibility for nature largely in the hands of management organisations, has gradually distanced nature from people's everyday lives.⁴⁵

Based on European regulations, any initiative with a potential impact on nature has to perform an analysis to assess expected effects on:

- Protected habitats
- Protected species
- Nature 2000 reserves

Legal frameworks oblige developers not only to account for the effects of a single activity, but also for the cumulative effects of human interference with nature in and around the projected site. In cases where there may be an impact on Natura 2000 reserves, an appropriate assessment [*'passende beoordeling'* in Dutch] is mandatory. Extremely strict norms apply to nitrogen emissions, as they contribute to already excessive levels of deposition in nature reserves. Any plan may reduce or increase nitrogen emissions or alter the chemical compounds in which nitrogen is emitted and transported. These changes must be calculated using the so-called Aerius model.

Many aspects of the assessment rely on expert judgement. When emissions exceed legally defined thresholds, the assessment is reviewed by the Netherlands Commission for Environmental Assessment. If an assessment shows effects on nature, these must be mitigated or compensated in order to obtain a permit for the activity.

The social-ecological system is based on maintaining or restoring the quality of nature, measured by the presence of important indicator or rare species. It carries a compelling historical dimension: nature management is dedicated to restoring the nature that once existed, aiming to meet concepts of how nature was perceived in former times. Even when conservationists speak of "nature development," outcomes are referenced against primeval nature. Marc Argeloo, who coined the term "nature amnesia," describes this as nostalgic nature recovery (2025). The system makes a sharp distinction between nature and humans. Overall, humans are seen as a threat to nature, while simultaneously acting as stewards of its well-being. The Birds and Habitats Directives stipulate that nature must not deteriorate compared to its condition at the time the directives were adopted in 1992.

Nature is considered easier to preserve in the countryside than in cities. Yet both in agrarian landscapes and urban areas, nature is seen as colonising specific habitats through opportunist species. It is almost exclusively within nature reserves that conservationists speak of ecosystems—places where species cooperate, compete and co-evolve in processes of succession.

⁴⁴ <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/longread/rapportages/2025/de-gebruikswaarde-van-natuur-in-nederland?onepage=true>

⁴⁵ https://www.tijdschriftcdv.nl/actueel/nieuws/130-48_Naar-een-nieuwe-natuurvisie

In project development, the inclusion of nature has become part of the public-private discourse on sustainability. This involves reserving spaces for green structures, creating roosting places for bats, and nesting spots for swifts and other birds. It also functions as compensation, since the modernisation of old houses has led to a dramatic decline in species living in and on buildings. How to deal with nature is addressed in a covenant called *Future-Proof Building*. In this public-private covenant, nature is treated as a principle: nature-based solutions should prevail over technical ones, ensuring worthy habitats for species living in buildings, trees, thickets, flowery grasslands, or water and banks. Projects may choose from three levels of ambition: bronze, silver or gold.

The Province of Overijssel is working to change the mainstream of project development by implementing good practices in nature inclusion. This involves giving nature a structural place in the design of new neighbourhoods and ensuring that young people have regular contact with nature. Their practice is becoming embedded in mainstream project development, and this approach is proving effective. They use formal arguments and causation frameworks, but a holistic ideology underpins their work.

In the case of De Beuk, a first ecological quick scan assessment has been carried out. However, it has become outdated due to recent policy changes on nitrogen emissions. The assessment focused on the actual and potential presence of protected species, the suitability of certain habitats for protected species, the ecological functionality of the area (feeding, breeding, migration, overwintering), and initial judgements of the impact of building a neighbourhood on protected species and on Natura 2000 areas. It did not assess potential effects on the water system or soil quality. Nor did it address the question of the reference basis for nitrogen, which represents a legal difficulty.

4.9.1.1 SES impact on different actor groups

Below, an impression is given of the actors in and around De Beuk, that are impacted by the social-ecological systems at work in relevant regulative frameworks. This picture was made in a co-learning workshop. A similar workshop was organised in Overijssel, with the province The actors of both workshops are put in table 9.2 below, wherein also the impact of the SES is indicated.

Table 9.1. Actors of the Beuk

Actor	How impacted by the formal SES
Politicians on municipal level	They must comply with the formal system that is used by the province but are open to add other arguments and include novel values that are normally out of the scope of the sector.
Politicians on provincial level	Same as municipal level but facing the responsibility of maintaining the quality of nature, measured in the way the SES prescribes.
Public officers on provincial level	Same as municipal level
Social housing cooperative	For new residential projects, they must comply with the regulations to acquire any permit. The effect of the SES is that those legal constraints need juridical support, in the end raising the price of houses. This makes building social housing less attractive and economically viable. However, by participating in the community of nature inclusive building, hosted by the province of

	Overijssel, some resources are provided to experiment and do research how to make their houses more nature inclusive.
Residents of province of Overijssel	Residents are impacted by provincial policies. Residents vote for a provincial board, as well as a water board, that create the provincial policies.
Local NGOs, such as Stichting Straatboeren	By being a partner of Nature for Each other, they are legitimized and are provided resources do to their work.
Local animals and vegetation	They have no voice in the SES, and decisions taken based on a SES analysis. Nature for each Other aims to have a positive effect on local animals and vegetation.
Project developers	Projects have become increasingly expensive with significant effects on the price of houses they build. They are complaining about the costs and about the velocity of planning and building new residential areas. For most project developers, Nature is perceived as expensive 'add-on' or blockage.
Architects and landscape architects	Architects and landscape architects that are a partner of Nature for Each other, all have ambitions to make nature-inclusive building more mainstream and having a positive effect on the SES. They struggle with a competitive market, where nature is often seen as add-on costs and efforts.
Builders and contractors	Builders and contractors have expressed the need of juridical and policy guidelines or laws to set a baseline for nature inclusive building.

Table 9.2. Actors of the province of Overijssel

Actor	How impacted by the formal SES
Politicians on municipal level	They must comply with the formal system that is used by the province but are open to add other arguments and include novel values that are normally out of the scope of the sector.
Politicians on provincial level	Same as municipal level but facing the responsibility of maintaining the quality of nature, measured in the way the SES prescribes.
Public officers on provincial level	Same as municipal level
Social housing cooperative	For new residential projects, they must comply with the regulations to acquire any permit. The effect of the SES is that those legal constraints need juridical support, in the end raising the price of houses. This makes building social housing less attractive and economically viable. However, by participating in the community of Practise of nature inclusive building, hosted by the province of Overijssel, some resources are provided to experiment and do research how to make their houses more nature inclusive.
Residents of province of Overijssel	Residents are impacted by provincial policies. Residents vote for a provincial board, as well as a water board, that create the provincial policies.
Local NGOs, such as Stichting Straatboeren	By being a partner of Nature for Each other, they are legitimized and are provided resources do to their work.

Local animals and vegetation	They have no voice in the SES, and decisions taken based on a SES analysis. Nature for each Other aims to have a positive effect on local animals and vegetation.
Project developers	Projects have become increasingly expensive with significant effects on the price of houses they build. They are complaining about the costs and about the velocity of planning and building new residential areas. For most project developers, Nature is perceived as expensive 'add-on' or blockage.
Architects and landscape architects	Architects and landscape architects that are a partner of Nature for Each other, all have ambitions to make nature-inclusive building more mainstream and having a positive effect on the SES. They struggle with a competitive market, where nature is often seen as add-on costs and efforts.
Builders and contractors	Builders and contractors have expressed the need of juridical and policy guidelines or laws to set a baseline for nature inclusive building.

4.9.1.2 Decision-making processes and power relations between relevant actor groups

Decision-making is complex. The effects of any initiative on nature must be assessed before a political decision can be taken. Monitoring the quality of nature in reserves is carried out by, or on behalf of, the State Forestry Agency or private institutes such as Natuurmonumenten. Most of this monitoring is undertaken by volunteers. If monitoring shows that critical target species are declining, the responsible institute must assess and address the problem, and a recovery plan must be drawn up.

Recently, an Ecological Authority has been established to evaluate the quality of information used in recovery or management of nature. Their work is legally mandated and aims to prevent further deterioration of Natura 2000 areas. At the system level, the minister is responsible for the quality of nature. At the field level, management organisations hold responsibility. In between, at the policy level, the provinces play a strong role and are held accountable for nature quality.

In the case of nitrogen, scientific actors have a decisive role: they assess the critical deposition loads above which vulnerable species will disappear. A model is required to assess the relationship between nitrogen emissions and deposition in Natura 2000 reserves.

Power is unevenly distributed. Much of it, political support based on public sentiment, lies with farmers, who are the largest emitters of nitrogen but are unable to change their farming practices due to financial constraints. The construction and housing sector is almost as powerful as the farmers. They have the means to buy out farms, thereby creating space for nitrogen emissions. The additional emissions from a project are compensated by the calculated nitrogen reduction of the farm taken out of production. This process is called nitrogen equalising (salderen), and it can be applied within a project or between projects. If large amounts of nitrogen space are required, a nitrogen bank is created.

Probably the greatest power position lies with the province. They may or may not grant a permit for a project. This permit was formerly regulated under the Nature Law and is now governed by the new Environmental Law. Municipalities have little power within the SES.

Similarly, the State Forestry Agency and Natuurmonumenten do not hold much power, though they can mobilise public opinion and thereby strengthen their position.

NGOs have a strong power position in that they can bring cases to court. Given the complexity of planning, there is almost always a flaw in the procedure. Through numerous lawsuits, NGOs have succeeded in changing nitrogen policies. Provinces and ministries remain cautious in dealing with them.

Citizens who take initiatives regarding nature generally hold a weak power position. Only when large groups are involved and the media amplify their cause can they gain some influence. A group like De Beuk has almost no power at all. They must operate within the framework of the SES and fulfil their legal obligations.

4.9.1.3 Governance of knowledge

The governance system relies on academic technical knowledge. For nitrogen, the outputs of computer models are given more weight than actual field measurements, since the latter may vary greatly over time (e.g. depending on wind speed, wind direction and rainfall). The process of technocratisation and juridification, as discussed above, means the system is not open to other sources of knowledge beyond the expertise that can stand up in court. Every decision in nature management is accompanied by extensive reports prepared by ecological consultancies. Human activities are, by default, considered negative influences, and there are rules of thumb for acceptable distances or dose–effect relations, based on the large number of impact assessments that have demonstrated significant effects. Other sources of knowledge, arising from alternative worldviews, are visible only in the media and play no role in decision making.

When it comes to identifying sites for new neighbourhoods, the SES operates differently depending on scale. At national level, the main issue is spatial conflicts. Potential effects on nature are discussed in very abstract terms, because the ultimate impacts depend heavily on how a residential area will be designed and constructed. This often leads to decisions about localities that prove far more problematic than initially anticipated. In Environmental Impact Assessments, most effects rely on expert judgement. At local level, the SES is much more fine-tuned, and in most cases effects can only be minimally mitigated, resulting in substantial compensation efforts. In the mainstream, compensation is achieved by buying out farms, which also creates legal space for nitrogen emissions.

If the system were to embrace other sources of knowledge related to nature positivity, this would require a fundamental rethinking of the relationship between humans and nature.

4.9.1.4 Types of knowledge informing decision-making and biodiversity framing

The governance system relies on academic technical knowledge. For nitrogen, the outputs of computer models are given more weight than actual field measurements, since the latter may vary greatly over time (e.g. depending on wind speed, wind direction and rainfall). The process of technocratisation and juridification, as discussed above, means the system is not open to other sources of knowledge beyond the expertise that can stand up in court. Every decision in nature management is accompanied by extensive reports prepared by ecological consultancies. Human activities are, by default, considered negative influences, and there are rules of thumb for acceptable distances or dose–effect relations, based on the large number of impact assessments that have demonstrated significant effects. Other

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4.9.1.5 Ecological functioning of the SES and direct drivers of biodiversity loss

The direct drivers of biodiversity loss are manifold, such as:

- Loss of habitats
- Soil disturbance
- Disconnecting nature reserves
- Increased traffic
- Quick water runoff
- Changing groundwater systems
- Nitrogen emissions due to the use of fuel

The SES functions as an agreement between public-private partners in the construction and building sector and nature management organisations. The principles are that:

1. Development activities have effects on nature.
2. These effects must be compensated.
3. Compensation ultimately leads to either an enlargement of nature reserves or an increase in the properties managed by nature organisations.

This arrangement is often presented as a win-win situation. However, biodiversity loss remains a concern, since compensation is rarely based on the exact ecological qualities of what is lost. Instead, it typically involves providing an equivalent area of land. For example, if ancient trees are removed for a development project, compensation usually consists of planting new trees. This does not account for the original leaf surface or the trees' established capacity to absorb CO₂.

4.9.1.6 Values underpinning decision-making processes

Broadly speaking, the building sector is primarily driven by financial considerations. The most dominant values in decision-making relate to increasing the number of houses and maximising their selling price. The sector tends to prioritise building homes for young families with good incomes. This is more profitable for project developers and constructors, and also advantageous for public administration.

By contrast, building for disabled people or elderly residents would imply a near-term strain on municipal budget calculations. For this reason, any deviation from what is most profitable generally requires intervention from higher authorities. This continuous process of negotiation often comes at the expense of including nature in projects. It is often mentioned in interviews and workshops that plans that are nature-inclusive start out with much higher aims than get realised in the end.

Nature is incorporated mainly through legal provisions, or in a bottom-up manner, as demonstrated by *Nature for Each Other*, which works collaboratively with partners in a network. However, they also struggle to make nature mainstream.

4.9.1.7 Political, cultural and institutional power dynamics

The sector advocates building one million houses within less than ten years, a goal motivated by demographic arguments. Much of this construction is intended to accommodate migrant workers and other immigrants; without these groups, the population would decline. The government does not have a demographic de-growth strategy. Within this context, any controversy involving nature is often framed by the sector as an obstacle to achieving this societal objective. The building and construction sector presents itself as a driving force of the national economy.

An alternative way to address the housing challenge would be to increase the number of inhabitants per dwelling, making house-sharing more attractive. However, this would generate less income for the government. More houses mean more revenue through dedicated taxes such as real estate taxes, VAT on building materials, and taxes on profits made by private actors in the sector. Public actors can also benefit financially if they participate directly in building projects, and this applies equally to semi-public actors such as the State Forestry Agency.

In practice, both public and private actors gain from the building process. Nature is often regarded as a constraint on returns, particularly when nature-inclusive measures require more space and reduce the number of houses per hectare.

Given the significant power of public-private partnerships (PPS), any conflict with nature is perceived as an infringement on their initial business model. The costs of hiring lawyers or pursuing court cases are negligible compared to project revenues. This contributes to the juridification of the sector's dealings with nature. It places a strong constraint on the SES, as the knowledge used must be legally defensible. This also strengthens the position of academics, since even minor uncertainties or knowledge gaps can provide openings to win lawsuits.

4.9.1.8 Economic structures' impact over the SES

Given the sector's ambition to build one million houses, large projects are generally favoured over smaller ones. Small innovative projects rarely meet the requirements needed to realise developments involving hundreds of houses. The public-private nature of the sector also makes it difficult for smaller initiatives to enter the market. Commissioning of new projects must usually take place in an open market, unless there are strong arguments to act differently. As a result, small innovative, nature-positive initiatives must compete with powerful project developers who do not need to borrow money for land acquisition and who possess the legal expertise to navigate regulatory hurdles.

In the Province of Overijssel, the programme seeks to introduce change within the open market system by applying a nature-inclusive grading system. This results in project tenders where nature-inclusive quality is valued alongside, or even above, low price.

When nature is incorporated into a project, this often reflects the priorities of specific parts of public administration, more often at provincial than local level. For example, the Province of Utrecht has launched the programme *Green grows alongside urbanisation (Groen groeit mee)*, which aims to balance green and functional urban structures. In this way, public administration invests resources in nature-leisure areas. Legislation allows for cost recovery from urbanisation projects, either through a facilitative process without a fixed timeframe or through an active approach within a defined period. Key here is the application of the PTP criteria—profits, attributability and proportionality—which set boundaries for investing in nature within the context of urbanisation projects.

Large construction firms operate internationally and have shareholder structures. Shareholders often place constraints on the resources allocated to nature inclusion.

Ensuring sufficient appropriate housing for highly educated residents and migrants is considered an asset for regional economies, as seen for example in the technology region around Eindhoven.

Banks tend to view collective projects such as *De Beuk* as financially risky. Mortgages for land acquisition in collective ownership, managed by an association of residents, are generally not available. Banks prefer individually based mortgages, and government regulation of the banking sector plays a role in this preference.

4.9.1.9 Assessment of biodiversity challenge and related biodiversity trends in the high impact sector

As discussed above in relation to environmental impact plans, local biodiversity challenges are not addressed at higher planning levels. Housing programmes are generally regarded as compensable in terms of natural quality. Awareness of the sector's contribution to ongoing biodiversity loss is relatively low, although there are initiatives moving in a more nature-positive direction.

Practices such as integrating nesting boxes into the building process are considered positive, albeit costly, innovations and have now been adopted into mainstream practice. A strong example of successful nature-inclusive building is provided by Unitura⁴⁶, a company offering a wide range of solutions for housing bats, insects, and nesting places for birds such as sparrows and peregrine falcons, as well as green façades, green roofs and local seed compositions. These products are tailor-made for new building projects and developed in cooperation with the construction sector. This represents an innovation that has emerged from within the sector itself.

Although the minister had planned to remove this obligation from the building decree (now part of environmental law), the sector had already integrated it into its workflow and opposed the proposal.

4.9.1.10 Current enablers and barriers for transformative change

Transformative change towards nature-inclusive building in the Netherlands is supported by some policy initiatives, innovative projects, and civil society engagement. At the same

⁴⁶ <https://.unitura.nl>

time, it encounters barriers such as financing constraints, regulatory rigidity, fragmented governance, and competition for space.

Enablers:

- Policy and government initiatives: The Dutch Ministry of Agriculture and Nature is actively promoting nature-inclusive living, emphasising greener, healthier urban environments.
- Collaborations and networks: Partnerships between policymakers, ecologists, architects, and local communities are helping embed biodiversity goals into urban development.
- Practical innovations: Companies like Unitura demonstrate how green roofs, façades, nesting boxes, and biodiversity-friendly designs can be integrated into mainstream construction.
- Collective Private Commissioning (CPC) carries potential for systemic change, as it supports innovations emerging from outside the sector and beyond its direct control. In connection with CPC, community based housing experiments show similar potential, particularly when communities intend to adopt nature positive lifestyles and apply advanced ecological techniques in the construction of their homes.
- Civil society involvement: The Collectief Natuurinclusief movement mobilise communities and professionals towards a shared vision of a nature-inclusive society.
- Public awareness: Opinion polls and campaigns show that natural values are broadly recognised as important, creating a supportive environment for policy change.

Barriers:

- Low private sector engagement: Many developers still prioritise short-term profitability over biodiversity goals.
- Competition for urban space: High demand for housing often conflicts with the allocation of land for nature-inclusive features.
- Insufficient policy implementation: While several frameworks exist, enforcement and mainstreaming of nature-inclusive standards remain inconsistent.
- Limited collaboration: Fragmentation between municipalities, provinces, and national authorities slows systemic change.
- Knowledge and data gaps: Reliance on technical models (e.g. nitrogen deposition) can overshadow practical ecological knowledge, leaving uncertainties that hinder innovation.
- Financial constraints: Banks often view collective or experimental housing projects as risky, making it difficult for initiatives like ecovillages to secure funding.
- Regulatory rigidity: Strict environmental laws and permitting systems focus on mitigation and compensation rather than experimentation with new human-nature relationships

4.9.2 Vision: What alternative SES could be?

Society is accustomed to viewing the environment as a system of interconnected objects. For example, a chair is seen as belonging to a table, with each object perceived as stable unless visibly altered. These relationships form what we commonly describe as systems. When humans interact with such systems, meanings emerge. This perspective also shapes

how we view nature: we see trees and shrubs and associate them with concepts such as forests or nature reserves. We seek to understand how natural elements relate to one another, categorising them into species, biotopes, habitats and ecosystems.

When changes occur in nature, we instinctively search for causes. Scientific inquiry is largely focused on uncovering causal relationships—how one element influences another within a system. This often reveals chains of change, where one shift triggers another. Our understanding of causality depends on observable relationships between things. Yet causality is not entirely free from human interpretation. In many cases, the true causes of change remain uncertain, leading us into the realm of hypotheses and assumptions. Our knowledge of what initiates change is limited, and the full complexity of causal relationships is often beyond our grasp. As a result, many natural objects are perceived as isolated and unchanging, with relationships only acknowledged when they are visibly active. Anything beyond that tends to fall outside our perceived scope of relevance.

A Holistic Alternative: Human-Inclusive Nature

An alternative way of relating to nature is practised by the societal partner in our case study. Their approach is rooted in holistic principles and highlights the potential for harmonious interaction between humans and the natural world. They work on the belief that everything in nature is interconnected, even if those connections are not immediately visible.

De Beuk has developed a concept called human-inclusive nature, which envisions humans not as external disruptors but as integral parts of the ecological web. This philosophy suggests that people can inhabit natural areas without degrading them, instead becoming embedded within the network of relationships that define those ecosystems.

Their interpretation of a Social-Ecological System (SES) differs from conventional models that underpin nature-inclusive frameworks. It moves beyond the standard “business-as-usual” approach and even beyond nature-inclusive thinking, towards a genuinely nature-positive SES. Below in table 9.3 we describe shortly the basic difference between SES in business as usual, a nature inclusive and a nature positive social ecological system.⁴⁷

Table 9.3. Fundamental differences in social ecological systems within and outside the high impact system

SES in Business as usual	Nature inclusive SES	Nature positive SES
One or two species are welcomed in adjusted architecture	Structures of nature can be fitted in the human habitat	People can fit in a natural habitat, if they adjust their lifestyle
Nature in leisure and parks	Living close to nature	Living is nature

⁴⁷ Table 3 is the product of interpretation by the writers of this report. It resonates with the framework of values approach in IPBES, see Luque-Lora, Rogelio, 2024. IPBES: *Three ways forward with frameworks of values*. Environmental Science and Policy 159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103827>

Significant influences of humans need to be compensated	The influence of humans is negative and should be restricted	The influence of humans can be positive and lead to a process of co-succession
Image of nature is restricted to protected species and habitats	Image of nature is based on what nature has been (memories and space for time substitutions)	Image of nature is physical and metaphysical, and is more about relations than objects
Focused on nature that adds value to projects	Focused on ecological patterns	Focused on ecological processes
Nature translated in norms and standards	Nature as opportunity for better lives	Nature translated in best ecological techniques
Innovations restricted to policy categories: circular and biobased materials	Transitional innovation in co-creation and under the control of the sector	Transformative innovation beyond the control of the sector

4.9.3 Discussion

A fundamentally different approach to understanding our environment shifts attention from static objects and their changes to the dynamic relationships that continuously shape both humans and nature. This perspective, known as relational ontology, suggests that instead of viewing things as fixed entities, we should consider the ever-evolving web of connections that defines our world.

Philosophers such as Bayo Akomolafe and Bruno Latour advocate this relational view, emphasising that our understanding of the environment is inherently limited. We cannot grasp all the relationships around us, and rather than isolating individual causal links, we should seek to understand the broader network of interactions. In this view, causality becomes secondary. Where relational understanding is incomplete, our minds fill in the gaps, much like recognising a face in a painting composed of dots.

In our case study, the Social-Ecological System (SES) is understood as a socially constructed framework of relationality, which varies across actors and groups. We adopt a relational ontology to explore the human–nature connection, viewing relationships not merely as links between entities but as discursive constructs that shape those entities themselves (Brijan, 2023). As Descola (2012) argues, without relationships, objects cease to exist.

SES is closely tied to worldviews. Holistic perspectives position humans within nature, influencing how we act in relation to the environment. These stand in contrast to Western dualism, which separates intellect and experience. Tim Ingold (2011) describes this divide as the “thinking mind” versus the “executive body,” critiquing the assumption that all action must originate in the brain. He suggests that Western thought often misinterprets other worldviews by attributing life or spirit to inert things, whereas many cultures perceive a dynamic sphere of relations in which all forms of life, whether person-like or object-like, interact and co-create existence.

Such holistic worldviews move beyond causality and empirical facts, using metaphors to explore relationships between humans and non-humans. Expressions such as “listening to the trees” or “a landscape has a memory” serve not as literal truths but as tools for understanding interconnectedness. According to Brijan, these metaphors are not intended to form a complete body of knowledge but to open space for exploring alternative worldviews. We observed this metaphorical intimacy in our case study.

Humans construct ontological boundaries to make sense of the cosmos, and these boundaries in turn shape lifestyles and societal structures (Joerstad, 2019). The most radical form of relational ontology would eliminate the distinction between humans and nature altogether. One way to transcend this divide is by granting personal rights to natural entities such as rivers and forests.

In this case study, we observed diverse expressions of cosmopolitical thinking, enriched with spiritual metaphors and holistic values. These perspectives often led to sustainable lifestyles and collective actions aimed at putting ecological ideologies into practice.

Despite operating within conventional causation frameworks, both De Beuk and the Province of Overijssel have assembled a bricolage of technical solutions, nature-inclusive measures and spiritual practices to bring their visions of living with nature to life. While regulatory systems, such as those governing permits for ecovillages and eco-housing, must be addressed thoroughly, they are only part of the picture. Beyond these rational structures, more intuitive and relational elements are essential to realising a genuinely nature-positive way of life.

4.9.4 References

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5 Discussion

Author: Julia Neidig

The nine case studies at the heart of BIOTraCes explore culturally, politically, economically and environmentally very diverse social-ecological systems in the European context, approaching biodiversity challenges from various angles. They are clustered and embedded into four high impact sectors, the urban, agriculture, forestry and water management sectors, that in themselves can be considered social-ecological systems constituted by diverse values, paradigms, rules, and norms that interact across sectors and scales. While the cases show context-specific differences, overarching sector narratives show many commonalities. Each of the cases offers insights into how biodiversity challenges and their related governance context remain a contested arena that is marked by power dynamics and imbalances, and in which niche innovators navigate structural barriers and lock-ins to achieve transformative and just changes in the local to global systems. While the scope and the targeted scale of the innovations differ across the cases, all the innovations examined in the cases aim to shift narratives of how biodiversity is approached, valued and governed, aiming for a better integration of plural values, worldviews, and knowledges that build on strong entanglements of the social and ecological into decision-making processes and actions.

In the following, we will discuss the key insights from the nine SES narratives, focusing on the need of (i) shifting the way we value, know and talk about biodiversity from instrumental towards relational approaches and of (ii) shifting power from higher scales and impact sectors towards local communities through co-governance of social-ecological systems. We will conclude with insights from approaching social-ecological systems as systems of relations and processes.

5.1 Shifting the way we value, know and talk about biodiversity from instrumental towards relational approaches in the social-ecological systems.

In most of the SES analyzed, local niche innovators encounter primarily instrumental framings of biodiversity that guide decision-making processes and economic structures. These framings build on a worldview that sees humans as separated or disconnected from nature, biodiversity is hence considered on element of the system, yet not through its relationships and processes with other system aspects. This becomes also apparent in the values dominating sector paradigms that are framed around productivity, efficiency, and overall human-centric approaches. Following, higher scale policies and high impact sectors often still follow framings of the biodiversity challenges under a logic of resource provision, e.g., through agricultural/ forestry production, land conversion for urbanization processes, or the provision of ecosystem services, e.g. through nature-based solutions beneficial for human well-being. Following, assessments of biodiversity challenges of high impact sectors heavily lean on scientific and technical knowledge, e.g., generated through indicator-based assessments.

The thick descriptions of the SES in this deliverable, however, show how niche innovators are increasingly putting forward plural perspectives aiming for redefining overarching human-nature relationships, by recentering care, local identity and traditions, place-attachment or multispecies narratives at the heart of the SES and its decision-making processes. Examples can be found in the Dutch cases that rethink human-nature relationships in urban developments under the lens of a nature-inclusive society or under

a Commons framework; in the Spanish case in which schoolyards are increasingly approached through the lens of care for the community and environment; or in the Italian and Portuguese cases in which local communities work together to reframe the local relationship with the territory to be much more rooted in local historic connections with the landscape.

This instrumental logic guiding most biodiversity framing and assessment exacerbates even more the direct drivers of biodiversity loss impacting the SES, such as intensive agriculture, forestry monocultures, river fragmentation or urbanization processes contributing to increasing droughts, pressures on river systems, heat islands, or soil degradation. While biodiversity challenges are increasingly recognized in the political arena and for instance through European frameworks and policies, such as the EU water framework, the common agricultural policy, the nature restoration regulation, or the EU mission for 100 climate-neutral and smart cities, they are nonetheless still embedded under an economic growth rationale. That is, local biodiversity innovations face logics of productivity, economic viability or infrastructure provision under the banner of increased livability.

In the local SES examined here, niche innovators ranging from social movements, researchers, to institutional actors, increasingly bring to the fore relational framings of biodiversity. These alternative framings of biodiversity can steer towards transforming the SES by giving space for new forms of human-nature relationships to emerge. This becomes visible, for instance, in the Italian and Portuguese case aiming for mainstreaming new agricultural practices through soil regenerations, such as syntrophic farming or permaculture, in the Hungarian case that shifts the way of knowing about the biodiversity challenges by focusing on traditional knowledge and its holders; the Romanian case connecting the local biodiversity and its landscape preservation to the local cultural heritage and local community economy structures; the Swedish and Lithuanian case that aims for community stewardship by connecting and building networks of small-scale forest owners or residents along the river; the two Dutch cases that tackle neoliberal urban processes by presenting alternatives to urban housing and consumption through connection urban communities with nature; or the Spanish case that tries to introduce relationality in teaching and learning practices. All these initiatives have in common that they aim to bring local community closer to their landscapes and local biodiversity by strengthening and deepening relationships with the community and nature, e.g. by embedding relational framings of human-nature interactions into the societal and policy discourse and practices.

The SES explored in BIOTraCes show clearly how the way we talk about/envision the biodiversity challenge is impacting how and what decisions are being made to govern different system components. Intentions to transform SES to systems characterized by inclusive relations, processes, and dynamics are challenged by the existence of competing narratives about society and nature. The Dutch ecovillage case exemplifies this as it points to a policy discourse that frames the decision of housing and nature policies as a question of housing versus nature, namely either providing housing through large-scale encroachments of land or the conservation of nature that impedes humans intervening in it. Instead of understanding nature and society as deeply connected, these compartmentalized governance approaches heavily draw on misconceptions of society and nature as competing entities. Following, narrative shifts are a key prerequisite for transformative change to occur. These narrative shifts need to happen across three

spheres, drawing on O'Brien et al. (2018)⁴⁸ three spheres of transformations. Shifting narratives at the practical sphere enables the implementation of alternative ways of doing, e.g., regenerative agricultural practices, new models of housing and conviviality through eco-villages or the Commons, or new ways of teaching and learning. Further, narrative shifts at the political sphere include new processes of decision-making, such as co-governance and other forms of participatory governance, including local communities' needs and perspectives at the heart of decision-making. Lastly, narrative shifts at the personal sphere are those that can enable a paradigm shift, e.g., by creating new collective imaginaries of the SES, as can be seen in the Portugues and Italian case that shift local narratives of the territory of one without future towards one that while being rooted in local histories and culture allows for new innovations and positive visions of the future.

5.2 Shifting power from higher scales and impact sectors towards local communities through co-governance of social-ecological systems.

Niche innovators trying to enact change in the SES typically are being faced with rigid institutional structures that favour public authorities and in different degrees private market actors in decision-making processes. That is, decision-making processes that shape and intervene in the SES are marked by power imbalances that complicate the implementation of innovations that are purely driven bottom-up. It further raises issues of justice in the decision-making processes, as often voices of vulnerable communities are only, if at all, considered at the margins. While this tendency of a power imbalance between institutional/ market actors on the one hand and bottom-up movements and marginalized communities on the other hand can be observed across all the BIOTraCes cases, the case studies differ in how these relationships between community, institutional, and market actors unfold. In all the case, conflict that arise between these actor groups never centres directly on biodiversity, but on questions of access to land and decision-making processes, that is, actors shaping the SES are constantly contesting and negotiating issues of distributional, recognitional, and procedural justice.

Overall, in the set of SES analysed in BIOTraCes, we identify four broad clusters of SES that describe how local communities and institutional actors interact and in which power dynamics unfold in different ways, ranging from absent or blocking to supportive or collaborative relationships. The first set of SES is marked by top-down technocratic processes that tend to overrun context-specificities and in which universal, yet context-detached solutions are being provided. This can be seen, e.g., in the Romanian, Hungarian or Lithuanian case where national actors enact European policies, e.g. of river renaturalization or agriculture, yet are detached from the local context and the implication this may have on the local SES. In those cases, researchers have played a core role in bringing together local marginalised communities to draw attention to local knowledges, values and perspectives and raise the local communities' awareness for the possible changes and impacts that may arise from top-down implemented policies.

⁴⁸ O'Brien, K. (2018). Is the 1.5 C target possible? Exploring the three spheres of transformation. *Current opinion in environmental sustainability*, 31, 153-160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.04.010>

In the second set of cases, high impact sector dominating paradigms are key in understanding power dynamics despite institutional awareness and in parts supportive higher-level policies. While these policies open up discursive space for alternative practice, they, however, are not yet imposing hard criteria that would enable the implementation of concrete transformative action as an economic rationale is often put forward as the *raison d'être*. Examples can here for example be found in the Dutch Foodpark case in which despite the city's discursive turn towards embracing common and degrowth approaches, market dynamics based on individual consumption patterns are still overrunning local efforts of building nature-connected community economy structures. In the Swedish case, the higher impact sector paradigms of large-scale monoculture forestry impede local actions aiming for continuous-cover forestry. To enact change in the local SES effectively, an all-encompassing paradigm change would be needed in the high impact sectors that shifts away from economic growth as the (only) guiding principle.

The third cluster of cases describes those SES in which niche innovators are supported by local institutional actors, and in which processes of multi-actor collaborations are either emerging or already in place. Examples are here for example the Spanish, the Dutch Province, and the Portuguese case. Niche innovators can here be found both inside local and regional institutions facilitating the implementation of demands and innovations put forward by societal actors, or through a true collaboration delivering resources to the societal actors in form of funds, land, accompanying activities, or knowledge to implement their innovations. Ideally, these cases develop processes of co-governance that build on inclusion and participation of marginalized voices.

In the last cluster, the niche innovators are facing institutions that are either absent or actively working against the biodiversity innovation. Following, innovations are driven by strong local collectives aiming for changes through small interventions in the system, while continuously being threatened by the status quo favoring practices driving biodiversity loss. A key example here is the Italian case, in which the local community collectively contests plans of macro photovoltaic parks through building renewable energy communities and is creating strong local networks across a variety of actors to counter institutional framings and practices. Here, the biodiversity innovation is merely driven bottom-up, which complicates the establishment of a governance structure enabling transformative change in the SES.

5.3 What we can learn from viewing social-ecological systems through a process-relational lens.

For the creation of this deliverable, we chose a process-relational approach of understanding SES as systems of relations composed of linkages, interactions and interdependencies of social and ecological domains. The main objective was hereby to zoom onto the interplay of values, knowledge, paradigms, rules, decision-making processes and ecological processes and how these components form and shape the current state of the SES embedded into high impact sectors. By zooming on to the processes and relationships occurring in the SES, the nine narratives are shedding light onto key barriers and enablers for transforming local SES towards systems that are both nature- and society-inclusive and can lead towards just and equitable futures. The nine SES narratives further show that the cases analysed here are not static systems but adapt and change as system components evolve. They further show how local SES and its niche innovators acting in it are strongly impacted and influenced by higher scale policies and paradigms.

The BIOTraCes cases draw attention to potential risks of a top-down technocratic approach, as e.g. strongly shaping the Lithuanian, Romanian, Hungarian, or Spanish case, that can create a gap between rigid institutional governance frameworks on the one side and dynamic processes that constantly change systems on the other side. This re-emphasizes the need for adaptive governance configurations that allow for creativity and flexibility to approach challenges in the local SES through context-specific solutions. Current top-down approaches are often too narrow and short-term focused which challenges the inclusion of local SES specific needs and realities into the governance structures.

Zooming onto the diverse social-ecological relations and how they have been valued by diverse actor groups could show that while social-ecological relations take diverse forms and shapes and build upon a plurality of values, mainstream framings and narratives tend to focus on a few dominant relations and values, often through the lens of instrumental values, while marginalising those values that build upon close-knit ties between the social and the ecological. For instance, while policies and high impact sector narratives often overemphasize values around cost-efficiency, productivity, and ecosystem services, expressions of care, stewardship, connectivity, or cultural identity only rarely find their way into cross-scale policies. However, those values are core motivations for niche innovators to enact change by implementing innovative actions and strategies for biodiversity. In this same line, there is a need to include other than technical and scientific knowledges into decision-making processes, as local and traditional knowledges are closely linked with how local communities value and think about the biodiversity challenge. The type of knowledge used to inform governance hence exemplifies another power relationship prevalent in the SES.

Following, power plays a key role in how the SES operates as it shapes the relationships existent in the SES. Power can take many forms and express itself e.g. in form of structural power of rules or rights, for example to land or infrastructures. It can take the shape of procedural power, defining who has access to and gets to participate in decision-making processes, including the agenda and hence topic setting. However, most and foremost, power can also take the form of relational power by forming local collectives and networks nurturing relationship in the community and with the land. It is this relational power that can drive transformative change locally and across scale.

5.4 Conclusion

This deliverable presented nine thick descriptions of social-ecological system narratives that shape the BIOTraCes case studies. By looking at the how the systems operate and how their different components are entangled in diverse relationships and processes, we showed the need for approaching transformative change inside and beyond these SES through changing social-ecological relations within the local context and community through relational practices, governance processes, and values and knowledges. Paying closer attention to how those relationships are formed locally and across scales can give important insights into current barriers and leverages for transformative change that allow for pluralizing, empowering, politicizing and embedding to occur in the local systems, the high impact sectors and higher policy scales. This deliverable with its nine SES narratives at its heart hence builds the base for the cross-case analysis conducted in BIOTraCes work package 3. Deliverable 3.1 specifically will identify major root causes, lock-ins and barriers and point to possible leverage points and amplification processes that can help to overcome those structural and imaginary lock-ins that currently hinder transformative change for biodiversity.